

Deliverable 8.1: Summary of findings (WP8)

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Executive Summary

This Deliverable 8.1 Summary of Findings forms part of Work Package 8 of the Horizon Europe UNTWIST project. It presents key insights drawn from the analysis of the UNTWIST survey dataset—one of the project’s central empirical contributions—designed to explore the role of gendered identities, perceived status loss, and political behaviour in contemporary Europe. The results offer valuable empirical evidence to assess core project hypotheses and support the development of grounded, country-specific policy recommendations.

The UNTWIST survey was conducted between October 2024 and January 2025 in six European countries: Denmark, Germany, Hungary, Spain, Switzerland, and the United Kingdom. The survey targeted adult population, with a total of 10,356 interviews collected through Computer-Assisted Web Interviewing (CAWI). After quality control, 9,698 valid cases were included in the final dataset. To ensure the inclusion of voters with lower prevalence in standard samples—specifically, those who support right-wing populist parties (RWPPs)—a targeted “Boost” sample was incorporated using a vote propensity question. Sampling was stratified by age, sex, education, and geographic region, with data weighting applied to maintain representativeness. The dataset, numeric in format and openly accessible on Zenodo (DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15083113>), follows FAIR data principles and is provided in CSV, SAV, and DTA formats. While technical documentation is openly available, microdata access is embargoed until March 31, 2026.

The structured questionnaire consisted of 60 closed-ended questions (over 100 response categories), covering political attitudes, voting behaviour, values, and socio-demographics. Fieldwork was divided into pilot, main, and Boost phases, with careful design and implementation across countries led by VERIAN and coordinated by DEUSTO. The survey employed a master version adapted to each national context and incorporated technical refinements after a soft launch. Overall, the instrument was designed to align with the theoretical framework and hypotheses set out in earlier stages of the project, particularly those concerning gender status perceptions, collective identity, and support for RWPPs.

A key area of focus in this report concerns individuals who perceive themselves as Losers of Feminism—those who believe that recent social, economic and cultural changes associated with feminism and gender equality have disadvantaged them. This includes both men and women who report status loss or threat, express anger about these experiences, and, in some cases, attribute responsibility to feminism. Though only a minority of respondents fall fully into this profile, the findings indicate that this narrative is significantly more common among RWPP voters, particularly men. These perceptions reflect broader feelings of gendered positional deprivation, in which individuals view their social status or symbolic role as having deteriorated, often in ways perceived as unfair. Indeed, men who identify as Losers of Feminism are 2.7 times more likely to report voting for a RWPP, while for those categorised as Losers of Globalisation, the figure is 2.4 times.

The analysis also shows that relative deprivation—both past (status loss) and future-oriented (status threat)—is reported by a significant proportion of respondents (34% and 51%, respectively), with men consistently more likely to report such feelings than women (with a gender gap of 4% and 2% across the two respective dimensions of relative deprivation). These perceptions are not only cognitive but also emotional: a notable share of respondents, particularly those facing economic strain, report anger linked to perceived status decline, supporting the idea that affective responses play a role in political mobilisation. RWPP voters, again, emerge as particularly susceptible to these perceptions, suggesting that their support is shaped by both material and symbolic dimensions of perceived injustice. Among men, these feelings of deprivation are not only driven by financial insecurity, but also by perceived contradictions between their gender identity and changing societal norms—especially among those with high household income and strong male GCI. For women, economic hardship remains the key driver, but higher education and strong female GCI can mitigate these feelings.

Another major finding concerns to gendered collective identity (GCI). The data reveal that around one-third of men and nearly half of women report some sense of collective identity aligned with their gender. However, the political alignment of these identities differs significantly: male GCI is most prevalent among RWPP voters, while female GCI is more common among supporters of left-wing parties. This is particularly pronounced among young male RWPP voters, where male GCI is especially strong, whereas female RWPP voters exhibit weaker gender identification than their left-leaning counterparts. These patterns reveal that gendered identity is not only unevenly distributed but ideologically structured, reinforcing the association between male collective identity and right-wing populist support. This distinction underscores the ideological structuring of collective gender identity in political attitudes and reinforces the need to understand radical right support as partly driven by collective identity concerns, particularly among men.

The analyses also identify two distinct logics of RWPP voting. The first is expressive: for some, voting for RWPP is a way to symbolically reject mainstream parties, liberal social changes, or perceived cultural marginalisation. The second is instrumental: many voters, especially women, cite the party's perceived strength or credibility in delivering policy outcomes as a reason for support. These logics are not mutually exclusive and often co-exist within individuals. Among RWPP voters, 8% are classified as expressive voters, while a substantially larger 48% are instrumental voters, suggesting that strategic considerations outweigh symbolic ones in aggregate terms. However, men are overrepresented in the expressive group, while women dominate the instrumental group, pointing to gendered logics of mobilisation. Importantly, while men tend to prioritise symbolic concerns and identity-related grievances, women's support for RWPPs is more often grounded in economic insecurity and institutional distrust.

Taken together, these findings contribute to a more nuanced understanding of political behaviour in contemporary Europe, particularly in relation to gender, inequality, and support for the right-wing populist parties. They highlight that attitudes often considered irrational or affective—such as resentment or symbolic grievance—are in fact rooted in consistent patterns of identity, perception, and experience. Importantly, the distinction between Losers of Globalisation and Losers of Feminism is empirically robust: our analyses show little overlap between the two, confirming that they capture distinct forms of perceived disadvantage affecting different segments of the electorate. This complexity must be considered in both academic analyses and in designing policy responses to democratic disaffection and polarisation.

List of abbreviations

CAWI	Computer-Assisted Web Interviewing
CSV	Comma-separated values
FAIR	FAIR principles (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability)
GCI	Gendered Collective Identity
GPD	Gendered Positional Deprivation
LF	Losers of Feminism
LG	Losers of Globalisation
LGBTQ+	Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual, Transgender, Queer +
MARPOR	Manifesto Project Database
ML	Mainstream Left
MR	Mainstream Right
NUTS	Nomenclature of Territorial Units for Statistics
PTV	Propensity to vote
RD	Relative Deprivation
RL	Radical Left
RWPP	Right-Wing Populist Parties

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1. Introduction

The Summary of findings is a deliverable that belongs to Work Package 8 of the Horizon Europe UNTWIST project. This document summarises and presents the main substantive findings obtained from the analyses of the UNTWIST survey data. The survey is one of the most important contributions of the project and provides valuable empirical evidence that allows the original hypotheses to be tested and, at the same time, helps to inform the development of policy recommendations.

The survey targeted all individuals aged 18 and over in Denmark, Germany, Hungary, Spain, Switzerland, and the United Kingdom, with data collected between October 23, 2024, and January 9, 2025. Conducted via Computer-Assisted Web Interviewing (CAWI), the study combined probabilistic and non-probabilistic panels to ensure representativeness across all countries, despite Denmark requiring supplemental non-probabilistic sampling. A total of 10,356 interviews were collected: 658 in a pilot stage, 8,419 in the main field, and 1,279 through a Boost aimed at overrepresenting voters of right-wing populist parties (RWPPs). Ultimately, 9,698 valid interviews formed the core dataset for analysis. Sampling design emphasized representativeness through stratification by sex, age, education, and geographic distribution using NUTS territorial units. VERIAN led fieldwork operations, with DEUSTO coordinating implementation across countries. The dataset, numeric in format and openly accessible on Zenodo (DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15083113>), follows FAIR data principles and is provided in CSV, SAV, and DTA formats. While technical documentation is openly available, microdata access is embargoed until March 31, 2026.

The structured questionnaire, modelled on a UK master version, contained 60 closed-ended questions with 110 response categories, covering socio-demographics, political attitudes, and behaviours aligned with the UNTWIST hypotheses¹. Fieldwork was divided into three phases: a pilot (July 26–September 11, 2024), the main field (October 23, 2024–January 9, 2025), and the Boost (December 6, 2024–January 9, 2025). A soft launch of 100 interviews per country preceded the main field, allowing technical refinements and calibration of sampling batches. In response to underrepresentation of RWPP voters, a targeted oversample was added using a propensity-to-vote question (Q5), identifying likely RWPP supporters with scores of 8–10 on a 0–10 scale. Quality control protocols excluded incomplete, low-effort, or unrepresentative responses. Response time was generally shorter in the Boost phase due to the use of experienced commercial panels. These multi-stage and rigorously managed

¹ Hypothesis 1: RWPP voters feel they have lost gender status, or they fear losing gender status in the future, and they blame feminism for that worsening. Hypothesis 2: Concerning sex and gender, participants might share at least two different logics for voting RWPP: an expressive logic (voting RWPP to express disagreement or anger with mainstream parties) and an instrumental logic (being able to bring about some change concerning their preferred policies). Hypothesis 3: Men and women hold different rationales regarding how they evaluate their gender status loss and regarding the motivations to vote for RWPP.

processes ensured high-quality, representative data for subsequent analysis of public attitudes and political behaviour across six European countries.

Deliverable 8.1 presents conclusions that may shed light on the original thesis of the ‘losers of feminism’. The thesis of ‘Losers of feminism’ refers to individuals—both men and women—who perceive themselves as disadvantaged by the social, economic, and cultural changes associated with feminist progress and gender equality, particularly those linked to the liberal transformation of Western democracies. Unlike the broader concepts of “losers of globalisation” this term focuses specifically on gender as a social cleavage. It captures the sentiment among some certain citizens that feminism and liberal policies have undermined their social roles, status, or opportunities, often in ways that feel unfair or exclusionary. These perceived losses may stem from shifts in family structures, labour market dynamics, or cultural narratives about gender norms. The UNTWIST project hypothesizes that such individuals are more likely to support right-wing populist parties, which they may view as representing their gendered concerns and offering symbolic or material redress. This perspective challenges traditional views of irrational populist voting, based on charisma or emotions, by emphasizing gender-based rational motivations. The results of this deliverable confirm that Losers of Feminism are most commonly found among RWPP voters, especially men Losers of Feminism, who are 4 times more likely to belong to having voted for RWPP as compared to those who are not.

The results and findings reported in this Deliverable 8.1 have been obtained through a quantitative approach using different analytical strategies. Specifically, descriptive and other multivariate analyses have been carried out. On the one hand, a comparative and cross-country perspective is adopted (analysing the six countries under study together in search of common patterns), and on the other, specific analyses of each national context are also presented to identify idiosyncratic patterns.

These findings provide empirical backing for several of the central hypotheses guiding the UNTWIST project. In particular, the results suggest that voters who support RWPP are more likely to perceive a loss of gender-related status, either as a decline already experienced or as a future threat. For some, these perceptions are accompanied by anger and a tendency to attribute blame to feminism, indicating the presence of a gendered grievance narrative. Overall, 9% and 18% of the population reported feeling anger in response to status loss or status threat, respectively, while a further 8% believed that the problems faced by people like them are caused by feminism. While only a minority of respondents fit the full profile of “Losers of Feminism” (0.9%), a more substantial 23.7% can be classified as experiencing “Gender Positional Deprivation”, both attitudes are more concentrated among RWPP voters—especially among men—than among those who support mainstream parties. Individuals classified as “Losers of Feminism” are 2.7 times more likely to vote for RWPPs, while those identified as “Losers of Globalisation” are 2.4 times more likely to do so. Notably, the “Losers of Feminism” profile is a stronger predictor of RWPP vote recall among men,

whereas the “Losers of Globalisation” profile appears more explanatory for women. Feelings of relative deprivation, both in cognitive and affective terms, appear especially prominent in this segment of the electorate, reinforcing the view that perceived social decline plays a meaningful role in radical right support.

The data also point to the coexistence of expressive and instrumental motivations among RWPP voters. Around 8% of individuals appear to use their support for RWPP as a way of expressing dissatisfaction with mainstream politics, particularly when this dissatisfaction is linked to perceived losses in cultural status or identity. A significantly larger share (48%), however, indicate a more strategic rationale, with vote choice linked to perceptions of party strength and credibility in delivering desired policy outcomes. This combination of expressive and instrumental logics reflects the complex ways in which feelings of exclusion, distrust, and pragmatic calculation can overlap in shaping political preferences.

Finally, the analysis highlights notable gender differences in how these dynamics unfold. Men and women do not appear to experience or interpret status loss in the same way. Male voters of RWPP are more likely to link these perceptions to masculinity and symbolic identity, since RWPP voters stand out scoring markedly higher male gendered collective identity than supporters of other party families, score noticeably lower (–0.22 to –0.38) on the same measure. Meanwhile, women tend to express dissatisfaction in relation to economic vulnerability and care-related burdens. Moreover, while male gendered collective identity is closely tied to RWPP alignment, female GCI is more strongly associated with support for left-wing parties and is generally linked to lower levels of radical right identification. These patterns suggest that support for RWPP is shaped by intersecting dimensions of gender, ideology, identity, and material experience, which affect men and women in distinct but equally important ways.

This document is structured as follows. First, we introduce the theoretical and methodological framework guiding the analysis, including key decisions regarding the classification of party families, the construction of dependent and independent variables, and guidance on how to interpret the figures presented throughout the deliverable. Section 2 provides descriptive analyses to contextualize the broader patterns in the data. Section 3 presents the results of international multivariate analyses, focusing only on statistically significant variables to construct concise and meaningful sociopolitical profiles related to key theoretical dimensions such as gendered identity, relative deprivation, and perceptions of inequality. Finally, the last section contains appendixes with the full model results, providing transparency and completeness for further reference.

The figures presented in this Deliverable fall into three categories: descriptive, inferential based on linear regression coefficients, and inferential based on odds ratios from binary logistic regressions. All analyses have been weighted using the variable *WgtMainBoost* to ensure the representativeness of the data. The descriptive plots provide an initial overview of the distribution of key variables, serving as a contextual basis for inferential analysis. In the

case of inferential graphs, each figure corresponds to a specific dependent variable, which is clearly stated and serves as the organising principle of the multivariate analysis section. This structure allows for the development of distinct analytical profiles based on each attitude, value, or sociopolitical behaviour under study. The regression-based graphs aim to summarise complex statistical relationships in a clear and accessible way, focusing on the practical interpretation of results rather than statistical jargon.

To enhance comprehension and ensure clarity for a broad readership—including those without formal training in statistics—each inferential graph displays only the independent variables or categories thereof that show a statistically significant relationship with the dependent variable. In the linear regression graphs, coefficients are interpreted as the average change in the dependent variable associated with each independent variable. In the logistic regression graphs, odds ratios express the likelihood of a particular outcome occurring, relative to a reference category. Odds ratios above 1 indicate a positive relationship—that is, a greater likelihood of perceiving status loss or threat—while values below 1 reflect a lower likelihood of experiencing these perceptions. These results should be understood as forming part of a broader effort to construct concise yet rigorous profiles of individuals who exhibit specific attitudes, values, or sociopolitical behaviours.

While the figures provide a focused and interpretable summary of the key statistically significant relationships, all full regression models—including variables that did not reach statistical significance—are comprehensively presented in the regression results tables found in the Appendices section. These tables allow interested readers to consult the complete modelling outputs, including coefficients, standard errors, and significance levels. This ensures full transparency of the analytical process and enables deeper exploration for those with more advanced statistical knowledge or specific interest in variables not highlighted in the graphical summaries.

There are also some important considerations when interpreting the findings of this deliverable. On the one hand, it is necessary to take into account the UNTWIST party scheme, which is based in MARPOR database and distinguishes 5 party families: right-wing populist parties, mainstream right, mainstream left, radical left, and others. Detailed information on this classification is available in the appendix (see Tables A1 and A2). The appendix also includes a comprehensive description of the key variables used in the analyses and their operationalisation. In addition, a summary table outlining the analytical strategies employed is provided (see table A5), which can serve as a useful guide for interpreting the results presented herein.

2. Descriptive analyses

This section presents the descriptive analyses of the UNTWIST project survey. It provides an overview of the main variables—both dependent and independent—that will be used in the later sections of this deliverable. Through a series of figures, we show the distributions and frequencies of these variables, both in total (aggregated) and separated by gender (disaggregated)². The goal is to offer a general picture of how respondents answered key survey questions related to identity, perceptions, and political attitudes. This allows us to better understand the shape and variation of the data before moving on to the multivariate analyses. The following is a series of descriptive plots representing the frequency distributions of the variables used in the inferential analyses and described in the previous section.

Figure 1 presents the distribution of vote recall as a function of the UNTWIST party coding scheme. This graph shows that mainstream parties are indeed the ones that respondents remember voting for the most in the last respective national elections in each country of the UNTWIST survey. Likewise, RWPPs are the third most likely to remember voting. In terms of gender differences, women are more likely to vote for Mainstream Left parties than men. In contrast, men voted in the last national elections more than women for the Mainstream Right, RWPP and Radical Left.

² For the purposes of this Deliverable 8.1, gender is analyzed using a binary approach (male/female) due to the very small number of respondents who identified as "Other" (n = 19; 0.20%) or selected "Rather not say" (n = 15; 0.16%), "Refusal" (n = 1), or "Don't Know" (n = 1). Together, these categories represent less than 0.4% of the total sample (n = 9,598) and are therefore not statistically robust enough to support meaningful disaggregated analysis. To preserve analytical clarity and comparability across figures and models, only responses from individuals identifying as male (n = 4,203) or female (n = 5,359) are included in gender-based breakdowns throughout this deliverable.

Figure 1: Vote recall to party families (%)

Figure 2 presents the distribution of Propensities to Vote (PTV) as a function of the UNTWIST party coding scheme. This plot shows that respondents report the highest propensity to vote for Mainstream Left parties, followed by Mainstream Right, Radical Left and finally RWPP. This trend largely holds for both men and women.

Figure: 2 Propensities to vote for party families (mean, 0-10)

Figures 3 and 4 below show the frequency distribution of the Gendered Collective Identity (GCI) indicators, both feminised (Female GCI) and masculinised (Male GCI). These two variables range from 0 (when the individual does not identify with male gender and any of the other identities at the same time) to 6 (when the individual identifies with male gender and all the identities presented at the same time). Identities provided are class, age, ethnicity, religion, sexual orientation, nationality. In both plots the proportion of respondents who manifest, to some degree, a gendered identity in line with their gender, i.e., sharing gender-specific issues in their daily lives, is considerable. Specifically, 46% of women report a feminised identity to some extent, while 32% of men report a masculinised identity. Not surprisingly, the proportion of respondents expressing a gendered identity other than their gender is very low: less than 2% for both men and women.

Figure 3: Female Gendered Collective Identity (GCI) (%)

Figure 4 Male Gendered Collective Identity (GCI) (%)

Figure 5 represents the distribution of respondents who report Past Relative Deprivation, i.e. feelings of Status Loss. Here it can be seen that one third of the respondents report feeling Status Loss and therefore consider that life in the past for people like them was better. In terms of gender differences, men report slightly more Status Loss than women.

Figure 5: Relative Deprivation (Past) - Cognitive Dimension – Status loss (%)

Figure 6 represents the distribution of respondents who report Future Relative Deprivation, i.e. feeling Status Threat. Here we observe that half of the respondents report

feeling Status Threat and therefore consider that life in the future for people like them will be worse. In terms of gender differences, along the same lines as with Status Loss, men report slightly more Status Threat than women.

Figure 6: Relative Deprivation (Future) - Cognitive Dimension – Status loss (%)

Figure 7 shows the proportion of survey respondents who report feeling angry in relation to their experience of Relative Deprivation. In this case, the focus is on the affective dimension of Past Relative Deprivation—specifically, anger in response to a perceived loss of status. What we observe here is that, although the difference is slight, men exhibit a marginally higher level of anger, with 9% expressing such feelings, compared to 8.2% of women.

Figure 7: Angry about Relative Deprivation (Past) - Affective Dimension (%)

Figure 8 depicts the proportion of a conceptually related variable, this time concerning anger elicited by a perceived threat to future status. In other words, the proportion of respondents who report feeling angry due to a situation of Relative Deprivation regarding future expectations. In this case, no notable gender differences are observed, with approximately one fifth of the sample expressing this form of anger.

Figure 8: Angry about Relative Deprivation (Future) - Affective Dimension (%)

Figure 9 represents the percentage distribution of social groups that UNTWIST respondents report as enjoying unfair advantages. The main social group reported as benefiting from unfair advantages in society is the Upper Classes (46.7%), with the second

most reported group being Refugees or Migrants (26.2%). Other groups that are also reported by respondents are Men, Elderly or LGBTQ+ people.

Figure 9: Unfairly Advantaged Social Groups (%)

In terms of identifying groups that benefit from unfair advantages in our society, Figure 10 shows considerable gender similarities and differences. On the one hand, in terms of similarities both the upper classes and immigrants are perceived as the groups most unfairly benefited by men and women. There are also specific social groups that, although with smaller percentage values, show considerable gender differences. Among these, the attribution of unfair advantages to men stands out, with 24.8% of women stating that men benefit from these unfair advantages in our society, while only 7.7% of men identify themselves as benefitting from unfair advantages. Furthermore, it is relevant that men identify LGBTQ+ people or religious minorities as beneficiaries of unfair advantages to a greater extent than women. In contrast, women identify working class people or disabled people as groups benefiting from unfair advantages in our society to a greater extent than men.

Figure 10 : Unfairly Advantaged Social Groups (% by gender)

Figure 11 displays the proportion of respondents characterised as *Losers of Feminism*, *Losers of Globalisation*, or individuals experiencing *Gendered Positional Deprivation* or *relative Deprivation*. These constructs—defined in greater detail in the introductory section—represent related yet analytically distinct concepts, each hypothesised as a potential predictor of voting for right-wing populist parties.

Losers of Feminism refers to individuals with a gendered collective identity (whether masculinised or feminised) who perceive that men or women are unfairly advantaged in society, report experiencing a loss or threat to their social status, express anger about it, and ultimately direct their anger and blame towards feminism. In contrast, *Gendered Positional Deprivation* refers to individuals who share a certain level of gendered collective identity (whether male or female) and perceive a loss of status or sense of threat, but without necessarily experiencing anger or assigning blame to feminism.

Losers of Globalisation refers to individuals who perceive a loss or threat to their socio-economic position, express anger about this situation, and direct their discontent toward domains associated with globalisation—such as capitalism, the global economy, economic elites, or the European Union. Finally, *Relative Deprivation* only includes individuals who show a perception of loss or threat to their status.

The results indicate that *Relative Deprivation* constitutes the most prevalent profile among respondents (with approximately 61% for the entire database and the same pattern by gender), followed by *Gendered Positional Deprivation* (24% in average for all respondents). In this regard, we observe a gender difference, with more women than men presenting this profile (26 % and 21%, respectively). In contrast, *Losers of Globalisation* and, especially, *Losers*

of Feminism, are markedly less represented within the survey sample. Furthermore, men are slightly overrepresented in these two profiles compared to women.

Figure 11: Losers of Feminism and Globalisation (%)

Figure 12 presents the distribution of perceived challenges reported by respondents, based on a survey question designed to capture gendered aspiration-based preferences. This question invited participants to identify up to five aspects of life they consider to be the most significant obstacles to achieving the kind of life they believe they should have or deserve. The results indicate that the most frequently cited challenges include access to a good healthcare system, affordable housing and public services, achieving work–life balance, fulfilling care responsibilities for children, the elderly, and dependants, as well as ensuring personal physical safety.

Figure 12: Perceived challenges (%)

Figure 13 also reveals relevant gender-based differences in the perception of such challenges. Although the overall distribution does not vary dramatically by gender—meaning that the core challenges identified at the aggregate level remain largely stable when disaggregated—certain distinctions are nonetheless evident. Men are more likely than women to perceive exercising civil rights and liberties, forming a family, and fulfilling the role of a good father as key challenges. In contrast, women more frequently identify work–family balance, access to affordable housing and social services, integration into the labour market, and particularly the responsibility of caring for children, older adults, and dependants as significant obstacles. These patterns suggest a gendered structure in the prioritisation of life aspirations and the constraints perceived in realising them.

Figure 13 : Perceived challenges (% by gender)

Figure 14 illustrates the proportion of respondents who identify, to some extent, as feeling close to a RWPP. The results clearly indicate that one quarter of the UNTWIST survey sample expresses some degree of identification or proximity with a RWPP. This segment of the sample reveals a notable gender disparity: 28.5% of male respondents report feeling close to a RWPP, compared to a somewhat lower proportion among women, at 23.5%.

Figure 14: Closeness to RWPP (%)

Figure 15 presents the level of instrumental voting across different party families, as defined by the UNTWIST party classification scheme³. The results show limited variation in the degree of instrumental voting across party families, with maximum differences of approximately one point on a ten-point scale. Moreover, no gender-based differences are observed in the relative ranking of party families by instrumental voting—that is, both men and women prioritise the same party families with similar intensity. The highest levels of instrumental voting are reported for the Mainstream parties, Mainstream Left, and Mainstream Right, followed by Right Populist Parties (RWPP), with Radical Left parties receiving the lowest average levels of instrumental motivation. Nonetheless, it is noteworthy that, across all party families, women consistently report lower levels of instrumental voting than men. This suggests a modest but consistent gender gap in how strategic or utility-based considerations shape voting behaviour.

³ In this analysis, the values displayed correspond to the average level of instrumental motivation for respondents who reported feeling close to more than one party within the same family. The category Other Parties has been excluded, as aggregating instrumental scores in this case would lack substantive interpretive value.

Figure 15: Instrumentality of voting to party families (means; 0-10)

Figure 16 illustrates the perceived credibility of each party family as a credible electoral option (trustworthy, competent, and capable of effectively implementing policies). The results indicate minimal variation in average credibility scores across party families. However, radical parties—particularly RWPP—exhibit slightly higher mean credibility compared to the rest. This marginally elevated credibility is more pronounced among male respondents, for whom the difference in perceived credibility reaches up to half a point (on a ten-point scale) when compared RWPP family with the *Mainstream Right* party family. This suggests that, while overall differences are modest, RWPP hold a somewhat stronger appeal in terms of perceived electoral credibility, especially among men.

Figure 16: Credibility of voting to party families (means; 0-10)

Figure 17 presents the perceived strength of the different party families in terms of their capacity to influence or advance policies. The most notable finding is the considerably lower level of perceived strength attributed to *Radical Left* parties compared to the other party families. In contrast, respondents assign similar levels of strength to both Mainstream and *Right-Wing Populist Party* families. These patterns hold consistently across gender, with both male and female respondents exhibiting comparable assessments of party family strength.

Figure 17: Strength of voting to party families (means; 0-10)

3. Cross-country multivariate analyses

This section of the report presents a series of multivariate analyses, each focused on a specific dependent variable that was previously examined in the descriptive analysis. The section is structured around individual subsections, each dedicated to a single dependent variable (or a set of dependent variables stemming from one survey question or several related survey questions) that captures a particular aspect of social attitudes, values, or socio-political behaviour. For each of these variables, we estimate a set of statistical models designed to identify and interpret the main socio-demographic and attitudinal predictors associated with the phenomenon in question.

Specifically, three weighted regression models are estimated for each dependent variable. The first model includes the full sample and provides an aggregate overview of the relationships between the independent variables and the outcome under study. The other two models, plotted together, are disaggregated by gender: one includes only male respondents, and the other only female respondents. Importantly, all models are weighted to ensure that the results are representative of the underlying population structure and to correct for potential sampling biases. This means that each observation contributes to the model in proportion to its relevance or prevalence in the population, rather than being treated as statistically equal.

In general, the set of independent variables (or explanatory variables) included in the models remains consistent across the different specifications, allowing for comparability of findings between the overall population and the gender-specific subgroups. However, in some cases, certain variables are either added, removed, or recoded. These modifications respond to analytical necessities—for example, to improve model fit, address measurement issues, or align more closely with our theoretical expectations and research hypotheses. Any such changes are explicitly noted and carefully justified within the subsection 1.3, so that readers can understand the reasoning behind these adjustments. In subsection 1.2 reader may also find a detailed explanation of how dependent and independent variables have been operationalised—that is, how it has been defined and measured in practical terms—and the rationale for its use in the analysis. This ensures conceptual clarity and makes the interpretation of results transparent to readers.

The presentation of results in each subsection follows a consistent structure:

1. First, we present a coefficient plot or odds ratio plot showing the variables included in the model⁴. This visual summary provides an accessible and interpretable snapshot of relevant predictors.

⁴ Although the figures offer a clear and concise summary of the key relationships, the complete regression models results are thoroughly documented in the regression results tables located in the Appendices. These

2. Secondly, we offer a narrative description of the typical profile or typology of individuals who are most strongly associated with the phenomenon under study, based on the patterns emerging from the regression models. This helps to translate complex statistical output into a more intuitive understanding of which social groups are more likely to exhibit certain attitudes, values, or behaviours.
3. Finally, we replicate the structure applied in steps one and two, but using a single comparative coefficient plot that simultaneously displays two separate regression models disaggregated by gender—one for men and one for women. This visual representation allows for direct comparison of the predictors across gender-specific models. As with the overall model, this plot is accompanied by a concise narrative summary that outlines the typical profile of men and women most strongly associated with the outcome in each gender group. The accompanying description aims to contextualise the statistical results and enhance interpretability by identifying the key socio-demographic, attitudinal, or behavioural characteristics that differentiate male and female patterns within the phenomenon under study.

This structured approach enables a comprehensive and nuanced understanding of the factors associated with each dependent variable, while also maintaining transparency and methodological rigour throughout the analysis.

3.1. Gendered Collective Identity

This section investigates the prevalence and distribution of gendered collective identities (GCI) across the electorate, distinguishing between male and female GCI and examining their political, demographic, and socio-economic correlates. Overall, male GCI is significantly more common among voters of RWPP, particularly among younger men, and less prevalent among those supporting left-wing parties (ML and RL). In contrast, female GCI is more salient among left-wing voters—especially among women with higher education and better economic conditions—while RWPP supporters report lower levels of female GCI overall.

RWPP voters are thus markedly more likely to express a male gendered collective identity than voters of mainstream left or right parties. This distinction is most evident among men, where RWPP support strongly correlates with male GCI, while among women, RWPP

tables provide readers with access to the full model outputs, including coefficients, standard errors, and significance levels, ensuring transparency in the analytical process and allowing for more in-depth exploration by those with advanced statistical expertise or a particular interest in less-emphasized variables.

voters show comparatively weaker gender identification than their left-wing counterparts. Moreover, identity salience diverges by gender: male GCI dominates among RWPP voters, while female GCI is more pronounced among ML and RL voters, particularly women. These patterns highlight the ideological and gendered structuring of collective identity in contemporary party electorates.

Profile of individuals displaying Male Gendered Collective Identity (overall)

Figure 18: Coefficients predicting male Gendered Collective Identity (GCI) for the overall database

The profile of individuals associated with higher scores on male GCI, across the full dataset (i.e., without separating by sex), reveals a distinct sociopolitical and demographic pattern (see Figure 18). First, individuals who support radical left (RL) and mainstream left (ML) parties show significantly lower levels of male GCI compared to those supporting Right-wing Populist Parties (RWPP). This points to a concentration of masculinised GCI attitudes within the right-wing populist electorate.

Furthermore, gender plays a significant role: the negative coefficient for women indicates that, holding all else constant, women are significantly less likely than men to exhibit

male GCI. In terms of age, individuals aged 40-54, 55–64 and especially 65 and older display lower levels of male GCI compared to those aged 18–24, suggesting that these attitudes are more prominent among younger cohorts. Regarding employment status, those who are disabled or working part-time tend to have lower levels of male GCI than those employed full-time. Interestingly, individuals who are separated show lower GCI scores than their married counterparts. Finally, there is also a marginal effect associated with religion, whereby individuals identifying as non-Christian (compared to Roman Catholics) are also associated with lower male GCI.

Profile of individuals displaying Male Gendered Collective Identity (men)

Figure 19: Coefficients predicting male Gendered Collective Identity (GCI) among men

Figure 19 shows which factors are associated with male GCI among men only. First, men who support radical left (RL) parties are significantly less likely to express a male GCI compared to those supporting right-wing populist parties (RWPP). Those aligned with mainstream right (MR) also show a slight decrease, although the effect is smaller. Regarding employment status, men who are disabled, working part-time, or who report military service tend to show higher levels of male GCI than those in full-time employment. The association with military service is particularly strong, although the wide confidence interval suggests some uncertainty around this estimate.

When it comes to religious background, both Jewish men and those classified as non-Christian (compared to Roman Catholics) exhibit lower levels of male GCI, though these effects are moderate. Age is another important factor: men aged 55–64 and especially 65+ tend to show lower male GCI than younger men aged 18–24. This suggests that male Gendered Collective Identity is more common among younger male cohorts. Finally, men who are separated (compared to those who are married) also show slightly lower levels of male GCI.

Profile of individuals displaying Female Gendered Collective Identity (overall)

Figure 20: Coefficients predicting female Gendered Collective Identity (GCI) for the overall database

Support for mainstream left (ML) and radical left (RL) parties is positively associated with stronger expressions of female GCI compared to support for right-wing populist parties (RWPP), as shown by Figure 20. This suggests that female GCI is more common among women who align with the political left. Gender also plays an important role: women are significantly more likely than men to express female GCI, as shown by the large positive coefficient for “Female (vs. Male).” When it comes to age, older women—specifically those aged 55–64 and 65+—are significantly less likely to express female GCI than younger women aged 18–24. Regarding employment, women who are disabled show lower levels of female GCI compared to those working more than 30 hours per week. Finally, women who say they are living with financial difficulty report significantly lower levels of female GCI compared to those living comfortably, highlighting the role of economic stress in shaping gendered identities.

Figure 21: Profile of individuals displaying Female Gendered Collective Identity (women)

Figure 21 shows that political orientation plays a clear role among women: support for mainstream left (ML), radical left (RL), and other parties is associated with higher levels of female Gendered Collective Identity (GCI) compared to support for right-wing populist parties (RWPP).

Regarding education, women with medium and especially higher education are significantly more likely to express female GCI than those with lower education levels. In terms of economic conditions, women who report coping or living with some financial difficulty show lower levels of female GCI compared to those living comfortably, suggesting that material insecurity may reduce identification with female GCI. Looking at age, older women — especially those aged over 55 — show lower levels of female GCI than younger women aged (18–24). Finally, women with disabilities and female military personnel show significantly lower and higher levels of female GCI, respectively, compared to those working full-time.

3.2. Relative Deprivation (cognitive dimension)

This section explores the cognitive dimension of relative deprivation, focusing on individuals' perceptions of status loss and status threat. The findings reveal that these perceptions are most strongly associated with material hardship, with individuals reporting difficult or very difficult financial conditions being significantly more likely to experience both forms of relative deprivation. Political orientation also plays a key role: RWPP voters are considerably more likely to perceive status loss and threat than supporters of mainstream left (ML), mainstream right (MR), or radical left (RL) parties. This suggests that feelings of downward mobility and social decline are particularly concentrated within the radical right electorate.

When examining gender differences, both male and female RWPP voters report elevated levels of relative deprivation, but the intensity and correlates vary. Among men, status loss and threat are especially associated with strong male gendered identity and even high household income, pointing to a perceived dissonance between expectations and reality. For women, economic insecurity remains the strongest predictor, but high female GCI and higher education appear to buffer against these perceptions. Overall, while RWPP voters of both genders are more likely to experience relative deprivation than their mainstream counterparts, the mechanisms and social profiles underpinning these perceptions differ notably between men and women.

Figure 22: Odds ratios predicting RD status loss (overall database)

Figure 22 represents a logistic regression model predicting relative deprivation (RD) status loss. Odds ratios above 1 indicate a higher likelihood of perceiving status loss, while values below 1 reflect a lower likelihood.

The strongest positive predictors of RD status loss are related to income dissatisfaction. Individuals who report living “very difficult” or “difficult” financial situations have significantly higher odds of perceiving a downward shift in their status compared to those living comfortably. Even those who say they are simply “coping” also show elevated odds. These findings suggest that material hardship is a critical driver of perceived status decline.

In contrast, several factors are associated with lower odds of experiencing RD status loss. People who support mainstream right (MR), mainstream left (ML), radical left (RL), or other political parties —compared to right-wing populist parties (RWPP)— are less likely to report status loss.

Sociodemographic characteristics also matter. Women are slightly less likely than men to perceive a loss of status. Being part-time employed, student, retired, or unemployed is similarly linked to lower odds of RD status loss compared to full-time workers — potentially because these groups have adjusted expectations about mobility and work-related identity. Age also plays a role: individuals aged 65 and older are less likely to perceive status loss than

younger adults, possibly due to a longer-term perspective or generational differences in expectations. Finally, a family-related variable acts as protective factor: those who place themselves higher on the social scale than the average are less likely to perceive a loss of status. This suggests that subjective social position may buffer individuals against feelings of decline.

Figure 23: Odds ratios predicting RD status loss (by gender)

As shown by Figure 23, for men the feeling of relative deprivation focused on the past is similar to the general pattern discussed above. Again, those who report living “very difficult” or “difficult” financial situations have significantly higher odds of perceiving RD status loss compared to those living comfortably. Furthermore, we find that those men who identify more with their own gender and other identifies (male GCI) express a greater perception of relative deprivation focused on the past. Also, contrary to what one might expect, we find that being above average in terms of household incomes increases the likelihood of feeling relative deprivation status loss among men.

On the other hand, several factors reduce the chances of perceiving status loss: being older (especially ages 55 and up), voting for mainstream left (ML) or mainstream right (MR) parties instead of right-wing populist parties, placing oneself higher on the social scale. All these characteristics are linked to a lower likelihood of reporting status decline among men.

Similarly, women who report living in “difficult” or “very difficult” financial conditions — compared to those living comfortably — are significantly more likely to feel that they have experienced a loss of status. In contrast, several factors are linked to lower odds of perceiving status loss among women. These include voting for the mainstream left (ML), mainstream right (MR), or radical left (RL) instead of right-wing populist parties (RWPP). Women with higher levels of education and those who score higher on the female GCI index also show a lower likelihood of reporting status loss.

Figure 24: Odds ratios predicting RD status threat (overall database)

Focusing on the overall database (that is, considering both men and women), we find that the material sphere is a key factor predicting relative deprivation status threat (see Figure 24). People who report living in “copying”, “difficult” or “very difficult” financial situations are clearly more likely to feel status threat, compared to those who declare living “comfortably”. Additionally, individuals who place themselves lower on the social scale, and score lower on the female GCI index and religiosity, are also less likely to feel threatened.

Figure 25: Odds ratios predicting RD status threat (by gender)

Figure 25 shows odds ratios predicting RD status threat by gender. Again, men who report living in economic hardship report higher levels of status threat, compared to individuals who declare they live comfortably. In addition, men with higher household income and those with higher scores on the male GCI index also show greater odds of feeling status threat. On the other hand, some characteristics are associated with lower odds of perceiving threat. Men who vote for the mainstream left (ML) or mainstream right (MR) parties — compared to those who support right-wing populist parties (RWPP) — are less likely to feel threatened. The same is true for older men, specifically those aged over 55 compared to younger men. Finally, men who place themselves higher on the social scale (over average) are also less likely to report a sense of threat.

As well as for men, women who report living in economic hardship report higher levels of status threat, compared to those who declare they live comfortably. In addition, Jewish women and those in a cohabiting relationship report higher levels of status threat (compared to Roman Catholic women and those who are married). Additionally, other factors appear to mitigate the perception of status threat among women. These include supporting the mainstream left (ML), mainstream right (MR), or radical left (RL) parties compared to right-wing populist parties (RWPP). Women working less than 30 hours a week, those with higher

education, and those who are retired (vs. full-time workers) also report lower likelihood of perceiving future status loss.

3.3. Relative Deprivation (affective dimension)

This section explores the affective dimension of relative deprivation, focusing on who is most likely to experience anger in response to perceived status loss and threat. The clearest and most consistent predictor is economic hardship. Individuals facing financial difficulties—whether coping, in difficulty, or in very difficult conditions—are significantly more likely to report anger about both forms of relative deprivation. The more severe the hardship, the greater the probability of experiencing anger.

Voting for right-wing populist parties (RWPP) is also strongly linked to anger. RWPP supporters are more likely to report anger than voters aligned with the mainstream left or right, suggesting a stronger affective dimension within the populist electorate. Gender differences are also evident in the predictors of anger. While both male and female RWPP voters report higher levels of anger, men's anger is linked more to occupational context and perceived status dissonance, while women's anger is more closely tied to worsening financial conditions. For women, mainstream political alignment and retirement appear to buffer against anger.

In sum, the findings show that anger about relative deprivation is most prevalent among economically strained individuals and RWPP voters, with gendered differences in how and why this anger emerges. While both men and women in the RWPP electorate report higher levels of affective deprivation, the social and political dynamics underpinning that anger are not identical.

Figure 26: Odds ratios predicting affective RD status loss (overall database)

As shown by figure 26, individuals with greater economic difficulties (vs. those who live comfortably) are more likely to show anger regarding their status loss. Conversely, voting for mainstream left and right (vs. supporting right-wing populist parties), and self-locating below the average in the social scale are negatively associated with angry evaluation of status loss.

Figure 27: Odds ratios predicting affective RD status loss (by gender)

Men facing economic difficulties (compared to those living comfortably) are more likely to experience anger related to status loss. Other factors that are positively associated with anger include having a military employment background (compared to full-time work). In contrast, certain factors reduce the likelihood of experiencing anger over status loss. These include voting for mainstream left or right parties (as opposed to right-wing populist parties) and placing oneself below the average on social scale.

On the other hand, several factors are associated with women expressing anger about status loss. Women who report being “coping”, “in difficulty”, or “in very difficult” financial situations — compared to those living comfortably— are significantly more likely to feel angry about status loss. The more severe the financial hardship, the higher the odds of experiencing this anger.

In contrast, several factors are associated with a lower likelihood of reporting anger. These include voting for the mainstream left (ML), mainstream right (MR), or other parties compared to right-wing populist parties (RWPP). Furthermore, women who are retired (vs. those working full-time) show lower levels of anger regarding status loss.

Figure 28: Odds ratios predicting affective RD status threat (overall database)

The figure 28 shows how being in a precarious economic position (vs. those living comfortably) increases the likelihood of experiencing anger about status threat. Conversely, factors like voting for the mainstream left and right (compared to those who vote for the RWPP) or being protestant, Eastern Orthodox, Eastern religions or other religions (vs. Roman-Catholic) decrease the probability of anger.

Figure 29: Odds ratios predicting affective RD status threat (by gender)

Figure 29 displays odds ratios predicting anger about status threat, differentiating by gender. We observe that, for both men and women, being in a precarious economic situation (versus those living comfortably) increases the likelihood of experiencing anger about status threat. Likewise, being in the military significantly increases the odds for men, just as being Jewish does for women (compared to working full-time and being Roman Catholic, respectively). Conversely, voting for the mainstream left and right, and other parties, reduces the odds for women, while voting for the mainstream left reduces the odds for men.

3.4. Unfairly Advantaged Social Groups

This section examines which social groups are perceived as enjoying unfair advantages in contemporary society, with particular attention to how such perceptions are shaped by political orientation—especially among voters of radical right-wing populist parties (RWPPs)—and gender. Overall, RWPP supporters are markedly more inclined than voters of other parties to identify certain groups as unfairly privileged, notably women, immigrants, young people, ethnic and religious minorities, and LGBTQ+ individuals. These beliefs reflect not merely ideological positioning, but broader social anxieties structured around perceptions

of status loss, redistribution, and cultural change. Crucially, these perceptions are not uniform: gender plays a decisive role in determining both the intensity and the specific targets of such views.

Among RWPP voters, men consistently emerge as the most likely to perceive a broad range of social groups as undeservedly advantaged. They tend to attribute unfair privileges to women, immigrants, the young, and sexual minorities—frequently framed through narratives of reversed discrimination or social overcompensation. Female RWPP voters, while not immune to such sentiments, display a more selective pattern of grievance. They are comparatively less likely to view immigrants or LGBTQ+ individuals as unfairly advantaged, and more likely to express concern over the perceived status of young people or religious minorities. This divergence suggests that men and women, even within the same political camp, interpret social hierarchies and group competition through distinct lenses—shaped by their own positional experiences and perceived vulnerabilities.

Besides, the belief that "people like me deserve more" further intensifies these attitudes, especially among male respondents, and is strongly linked to perceptions of immigrants and the working class as undeservingly privileged. Economic precarity appears to heighten this sense of relative deprivation across genders, yet its effect is more pronounced and generalised among men. These findings point to a broader pattern in which gendered notions of deservingness, merit, and social recognition interact with political ideology to shape how individuals interpret intergroup dynamics.

In sum, the perception of unfair group advantage is not randomly distributed but systematically mediated by political affiliation, gender, and subjective status positioning. RWPP voters —particularly men— articulate the most expansive and consistent sense of group-based grievance, aligning with broader patterns of populist politics that construct social conflict in zero-sum terms. Women, while also susceptible to such narratives, tend to voice them more selectively and often in relation to different groups. These patterns underscore the importance of integrating both gender and political behaviour into analyses of contemporary grievance-based politics.

Overall dataset

Figure 30: Odds ratios predicting perceived unfair advantages enjoyed by men (overall dataset)

In Figure 30, we observe that believing people like you deserve more decreases the likelihood of thinking men enjoy unfair advantages. At the same time, other factors increase the probability of this perception: for example, voting for the mainstream left, mainstream right, radical left, or other parties (vs. supporting RWPP), being female (vs. male), having non-zero female or male CGI levels, having high education level (compared to those with lower level), or being divorced (vs. married).

Figure 31: Odds ratios predicting perceived unfair advantages enjoyed by women (overall dataset)

Figure 31 shows that being a woman is related to a higher probability of thinking women enjoy unfair advantages. Other factors are also positively associated with this idea: having non-zero male CGI, thinking people like you deserve more, and being Jewish (vs. Roman-Catholic). On the other hand, voting for the mainstream left and right, the radical left, or other parties (compared to supporting RWPPs) decreases the likelihood of thinking women have unfair advantages.

Figure 32: Odds ratios predicting perceived unfair advantages enjoyed by young people (overall dataset)

Figure 32 shows that the factors associated with a higher probability of thinking young people have unfair advantages are being female, having having above-average personal income, working part-time (vs. working full-time), being Protestant (vs. Roman-Catholic), and believing people like you deserve more. Conversely, having education levels between medium-high reduces the likelihood of believing that young people are unfairly advantaged.

Figure 33: Odds ratios predicting perceived unfair advantages enjoyed by older people (overall dataset)

As can be seen in Figure 33, being over 40 significantly decreases the likelihood of thinking older people have unfair advantages (compared to those under 24). Likewise, having medium-high level education level also decreases this probability (vs. those with low level).

Figure 34: Odds ratios predicting perceived unfair advantages enjoyed by LGBTQ+ (overall dataset)

As we can see in Figure 34, having a non-zero CGI level increases the probability of thinking that LGBTQ+ individuals have unfair advantages. This means an intersectional masculinized identity is linked to greater prejudice towards the LGBTQ+ community. At the same time, voting for the mainstream left, mainstream right, radical left, or other parties (versus supporting RWPPs) decreases this belief, as well as being woman.

Figure 35: Odds ratios predicting perceived unfair advantages enjoyed by heterosexual people (overall dataset)

On one hand, in Figure 35 we see that being female is associated with a lower probability of thinking heterosexual people have privileges. On the other, being single (vs. being married) and having a non-zero female CGI level increase the likelihood of having this perception.

Figure 36: Odds ratios predicting perceived unfair advantages enjoyed by immigrants (overall dataset)

Figure 36 shows that having non-zero female GCI and voting for the mainstream left, mainstream right, radical left, and other parties (compared to those who vote for RWPPs) reduce the probability of thinking that immigrants enjoy unfair advantages. On the other hand, being self-employed and being in a precarious economic situation—categories "coping" and "difficult"—increase the likelihood of experiencing this perception (in comparison with those working full-time and those living comfortably).

Figure 37: Odds ratios predicting perceived unfair advantages enjoyed by working class people (overall dataset)

As can be seen in Figure 37, several factors are related to a higher propensity to think that the working class is unfairly advantaged: being female, being separated (vs. being married), being in a very difficult economic situation (vs. those living comfortably), and believing that people like you deserve more than others. Conversely, other characteristics are associated with negative levels of prejudice toward the working class: being in a civil union (vs. being married), being in military service (vs. working full-time), professing a religion classified as "Other non-Christian" (vs. Roman Catholics), having a non-zero female CGI identity, and voting for the radical left (vs. voting for RWPPs).

Figure 38: Odds ratios predicting perceived unfair advantages enjoyed by middle class people (overall dataset)

Figure 38 shows that several sociodemographic factors reduce the likelihood of thinking middle classes have unfair advantages: being female, having an high education level, serving in the military (vs. working full-time), and in religious terms, being Eastern Orthodox or Protestant (vs. Roman Catholics). On the other hand, being in a very difficult economic situation (compared to those living comfortably) increases the likelihood of having this perception.

Figure 39: Odds ratios predicting perceived unfair advantages enjoyed by upper class people (overall dataset)

Figure 39 shows the predictors of thinking that upper classes enjoy unfair advantages. On one hand, voting for other parties, the mainstream left, and the radical left (in particular, with very high odds ratios for the latter two options) is significantly associated with this prejudice against the upper classes (compared to those who vote for RWPPs). Additionally, other factors are also positively and significantly associated: being widowed (vs. married), having the "other jobs" category (vs. full-time work), and having a non-zero feminized CGI identity. Conversely, other characteristics are negatively associated, predicting lower levels of this perception: being female, being in military service, and being self-employed (vs. working full-time), self-locating below average in the social scale, and thinking that people like you deserve more.

Figure 40: Odds ratios predicting perceived unfair advantages enjoyed by religious minorities (overall dataset)

Being female and voting for the mainstream left, the radical right, and other parties (versus supporting RWPP) are associated with a higher probability of thinking that religious minorities enjoy unfair advantages, as shown in Figure 40. In turn, factors such as being "other Christian" or having no religious denomination (vs. Roman Catholic), believing that people like you deserve more, and being over 65 years old (vs. Those under 24) are positively associated with this attitude.

Figure 41: Odds ratios predicting perceived unfair advantages enjoyed by religious majorities (overall dataset)

Regarding religious majorities, we find that being female and being separated (vs. married) reduces the perception that these groups have unfair benefits. At the same time, being in military service (vs. working full-time), being Muslim, other types of Catholics, or not self-identifying religiously (vs. Roman Catholics), and voting for the radical left (vs. supporting RWPPs) increases the likelihood of thinking that religious majorities are advantaged.

Figure 42: Odds ratios predicting perceived unfair advantages enjoyed by non-disabled people (overall dataset)

As might be expected, being disabled is associated with higher levels of perception that non-disabled people are unfairly advantaged. In this regard, other factors also follow the same trend: being in a cohabiting relationship (vs. married), working part-time, or retired (vs. full-time), being in a difficult or very difficult economic situation (vs. living comfortably), and voting for the mainstream left or the radical left (vs. supporting RWPPs).

Figure 43: Odds ratios predicting perceived unfair advantages enjoyed by disabled people (overall dataset)

We see in Figure 43 that being female and being separated are associated with higher levels of perception that disabled people are unfairly advantaged. Conversely, being in a civil union (vs. married), being between 25 or +64 years old (vs. those under 25), working part-time, being unemployed (vs. working full-time), having non-zero female GCI, and voting for the radical left (vs. supporting RWPPs) are associated with lower levels of this perception.

Figure 44: Odds ratios predicting perceived unfair advantages enjoyed by ethnic minorities (overall dataset)

Regarding the perception of unfair advantages for ethnic minorities (see Figure 101), we only find that voting for the mainstream left, the radical left, or other parties (vs. supporting RWPPs) reduces this perception. Also, that in religious terms, being in the "other" category (vs. Roman Catholics) increases this probability.

Results by gender

Figure 45: Odds ratios predicting perceived unfair advantages enjoyed by men (by gender)

It is relevant that Figure 45 shows there are significant political behavior predictors when it comes to thinking men are unfairly advantaged: in particular, voting for the mainstream left, mainstream right, radical right, and other parties has a positive effect on this perception for women (vs. those who vote for RWPP), while for men, this same effect only operates with the radical left. Furthermore, we observe that having non-zero female CGI increases the likelihood of holding this belief in both men and women.

Figure 46: Odds ratios predicting perceived unfair advantages enjoyed by women (by gender)

When referring to the perception that women are unfairly advantaged (Figure 46), we find that for men, voting for the mainstream right, mainstream left, radical right, and other parties (vs. voting for RWPP) decreases the probability of having this perception. The same for women who are 55-64 years old (vs. 18-24) and with medium-high education level. Likewise, for women who are Jewish, this effect is positive (compared to those who are Roman Catholic), although with a very large confidence interval.

Figure 47: Odds ratios predicting perceived unfair advantages enjoyed by young people (by gender)

Regarding Figure 47, related to prejudice concerning young people, we find few significant predictors. For example, men with high education level tend to think this to a lesser extent than those with low education level.

Figure 48: Odds ratios predicting perceived unfair advantages enjoyed by older people (by gender)

We observe in Figure 48 that it is relevant that men who vote for the mainstream left and radical left are more likely to think that older people are advantaged (compared to those who vote for RWPPs). Likewise, the effect is negative among men who are in an economic situation categorised as "coping" (vs. those living comfortably) and positive among women who are in an economic situation conceptualised as "difficult" (vs. those living comfortably).

Figure 49: Odds ratios predicting perceived unfair advantages enjoyed by LGBTQ+ (by gender)

The most interesting finding of Figure 49 is that for both men and women, voting for the mainstream left and the radical right decreases the likelihood of thinking that the LGBTQ+ community is unfairly advantaged (vs. those who vote for RWPP). This effect is also the same for women who vote for the mainstream right.

Figure 50: Odds ratios predicting perceived unfair advantages enjoyed by heterosexual people (by gender)

We find that men with a certain level of female CGI are more likely to think that heterosexual people are unfairly advantaged. The same applies to women in military service (vs. full-time) and men with a religious denomination of "other non-Christian" (vs. Roman Catholic), though these with very large confidence intervals.

Figure 51: Odds ratios predicting perceived unfair advantages enjoyed by immigrants (by gender)

We find a gender similarity: both men and women who vote for the mainstream right, mainstream left, radical left, or other parties are less likely to think that immigrants are unfairly advantaged than those who support RWPPs. A gender similarity is also seen in the "own deservingness" variable, where both men and women who think they deserve more tend to think this more of immigrants. Similarly, men in precarious economic situations (categories "coping" and "difficult") are more likely to have this perception (compared to those living comfortably).

Figure 52: Odds ratios predicting perceived unfair advantages enjoyed by working class people (by gender)

Interestingly, both men and women who support the radical left are less likely to think that the working class is unfairly advantaged (compared to those who vote for RWPPs). Similarly, men with a certain female CGI level show the same effect. On the other hand, men in a "very difficult" economic situation exhibit a positive and very pronounced effect on this belief (vs. those living comfortably), although with a very large confidence interval.

Figure 53: Odds ratios predicting perceived unfair advantages enjoyed by middle class people (by gender)

In Figure 53 (which shows the odds ratios predicting unfair advantages for the middle class), we find little relevant information, and it's mainly related to religion: we see a positive effect for women with Eastern religions and a negative effect for women with "No denomination"; and at the same time, a positive effect for Jewish men (all compared to Roman Catholic).

Figure 54: Odds ratios predicting perceived unfair advantages enjoyed by upper class people (by gender)

Figure 54 presents a stable pattern by gender: voting for the mainstream left, radical left, or other parties increases the likelihood of thinking that upper classes are unfairly advantaged (vs. those who vote for RWPP). In turn, the effect is negative among self-employed women or women in military service (vs. full-time work) and positive among women with a certain female CGI level.

Figure 55: Odds ratios predicting perceived unfair advantages enjoyed by religious minorities (by gender)

Figure 56: Odds ratios predicting perceived unfair advantages enjoyed by religious minorities (by gender)

We find that individuals, both men and women, who believe that people like themselves deserve more than others, are more likely to think that religious minorities are unfairly advantaged. On the other hand, this effect is negative for men and women who vote for the mainstream left and radical left (vs. supporting RWPPs), and also for men who support the mainstream right.

Figure 57: Odds ratios predicting perceived unfair advantages enjoyed by non-disabled people (by gender)

As might be expected, both disabled men and women are more likely to believe that non-disabled people are unfairly advantaged. The effect is negative among women who believe they deserve more than others.

Figure 58: Odds ratios predicting perceived unfair advantages enjoyed by disabled people (by gender)

Regarding Figure 58, the only significant and positive effect is that of women in military service, who are more likely to think that disabled people are unfairly advantaged, and that of women who vote for the radical left (with a negative effect on this perception).

Figure 59: Odds ratios predicting perceived unfair advantages enjoyed by ethnic minorities (by gender)

From the perspective of political behavior, we find a stable gender pattern: voting for the mainstream left, radical left, and other parties (vs. voting for RWPP) decreases the probability of thinking that ethnic minorities are unfairly advantaged. This is also true for men who support the mainstream right and for women who are separated (vs. married). On the other hand, positive effects are found among women in military service (vs. full-time) and Jewish women (vs. Roman Catholics), although with very large intervals.

3.5. Losers of Feminism and Gendered Positional Deprivation

This section explores the perceptions of gender-based positional deprivation, focusing on individuals who feel they are Losers of Feminism.

Two analytical profiles are considered: Losers of Feminism and Gendered Positional Deprivation. *Losers of Feminism* refers to individuals with a gendered collective identity (whether masculinised or feminised) who perceive that men or women are unfairly advantaged in society, report experiencing a loss or threat to their social status, express anger

about it, and ultimately direct their anger and blame towards feminism. In contrast, *Gendered Positional Deprivation* refers to individuals who share a certain level of gendered collective identity (whether male or female) and perceive a loss of status or sense of threat, but without necessarily experiencing anger or assigning blame to feminism.

When disaggregated by gender, distinct patterns emerge. Women are more likely to experience Gendered Positional Deprivation when they have higher education levels and belong to Eastern Orthodox religion or Other religion, while older age reduces this likelihood. Among men, individuals within the 40-54 age cohort are less likely to experience this situation compared to young people. In addition, in terms of sociodemographic factors, women with a certain level of female GCI or who belong to Other Christian faiths, Islam, or Eastern religions are more prone to be Losers of Feminism than Catholic women.

Overall dataset

Figure 60: Odds ratios predicting Gendered Positional Deprivation (overall dataset)

Figure 60 shows results from logistic regression model predicting profile of Gendered Positional Deprivation for the overall dataset. We find that being woman, with high education level and having the category “Other” regarding religion (vs. Roman Catholic) positively correlates with experiencing Gendered Positional Deprivation.

In addition, several factors are negatively associated with this profile. People who are disabled (compared to those working full-time) or who vote for the mainstream left (ML) or mainstream right (MR) parties — rather than right-wing populist parties (RWPP) — are less likely to fall into this group.

Figure 61: Odds ratios predicting Losers of Feminism (overall dataset)

The figure above (Figure 61) displays the findings for profile of Losers of Feminism concept. Positive associations are observed for individuals who belong to Eastern religions (compared to Roman Catholics). In addition, higher scores on both the female and male Gendered Collective Identity (GCI) indexes are also linked to a greater likelihood of being part of this profile.

On the other hand, several factors are negatively associated with this profile. These include voting for the mainstream left (ML) or mainstream right (MR) (as opposed to RWPP, as well as being divorced (vs. married) or be part of the age group 40-54 (compared to young cohort between 18-24 years old). Individuals with these characteristics are less likely to belong to the Losers of Feminism profile.

Results by gender

Figure 62: Odds ratios predicting Gendered Positional Deprivation (by gender)

Figure 62 presents the profile of individuals within the Gendered Positional Deprivation category, by gender. We see that for women, the Gendered Positional Deprivation profile significantly includes women who vote for the radical left or other parties (in contrast to those who support RWPPs), while for men, voting for the mainstream right or mainstream left decreases the likelihood of experiencing this profile. This points to a clear link between voting for RWPP and male respondents with regard to the Gendered Positional Deprivation profile.

Figure 63: Odds ratios predicting Losers of Feminism (by gender)

Figure 63 shows the profile of men and women regarding the concept of Losers of Feminism. We find very interesting gender patterns. On one hand, men who vote for mainstream left or right parties are less likely to be Losers of Feminism than those who support RWPPs. On the other hand, women with a non-zero level of female or male GCI and who belong to Other Christian faiths, Islam, or Eastern religions are more prone to be Losers of Feminism than Catholic women.

Differences between men and women

This section examines which social and political profiles are more likely to perceive men or women as socially aggrieved groups. Patterns of perceived group grievance differ

notably by gender and political affiliation. While men who support RWPPs and who express gendered identities are more likely to view men as an aggrieved group, this perception is significantly less common among those who vote for mainstream or left-leaning parties. Besides, the belief that women are disadvantaged is more prevalent among women—particularly those with stronger gendered identities—and among voters of the mainstream and radical left. These trends suggest that identification with an “aggrieved ingroup” is shaped less by gender alone than by the intersection of political orientation, along with economic insecurity and gender identity salience.

Figure 64: Odds ratios predicting perceiving Men as aggrieved (overall dataset)

Figure 64 indicates that for the overall sample, being female and voting for the mainstream right, mainstream left, radical left, and other parties (vs. supporting RWPPs) is associated with a lower propensity to think that men are aggrieved. On the other hand, the effect on the dependent variable is positive and significant for those in a "difficult" economic situation (vs. those living comfortably) and among individuals with a certain level of GCI.

Figure 65: Odds ratios predicting perceiving Women as aggrieved (overall dataset)

In Figure 65, we find very similar results to those in Figure 64, but in the opposite direction. Thus, we see that being female, having a certain level of female GCI, and voting for the mainstream left, radical left, or other parties (vs. voting for RWPPs) increases the probability of perceiving that women are aggrieved.

Figure 66: Odds ratios predicting perceiving Men as aggrieved (by gender)

Regarding electoral behaviour, we find the following gender similarity: for both men and women, voting for the mainstream left and radical left decreases the likelihood of thinking that men are aggrieved. Likewise, there are particularities: the effect is also negative for men who vote for the mainstream right or other parties (compared to those who support RWPP). It's also relevant and interesting that men with a certain level of feminized GCI identity have a higher probability of thinking that men are disadvantaged.

Figure 67: Odds ratios predicting perceiving Women as aggrieved (by gender)

Regarding Figure 67, first, we observe that being a woman with female GCI increases the propensity to think that women are an aggrieved group. Similarly, voting for the mainstream left and other parties increases this propensity for both men and women. Furthermore, voting for the radical left does so in the case of men (compared to those who support RWPPs).

3.6. Losers of Globalisation

This section explores the profile of individuals who fall into the categories of Relative Deprivation and Losers of Globalisation, using predictive models to identify key differentiating factors. The analysis reveals that those who feel left behind by globalisation tend to be individuals experiencing economic hardship, and are significantly more likely to support radical right-wing populist parties (RWPP) than mainstream political alternatives. Importantly, gendered patterns emerge: while economic precarity consistently increases the likelihood of perceived deprivation for both men and women, the effect of material hardship on the likelihood of being categorised as a Loser of Globalisation is particularly pronounced among women. These findings point to a possible gendered dimension in how grievances related to globalisation are experienced and politicised, shaped by the intersection of socioeconomic vulnerability and broader identity dynamics.

Figure 68: Odds ratios predicting perceiving Relative Deprivation (overall dataset)

Figure 68 displays the profile of individuals who fall into the "Relative Deprivation" category. On one hand, we find that these are individuals with economic difficulties (to a greater extent than people in a comfortable economic situation). On the other hand, we see

that being female, being below average on the social scale, and voting for the mainstream right, mainstream left, or other parties (instead of voting for RWPP) decreases the likelihood of experiencing "Relative Deprivation."

Figure 69: Odds ratios predicting perceiving Relative Deprivation (by gender)

Figure 69 shows the profile of individuals experiencing Relative Deprivation, differentiated by gender. In this regard, we see similarities for both genders: both men and women who experience a precarious economic situation are more likely to experience Relative Deprivation; furthermore, both men and women who vote for the mainstream right and the mainstream left are less likely to fall into this profile compared to those respondents who support RWPP.

Figure 70: Odds ratios predicting perceiving Losers of Globalisation (overall dataset)

Figure 70 shows that the profile of an individual categorized as a Loser of Globalisation is someone in a difficult economic situation (compared to those living comfortably) who is more likely to vote for the RWPP than for the mainstream right, mainstream left, radical left, or other parties.

Figure 71: Odds ratios predicting perceiving Losers of Globalisation (by gender)

Finally, the examination of the Losers of Globalisation profile gives us very interesting nuances. In particular, we observe that economic hardship has a positive effect only for women (in comparison with those living comfortably). That is, women who are facing economic hardship are more likely to be Losers of Globalisation compared to those living comfortably. This can lead us to hypothesize about a gender dimension in the Losers of Globalization profile, referring how the confluence of gender and material hardship takes interact. On the other hand, both men and women who vote for the mainstream left are less likely to be Losers of Globalization than RWPP voters. The same applies to men who support the mainstream right and the radical left.

3.7. Losers of Feminism and Losers of Globalisation

This subsection presents a series of heatmaps displaying bivariate correlation matrices between the various indicators previously introduced under the conceptual umbrellas of Losers of Globalisation and Losers of Feminism, including the intermediate constructs of Relative Deprivation (RD) and Gendered Positional Deprivation (GPD). These visualisations aim to explore the degree of empirical overlap between these constructs, thereby addressing the extent to which they capture related or distinct forms of relative deprivation. In doing so, the analysis probes whether the notion of Losers of Feminism—particularly in its operationalised form as GPD—represents a gender-sensitive extension of the Losers of Globalisation framework, or whether it constitutes a qualitatively different phenomenon altogether. The results indicate that correlations between these measures are generally weak or non-existent, particularly between the two primary constructs (Losers of Globalisation and Losers of Feminism), suggesting that they capture distinct forms of perceived disadvantage and refer to different segments of the population affected by divergent grievances and sociopolitical dynamics.

Figure 72: Correlation coefficients between different profiles (overall dataset)

Figure 72 presents a heatmap displaying the results of bivariate correlations between the various measures of Losers of Feminism and Losers of Globalisation discussed earlier. Overall, the figure indicates that these two constructs are only weakly associated, suggesting that they capture distinct sociopolitical dynamics and reflect different types of citizen grievances. The strongest relationship observed is between Relative Deprivation (RD) and

Gendered Positional Deprivation (GPD), with a correlation coefficient of 0.45. This moderate association is to be expected, given that GPD can be understood as a gender-sensitive operationalisation of RD—both constructs tap into a sense of status-based resentment, though GPD explicitly integrates a gendered dimension.

By contrast, the remaining associations are negligible. Particularly striking is the near-zero correlation between the core constructs Losers of Feminism and Losers of Globalisation. This finding reinforces the view that these measures represent fundamentally different manifestations of positional discontent, likely rooted in divergent social identities, political orientations, and perceived sources of disadvantage. In sum, while RD and GPD exhibit a meaningful conceptual and empirical overlap, the broader pattern of results points to a general lack of convergence between the feminist and globalisation-related grievance frameworks.

Figure 73: Correlation coefficients between different profiles (men)

Figure 73 presents the same heatmap but restricted to the male subsample. The results indicate that the magnitude of the associations closely mirrors the patterns observed in the aggregated data. Of particular note is that the correlation between Losers of Feminism and Losers of Globalisation is marginally higher among men. Similarly, the association between Gendered Positional Deprivation and Losers of Feminism—that is, between men who experience gendered forms of relative deprivation and those who not only report such deprivation but also attribute it to feminism and perceive women as enjoying unfair advantages—is slightly stronger than in the full sample.

Figure 74: Correlation coefficients between different profiles (women)

Figure 74 shows the same heatmap, this time limited to the female subsample. Here, correlations between variables are generally weaker than those in the aggregated data. The most analytically significant finding is the correlation of 0 between Losers of Feminism and Losers of Globalisation. This indicates that, for women, the experience of relative deprivation linked to globalisation—such as economic change, perceived unfair advantages for migrants, and resentment toward institutions or elites—is entirely unrelated to the gendered experience of deprivation attributed to feminism or perceived advantages held by either men or women. Among the female subsample, then, these appear to constitute wholly distinct domains of perceived injustice.

3.8. Perceived Challenges

Achieving a life that one values or considers deserved is rarely a matter of individual effort alone. Across diverse social groups, structural factors—ranging from economic insecurity to gendered expectations—shape how individuals perceive their capacity to pursue life goals. The barriers people face are not distributed evenly, and the narratives of difficulty vary depending on one's positionality within broader systems of power and change. This section examines the profiles of individuals more likely to perceive thirteen distinct challenges as significant in their lives. While each domain (or challenge) reflects specific concerns—ranging from employment and housing to family life, care responsibilities, and social recognition—common patterns emerge across them.

Age consistently shapes perceptions: younger individuals are more likely to report difficulty in areas tied to life-course transitions such as education, labour market entry, and family formation, whereas older individuals express more concern in domains such as physical safety and healthcare access. Economic conditions also play a central role. Those with lower personal income, those who report coping or struggling to meet their needs, and those who place themselves lower on the social scale tend to express more perceived challenges across all issues.

Collective gender identity and related social dimensions are also important. Individuals with less masculinised identities more frequently perceive difficulties in balancing work and care, gaining respect, and engaging in parenting, suggesting differentiated norms and expectations. Those characterised as Losers of Globalisation are more likely to report difficulty in domains tied to institutional access and economic stability. Meanwhile, Gendered Positional Deprivation tends to predict concern in areas where traditional gender hierarchies and caregiving expectations intersect.

Political orientation introduces further variation. Voters aligned with radical left or mainstream left parties often report heightened sensitivity to structural or institutional challenges, while those aligned with RWPP express concern over symbolic and identity-related domains such as family formation, respect, and civil rights. These patterns, however, diverge further when disaggregated by gender, as RWPP-aligned men and women reveal distinct configurations of perceived barriers, shaped by their specific location in the intersection of ideology, gender, and socioeconomic conditions.

The profiles that follow offer a detailed, model-based view of how different segments of the population understand and experience obstacles to achieving a desirable life, across thirteen key areas of perceived challenge.

Profile of individuals displaying higher probabilities of perceiving integrating successfully into the labour market as a challenge

Figure 75: Odds ratios predicting the selection of integrating successfully into the labour market as a challenge (overall dataset)

Figure 75 presents the profile of individuals who perceive successful integration into the labour market as a significant challenge is characterised by being younger, often at an early stage in their professional careers. This suggests that limited prior experience in the labour market is associated with greater awareness of the difficulties involved in integration. Those who are unemployed also show higher levels of concern, reflecting their direct engagement with the challenge, while retired individuals and those in other active labour categories report lower concern, consistent with their more stable employment situations.

A similar pattern appears with socioeconomic status. This profile includes individuals with lower household income and those who report being unable to live comfortably on their current earnings, indicating heightened sensitivity to labour market barriers. At the same time, those with household incomes above the average also display a higher likelihood of considering this a problem, suggesting that concern about integration extends beyond the most economically vulnerable. Additionally, the perception of this issue is statistically more prevalent among those with higher levels of formal education, pointing to a more critical or informed assessment of labour market challenges.

Lastly, this profile is further characterised by lower levels of masculinised collective identity, by Losers of Globalisation, and voters of the Radical Left, highlighting values and experiences that increase awareness of structural inequalities in the labour market.

Figure 76: Odds ratios predicting the selection of integrating successfully into the labour market as a challenge (by gender)

Figure 76 displays the profile of men and women who perceive successful integration into the labour market as a significant challenge is defined by several clear features. The male profile is characterised by younger men, especially those in early adulthood rather than more mature young adults, as well as men who are retired rather than actively employed full-time, reflecting stages of life where concerns about labour market re-entry or entry are more salient.

Financially, this profile includes men who are managing with limited resources—those who describe themselves as struggling or just coping on their current income—and men with lower-than-average personal income. Interestingly, it also encompasses men living in households with higher-than-average household income, illustrating the relevance of relative deprivation and social comparison in shaping perceptions of labour market barriers. Additionally, men Losers of Globalisation demonstrate a heightened awareness of the challenges involved in achieving secure labour market integration.

Among women, the profile is similarly nuanced. It is marked by younger women who, more than older or even young adult women, perceive significant barriers to successful integration, highlighting a pronounced age-related sensitivity to labour market entry conditions. Women with higher or intermediate levels of education are also more likely to

identify this challenge, suggesting that greater formal education is linked to heightened recognition of structural barriers.

Employment status is another defining factor for this profile: it comprises unemployed women in particular, but also those in full-time employment to a lesser extent, underscoring the role of direct engagement with the labour market in shaping perceptions. Socioeconomic characteristics remain central: women with below-average personal income and those who locate themselves lower on the social scale are especially likely to express this concern, reflecting a clear awareness of the obstacles tied to their economic position.

Finally, political orientation further characterises this profile: women who support the Radical Left are more likely to perceive integration into the labour market as a significant challenge, reflecting ideological frameworks that emphasise structural inequalities and advocate for more inclusive labour market policies.

Profile of individuals displaying higher probabilities of perceiving accessing affordable housing, social services, and other goods as a challenge

Figure 77: Odds ratios predicting the selection of accessing affordable housing, social services, and other goods as a challenge (overall dataset)

Figure 77 depicts the profile of individuals who perceive access to affordable housing, social services, and other essential goods as a significant challenge is characterised by several distinct and interrelated features. Individuals in full-time employment display a higher likelihood of perceiving this issue as a challenge compared to those in part-time employment, the unemployed, the self-employed, or homemakers. This appears counterintuitive but may reflect the fact that full-time employment does not always guarantee sufficient income or access to social support, especially in contexts of high cost of living or limited public provision.

Marital status also shapes this profile: it is marked by individuals who are single, divorced, or cohabiting, reflecting household arrangements that may be more exposed to economic vulnerability or less supported by pooled resources. Household composition further differentiates this group, with those raising fewer children than the average family demonstrating particular sensitivity to challenges in accessing basic goods and services.

Economic and financial circumstances are among the most powerful predictors. Respondents with personal below-average income and those who report having difficulty making ends meet or merely coping on their present income are significantly more likely to perceive this as a pressing challenge. Additionally, those who self-identify lower on the social

scale and individuals Losers of Globalisation are similarly more likely to report concern in this domain, reflecting both material disadvantage and perceived social marginalisation.

In terms of political orientation, those who vote for parties on the Left, including both the ML and the RL, show a higher probability of perceiving access to affordable housing and services as a major challenge, compared to those who support RWPP. This may indicate differing sensitivities or ideological framings of structural inequality and public provision across the political spectrum.

Figure 78: Odds ratios predicting the selection of accessing affordable housing, social services, and other goods as a challenge (by gender)

Figure 78 presents the profile of men and women who perceive accessing affordable housing, social services, and other essential goods as a significant challenge reveals both shared patterns and meaningful differences between genders. Among men, this profile is characterised by those in full-time employment, underscoring how formal labour market attachment can coincide with heightened sensitivity to economic pressures—particularly in contexts where stable work does not ensure adequate income or access to social support. Men with smaller family structures, reflected in having fewer children than the average, also show greater awareness of potential vulnerability in meeting essential needs.

Economic and financial circumstances are central to this male profile. It includes men experiencing financial strain and those who position themselves lower on the social scale, highlighting the role of both material conditions and subjective social status in shaping these perceptions. Men who experience Gendered Positional Deprivation and forms of exclusion associated with globalisation further illustrate the importance of perceived economic marginalisation in driving concern over access to basic goods and services. Politically, this profile is more prevalent among men who support the Mainstream Left or Radical Left, indicating ideological orientations attuned to recognising and addressing structural inequalities and advocating for stronger public provision.

Among women, some features align with those observed in men, while others show distinctive patterns. Employment-related pattern displays a notable gender difference: women in full-time employment are more likely to perceive difficulties accessing affordable housing and essential goods when compared to housemakers. This gender difference suggests that for women in particular, formal labour market integration does not necessarily shield against economic strain, reflecting added pressures they may face in balancing employment with other responsibilities or navigating persistent income gaps. Women also demonstrate a similar sensitivity to economic hardship: those who report struggling or just coping on their income, and those who place themselves lower on the social scale, are especially likely to perceive this issue as pressing.

Partnership status distinctly shapes the female profile: single, divorced, cohabiting, and widowed women stand out for their heightened awareness of barriers to accessing affordable housing and services, suggesting that these household arrangements may be associated with greater economic vulnerability or reduced access to shared resources. As with men, women with fewer children than average also display increased concern, pointing to the role of family structure in perceptions of economic security. Politically, women who support the Mainstream Left or Radical Left similarly express stronger concern about these challenges, reflecting ideological commitments to addressing social inequality and expanding public provision.

Overall, as shown in Figure 78 the profile of those most attuned to challenges in accessing affordable housing and essential services spans both men and women in full-time employment, those experiencing economic hardship or social marginalisation, and individuals with left-leaning political orientations—while gendered differences in family, partnership structures and men as Losers of Globalisation further nuance how these concerns are experienced.

Profile of individuals displaying higher probabilities of perceiving balancing paid employment and family duties as a challenge

Figure 79: Odds ratios predicting the selection of balancing paid employment and family duties as a challenge (overall dataset)

Figure 79 outlines the profile of individuals who perceive balancing paid employment and family duties as a significant challenge is shaped by clear patterns across employment status, socio-demographics, family composition, financial conditions, identity markers, and political orientation.

Employment status plays a central role in defining this profile. Individuals in full-time employment are more likely to perceive this challenge compared to those who are self-employed, in part-time work, homemakers, retired, or disabled. This suggests that full-time roles, with their greater time demands and reduced flexibility, intensify awareness of the strain involved in balancing work and family responsibilities, even though they may offer greater income stability.

Financial circumstances are another strong differentiator. The profile includes those finding it difficult or just coping on their present income, who are more likely to report this challenge than those living comfortably. Similarly, individuals with below-average personal income show higher concern, highlighting how managing economic insecurity alongside family obligations amplifies the perceived difficulty of achieving work–family balance.

Marital status further distinguishes this group. Married individuals are more likely to report difficulties balancing work and family life compared to those who are single or

divorced. This pattern likely reflects the greater caregiving responsibilities often embedded within marriage and shared household structures. Family composition is also relevant: individuals with more children than the average are more likely to perceive this challenge, indicating that larger family size intensifies the demands of coordinating work and caregiving roles.

Age is another defining factor. Young adults are more likely to report this concern than adolescents or younger individuals, suggesting that the challenge becomes more salient during life stages typically associated with childrearing and career consolidation. Overall, younger people (including young adults and adolescents taken together) show higher likelihood of perceiving balancing work and family duties as a challenge than those over 55, indicating that this issue is especially pressing in earlier stages of the life course when work and family responsibilities most overlap.

Educational attainment also shapes this profile. Individuals with upper secondary education are more likely to perceive this challenge than those with only primary education or no formal education, reflecting higher expectations of work–life integration and greater engagement in dual-role settings among the more educated.

Gendered identity is another important element. Individuals with a less masculinised gendered collective identity are more likely to perceive this challenge, compared to those with stronger identification with traditional masculine roles. This suggests that those less aligned with traditional masculinity may experience or acknowledge a greater sense of responsibility for family-related duties.

Finally, political orientation provides further insight. Individuals who support Mainstream Right and Mainstream Left parties are more likely to report difficulties balancing work and family life than those who support RWPP. This may reflect ideological commitments that place greater emphasis on work–life balance, gender equality in caregiving responsibilities, and institutional support for reconciling work and family roles.

Figure 80: Odds ratios predicting the selection of balancing paid employment and family duties as a challenge (by gender)

Figure 80 displays the profile of men and women who perceive balancing paid employment and family duties as a significant challenge displays both shared features and important gender-specific differences. Among men, this profile is characterised by those in full-time employment, who are more likely to report this challenge than those in part-time work, retired, or disabled. This highlights how intensive labour market participation can amplify the strain of simultaneously managing work and family roles.

Marital status further defines this male profile, with married men more likely to perceive difficulty balancing paid work and family responsibilities than their single or divorced counterparts. Family size also plays an important role: men with more children than the average are more likely to report this challenge, reflecting increased caregiving demands within larger family units. Age also differentiates this profile: older and elder men are more likely to perceive this challenge than younger men, indicating that concern about balancing work and family roles can intensify with age, perhaps as responsibilities evolve over the life course.

Gendered identity is a significant dimension as well: men with a less masculinised Gendered Collective Identity (GCI) are more likely to perceive difficulty in balancing work and care responsibilities than those with stronger alignment with traditional masculine roles, suggesting greater engagement with or recognition of family-related duties.

Among women, the profile is both broader and marked by some distinct patterns. Employment status remains a consistent predictor: women in full-time employment are more likely to report this challenge than those in part-time roles, self-employment, unemployment, or those who are disabled or in military service. This underscores that full-time work, with its demanding schedules and reduced flexibility, intensifies awareness of work–family tensions for women even more markedly than for men. Age plays a role as well: younger women are more likely to express concern than elder women, consistent with life-stage differences where childrearing and career consolidation overlap most intensively.

Financial conditions strongly shape the female profile. Women finding it difficult or just coping on their current income are more likely to perceive this challenge than those living comfortably, highlighting how economic insecurity adds pressure to balancing work and care.

Education is also an important differentiator among women: those with higher levels of education are more likely to perceive this challenge than those with primary or no formal education—a pattern not observed among men. This may reflect higher expectations for work–life integration and greater involvement in dual-role settings among more educated women. A particularly notable female-specific pattern emerges in relation to household income. Women living in households with above-average income are more likely to report this challenge, suggesting that dual-earner arrangements, greater involvement in professional careers, or heightened expectations around achieving work–life balance may make this issue especially salient for women in higher-income households.

Profile of individuals displaying higher probabilities of perceiving caring for children, elderly relatives, and other dependents as a challenge

Figure 81: Odds ratios predicting the selection of caring for children, elderly relatives, and other dependents as a challenge (overall dataset)

Figure 81 presents that the profile of individuals with a higher probability of perceiving caring for children, elderly relatives, and other dependents as a significant challenge is defined by clear patterns across age, family composition, marital status, and political orientation. Age is a central differentiator. This profile is characterised by adults over 24, who are more likely to perceive caregiving as a challenge than those under 24. This reflects the greater likelihood of assuming caregiving responsibilities as people establish their own households, form families, or take on caring roles for relatives.

Family composition also plays an important role. Individuals with more children than the average are more likely to perceive caregiving as a challenge, highlighting the practical demands and increased caregiving burdens associated with larger family sizes. Marital status further shapes this profile. Married individuals are more likely to report difficulties related to caregiving compared to those who are separated, single, widowed, or divorced. This suggests that married households are more often sites of active caregiving responsibility, reflecting higher rates of co-residence with dependents or shared caregiving duties.

Political orientation adds another dimension. This profile is more prevalent among voters who do not support RWPP, compared to RWPP supporters. This pattern may reflect differing expectations around family roles, greater emphasis on shared or institutional

responsibility for caregiving, or contrasting cultural framings of care-related burdens across the political spectrum.

Figure 82: Odds ratios predicting the selection of caring for children, elderly relatives, and other dependents as a challenge (by gender)

The profile of men and women with a higher likelihood of perceiving the care of children, elderly relatives, and other dependents as a significant challenge reveals clear and sometimes gender-specific patterns across employment status, marital or partnership situation, age, family composition, political orientation, religious affiliation, and gendered identity as depicted in Figure 82.

Among men, this profile is marked by those in full-time employment, who are more likely to report caregiving as a challenge than men who are disabled. This suggests that intensive labour market participation can heighten awareness of the strain involved in managing family caregiving alongside work demands.

Marital status is another key differentiator for men. Married men are more likely to perceive caregiving as a challenge than single men, indicating closer involvement with family caregiving roles within marriage. Family composition also shapes this male profile: men with

more children than the average are more likely to report this challenge, underscoring the greater practical demands of caring for larger families.

Political orientation adds a further dimension: men who vote for Mainstream Left (ML) or Mainstream Right (MR) parties are more likely to perceive caregiving as a challenge than those who support RWPP, reflecting ideological differences in how caregiving responsibilities and public or family support structures are understood.

Among women, the profile is broader and reveals additional factors. Age is a key differentiator: older women are more likely to perceive caregiving as a challenge than younger women, consistent with the shifting caregiving roles that emerge across the life course. Partnership status remains significant: married women are more likely to report this challenge than those who are separated, widowed, single, or divorced, reflecting the greater caregiving responsibilities typically embedded in married households.

Employment status also plays an important role. Women in full-time employment show a higher probability of reporting caregiving as a challenge than those who are unemployed or retired, highlighting how formal labour market integration can increase the tension between work and family responsibilities. Within occupational categories, women in military service stand out for the highest likelihood of perceiving this challenge, suggesting a particularly demanding context in terms of balancing work and care obligations (while acknowledging interpretive caution due to response category limitations).

Religious affiliation also distinguishes the female profile. Roman Catholic women are more likely to perceive caregiving as a challenge than Muslim women, pointing to potential cultural or institutional differences in expectations around caregiving roles and support networks.

Political orientation further characterises the female profile. Women who vote for MR, ML, or Radical Left (RL) parties are more likely to report caregiving as a challenge than those supporting RWPP, suggesting ideological differences in how caregiving burdens and the role of public support are understood.

Profile of individuals displaying higher probabilities of perceiving accessing good quality healthcare as a challenge

Figure 83: Odds ratios predicting the selection of accessing good quality healthcare as a challenge (overall dataset)

The profile of individuals more likely to perceive access to good quality healthcare as a challenge presented in Figure 83 is shaped by specific family configurations, employment circumstances, identity markers, and political orientations—each of which reflects deeper structural or experiential dynamics. Firstly, age is a key factor shaping this profile. Older individuals—especially the elderly—are more likely than younger groups to report difficulties, highlighting how accumulated health needs and more frequent interaction with health systems may increase awareness of systemic barriers or service inadequacies.

From a family perspective, individuals with fewer children than the average are more likely to report challenges in accessing healthcare, suggesting that this group may be more attentive to personal health needs or more reliant on external systems rather than intra-household care networks. Married individuals are also more likely to perceive difficulties than those who are separated or in civil partnerships, potentially indicating greater exposure to healthcare navigation on behalf of multiple family members and the complexities this entails.

From a socioeconomic and employment standpoint, individuals engaged in full-time employment are more likely to experience difficulty accessing quality healthcare than those in part-time roles. While full-time workers may benefit from greater financial resources, they may also face constraints in scheduling care or navigating employer-based insurance systems, particularly when these lack flexibility or inclusiveness. Likewise, individuals who position

themselves lower on the social scale are more likely to report healthcare access as a challenge, reflecting the compounded impact of economic insecurity, reduced social capital, and administrative or informational barriers.

Identity-related factors also feature prominently. Individuals with a less pronounced gendered collective identity—whether masculinised or feminised—are more likely to perceive access to healthcare as a challenge. This may suggest that distance from conventional gender norms is associated with reduced confidence in institutional navigation or lesser visibility in policy design. In terms of religious affiliation, Roman Catholic individuals are more likely to report challenges compared to Protestants and followers of other religions, which may reflect regionally embedded expectations about the role of public services or institutional support.

Political orientation adds a final layer to this profile. Individuals who support Right-Wing Populist Parties (RWPP) are more likely to perceive difficulties accessing healthcare compared to those aligned with Mainstream Right (MR) parties. This may reflect deeper scepticism toward the efficiency or fairness of public systems, or a heightened sensitivity to perceived exclusion from institutional responsiveness.

Figure 84: Odds ratios predicting the selection of accessing good quality healthcare as a challenge (by gender)

Figure 84 depicts the profile of men and women more likely to perceive access to good quality healthcare as a challenge revealing distinct patterns shaped by age, social status, identity orientation, family composition, religious and educational background, and partnership or employment status. These individuals tend to have more frequent interactions with healthcare systems or experience conditions that heighten their sensitivity to structural barriers.

Among men, the profile of those most concerned about healthcare access is defined by a combination of age, identity, and social conditions. Older men are more likely to perceive healthcare access as a challenge than younger men, reflecting the increasing need for medical care over the life course. This pattern is also present among women but appears slightly more pronounced among men, possibly reflecting differences in help-seeking behaviour or in the experience of navigating healthcare systems.

Men with a weaker masculine gendered collective identity (Male GCI) show a higher likelihood of reporting difficulty, indicating that less adherence to traditional masculine norms may be linked to reduced institutional confidence or access. Similarly, men who self-position lower on the social scale tend to perceive greater challenges, consistent with material disadvantage and reduced familiarity with navigating complex systems.

In terms of family dynamics, men with fewer children than the average are more likely to express concern, possibly due to lower reliance on informal care within the family or increased individual responsibility for health management. Married men also report more difficulties than those in civil partnerships, suggesting that the management of healthcare within multi-person households may increase perceived strain or bureaucratic complexity.

Among women, the profile of those more likely to be concerned about healthcare access includes several overlapping and gender-specific dimensions. As with men, older women are more likely to perceive difficulties, consistent with increased care needs and system usage across the life course. In terms of identity, women with a weaker feminine GCI are more likely to report access challenges, suggesting that distance from traditional gender roles may reduce confidence in navigating institutional processes or decrease visibility within policy design.

Women who self-identify at lower positions on the social scale also show a higher likelihood of concern, mirroring the male pattern and underlining the significance of socioeconomic insecurity in shaping experiences with healthcare. Likewise, women with fewer children than average are more likely to report challenges, which may point to reduced household support structures or a greater reliance on external care systems.

Partnership status adds nuance to the female profile: married women are more likely to express concern than those who are separated, suggesting that caregiving and coordination responsibilities within marriage may intensify healthcare-related stress. Women in full-time employment also report more difficulty than their part-time counterparts, underscoring the tension between work schedules and healthcare access, particularly when services lack flexibility.

From a cultural and institutional perspective, Roman Catholic women are more likely to report concern than Protestant women, suggesting possible regional or community-based differences in public service reliance and expectations. Educational background further shapes this profile: women with primary or no formal education are more likely to perceive access as a challenge than those with intermediate levels of education. This may reflect limited health literacy, reduced bureaucratic fluency, or lower confidence in institutional engagement. In the same line, key factor is level of religiosity: women with lower levels of religious involvement are more likely to express concern, possibly indicating that regular participation in religious communities may offer emotional, informational, or practical support in dealing with institutional systems.

Finally, a distinctly gendered marker within the female profile is the heightened concern observed among women identified as Losers of Feminism. This suggests that feelings of social or political exclusion related to gender equality may be associated with diminished trust in institutions or a stronger perception of being underserved by public systems.

Profile of individuals displaying higher probabilities of perceiving getting a good education as a challenge

Figure 85: Odds ratios predicting the selection of getting a good education as a challenge (overall dataset)

The profile of individuals most likely to perceive access to good education as a challenge, as shown in Figure 85, reflects distinct social, economic, and identity-related characteristics, with differences particularly evident across employment status, age, financial situation, and gendered identity. These individuals tend to be more directly engaged with educational systems or more exposed to barriers—real or anticipated—in navigating them.

People who are currently students form the core of this concerned profile. Their direct exposure to educational processes, as well as possible uncertainty regarding future outcomes, makes them more attuned to systemic obstacles in securing quality education. To a lesser extent, retired individuals are also more likely than those in full-time employment to perceive this as a challenge, possibly due to intergenerational concerns—such as supporting grandchildren—or reflections on societal shifts in access and opportunity.

Younger individuals, particularly those under 24, are more likely than some older age groups to express concern. This generational pattern suggests that expectations around education may have evolved, with younger cohorts placing greater emphasis on educational

equity or experiencing more acute pressures related to competition, affordability, or institutional access.

From a financial perspective, individuals who report difficulty or just managing on their current income are more likely to express concern about educational access than those living comfortably. This underlines the persistent role of economic insecurity in shaping perceptions of institutional accessibility, particularly in systems where education carries direct or indirect costs.

With regard to identity, those with a less feminised gendered collective identity are more likely to perceive education access as a challenge. This may point to reduced perceived inclusion in educational narratives or to a disconnection from social groups more closely aligned with institutional trust and navigation.

Notably, the individual's own level of education does not significantly influence whether they perceive access to good education as a challenge. This suggests that the concern is less about personal attainment and more about structural awareness or empathy with others' experiences—particularly among those who see education as a key driver of social opportunity yet recognize persistent barriers.

Figure 86: Odds ratios predicting the selection of getting a good education as a challenge (by gender)

Figure 86 presents that the profile of individuals who are more likely to perceive access to good education as a challenge reveals notable gender differences, with a broader and more multifaceted pattern emerging among women. While male concern is primarily concentrated in a specific subgroup, female concern spans across age, financial situation, family composition, and gendered identity—indicating a more widespread sensitivity to perceived barriers within the educational system.

Among men, the profile of those concerned about access to good education is defined by a single, clear predictor: being a student. Male students are more likely than those in full-time employment to report this concern, which reflects their direct engagement with the education system and heightened exposure to institutional barriers such as affordability, competition, or quality gaps. The fact that no other factor significantly predicts concern among men suggests that this issue is less central in the male population overall, or that broader concerns around education may be less strongly internalised outside the student experience.

Among women, the profile is more complex and layered. Younger women (under 24) are more likely than older women to express concern about access to education, pointing to a heightened awareness of current challenges in securing quality learning opportunities. Interestingly, retired women also show a higher probability of concern than women in full-time employment. This may reflect an intergenerational perspective, where retired women

project their concern based on their own past experiences or on the perceived educational prospects of children and grandchildren.

In contrast to the male profile, being a student is not a significant predictor of concern among women. This divergence may suggest that concerns about educational access among women are less tied to individual status and more connected to broader social awareness, role-based responsibilities, or relational dynamics—such as caregiving and financial management within households.

Financial situation is a strong predictor within the female profile: women who report coping or struggling on their current income are more likely to perceive education as a challenge than those living comfortably. This reflects how economic vulnerability can amplify concerns over affordability, access to quality institutions, or continuity of educational opportunities—particularly for families.

Two identity-based elements further distinguish this female profile. First, women with a weaker feminine gendered collective identity (Female GCI) are more likely to report concern, possibly reflecting a sense of distance from institutional inclusion or a perception that the education system does not fully reflect or accommodate diverse gender experiences. Second, women with more children than the average are also more likely to express concern, which may indicate greater awareness of systemic limitations from the perspective of parental responsibility or long-term educational planning.

Overall, the profile of women concerned about educational access is broader and more structurally grounded than that of men, as illustrated in Figure 86. It spans both personal experience and relational roles, suggesting that for many women—especially younger, financially constrained, caregiving, or identity-marginalised individuals—education is not only a personal pathway but also a family and societal concern.

Profile of individuals displaying higher probabilities of perceiving exercising my civil rights and freedoms as a challenge

Figure 87: Odds ratios predicting the selection of exercising my civil rights and freedoms as a challenge (overall dataset)

Figure 87 presents that the profile of individuals most likely to perceive the exercise of civil rights and freedoms as a challenge is shaped by a combination of gender, age, educational attainment, political orientation, religious affiliation, employment status, and family composition. This concern appears particularly pronounced among individuals who are more sensitive to institutional change, value individual autonomy, or feel socio-politically excluded from dominant narratives.

A key feature of this profile is its gendered dimension: men are more likely than women to report concern about the ability to exercise civil rights and freedoms. This suggests that, in certain sociopolitical contexts, men may be more prone to interpret shifts in institutional norms, regulation, or public discourse as limiting to individual autonomy, especially when these shifts challenge established roles or frameworks of authority.

Individuals with higher levels of education—particularly those with tertiary studies—are more likely to express this concern than those with primary or no formal education. This indicates that the perception of rights-based challenges is not linked to low institutional

knowledge, but rather may reflect a more critical or vigilant stance toward civic institutions and evolving governance norms.

Age is another defining factor: both adults and older individuals show higher levels of concern than younger people. This generational pattern may reflect accumulated experience with civic institutions or a greater tendency to compare current conditions with perceived past standards of freedom and autonomy.

Those identified as Losers of Globalisation also form part of this concerned profile. Their higher levels of concern suggest a broader perception of disempowerment in the face of global economic and cultural shifts, which may be experienced as institutional detachment or democratic dilution.

From a family perspective, individuals with fewer children than average are more likely to express concern. This may reflect a more individualized orientation toward civic life, with fewer distractions from personal or political engagement, or a stronger focus on rights in their own life course.

Religious affiliation also plays a role: individuals with no religious denomination are more likely to report concern than Roman Catholics, suggesting that those outside traditional religious frameworks may feel less institutionally represented or protected in their exercise of rights and freedoms.

From an employment standpoint, disabled individuals are more likely than those in full-time work to perceive restrictions on their rights, possibly reflecting direct experience with institutional limitations, administrative barriers, or perceptions of unequal treatment in civic or bureaucratic settings.

Political orientation is a particularly sharp dividing line. Individuals who support Right-Wing Populist Parties (RWPP) are more likely to perceive challenges in exercising civil rights than those aligned with Mainstream Right (MR), Mainstream Left (ML), or Radical Left (RL) parties. This aligns with broader populist narratives (Mudde & Rovira Kaltwasser, 2017) that frame institutions as distant, restrictive, or biased, and often cast the self-perception of the individual as “excluded” from mainstream democratic representation.

Overall, the profile of people concerned about the exercise of civil rights and freedoms is most prominent among men, older adults, highly educated individuals, those outside traditional religious institutions, and those politically aligned with RWPP.

Figure 88: Odds ratios predicting the selection of exercising my civil rights and freedoms as a challenge (by gender)

Figure 88 presents that the profile of individuals who perceive the exercise of civil rights and freedoms as a challenge shows a marked gender distinction, with a higher concentration of concern among men, but with important patterns also emerging among women. In both cases, the concern reflects perceived limitations in institutional responsiveness, shifting societal norms, and evolving frameworks of political legitimacy.

Among men, the profile of those most concerned is shaped by a combination of age, political orientation, globalisation-related identity, and family configuration. Men aged 55 and over are more likely to express concern than younger men, pointing to a generational dynamic in which older individuals may experience—or interpret—social and institutional changes as restrictive in terms of civic autonomy or freedom of expression.

Men identified as losers of globalisation are also more likely to report this concern, reflecting a broader perception of political disempowerment or exclusion from the benefits of recent economic and cultural shifts. Similarly, men who support right-wing populist parties (RWPP) are more likely to report difficulties in exercising their rights than those aligned with mainstream left (ML) parties. This alignment suggests that anti-establishment narratives (Zulianello, 2018), focused on loss of voice or institutional distrust, are particularly salient for this male subgroup.

From a family perspective, men with fewer children than the average are more likely to express concern, which may be interpreted as a reflection of a more individualised or autonomy-focused view of civic engagement, or as reduced involvement in institutions (like schools or healthcare) that mediate everyday rights.

Among women, although the overall intensity of concern is lower, a distinct and meaningful profile emerges—shaped by age, employment vulnerability, religion, and political orientation. Adult and older women are more likely to perceive challenges in exercising their civil rights than younger women, suggesting similar generational dynamics to those observed among men, though potentially linked to different reference points (e.g. changing gender roles, family-related rights, or institutional access across life stages).

Disabled women report higher levels of concern than women in full-time employment. This suggests that institutional accessibility and equal treatment are key dimensions in how civil freedoms are experienced, particularly among women who face compounded structural barriers.

In terms of religious affiliation, women who belong to non-Catholic Christian or non-Christian faiths show higher levels of concern than Roman Catholic women. This may reflect experiences of religious minority status, perceptions of underrepresentation, or discomfort with dominant cultural frameworks shaping civic life.

Women aligned with RWPP are also more likely to report concern than those who support MR, ML, or RL parties. This points to the presence of gendered versions of political disaffection, where populist narratives—though often associated with male-dominated discourse—also resonate with certain groups of women, particularly around themes of loss of control, identity, or institutional fairness.

In summary, as set out in Figure 88, while concern about civil rights and freedoms is more concentrated among men, the female profile is far from marginal. It is rooted in lived experience, institutional positioning, and political identity. Together, these gendered profiles reflect distinct but intersecting modes of perceiving vulnerability in civic participation, highlighting how rights-based anxieties are shaped not only by ideology or generation, but also by embodied, everyday interactions with institutions, norms, and structures of inclusion or exclusion.

Profile of individuals displaying higher probabilities of perceiving being able to express my sexual orientation as a challenge

Figure 89: Odds ratios predicting the selection of being able to express my sexual orientation as a challenge (overall dataset)

Figure 89 illustrates that the profile of individuals who are more likely to perceive expressing their sexual orientation as a challenge is shaped by intersecting demographic, religious, familial, identity-based and political factors. While the concern is more prevalent among men, meaningful patterns also emerge among women, each reflecting distinct experiences of social visibility, normative pressure, and perceived institutional support or exclusion.

Among men, the profile of those more likely to express concern is characterised by younger age, minority religious affiliation, non-traditional family structures, and a heightened sensitivity to political and cultural narratives around sexual normativity. Younger men are more likely to report this challenge than older men, pointing to a generational shift in expectations: younger cohorts may feel greater entitlement to express their identity openly, but are also more exposed to persistent social or institutional barriers. Men with no children or fewer than average are more likely to report concern, as are those who are single rather than married, suggesting a profile more focused on personal autonomy or less shielded by conventional family roles.

Religious affiliation is a key factor: men belonging to non-Christian religions report higher concern than Roman Catholics, who themselves are more likely to report difficulty than men from other Christian denominations. This gradient may reflect both the normative

frameworks embedded within specific faith traditions and the degree of institutional visibility afforded to non-heteronormative identities. Politically, men who support mainstream or radical left parties are more likely to report concern than those aligned with right-wing populist formations, reinforcing the association between political orientation and perceived acceptance or protection of sexual diversity.

Among women, concern about expressing sexual orientation is generally lower in prevalence but reveals distinct patterns of its own. As with men, younger women are more likely to report concern than older women, indicating that visibility and expectations around expression are stronger among younger generations. Religious affiliation again plays a role, with higher levels of concern among women from non-Christian religions, followed by Roman Catholic women. Women with fewer children than average and those who are single also show a higher likelihood of expressing concern, reflecting similar dynamics to those seen among men—though possibly influenced by different social expectations around femininity and relational status.

A distinctive feature of the female profile is the role of gendered collective identity. Women with a stronger feminine GCI are more likely to report concern. This may suggest that identification with care-oriented or inclusive values is associated with greater awareness of—and sensitivity to—barriers to sexual expression. It may also reflect stronger alignment with social or political communities in which issues of sexual diversity are more visible or openly contested.

Finally, as with men, political orientation is a clear predictor. Women aligned with the mainstream or radical left are more likely to perceive expressing their orientation as a challenge than those supporting RWPP, reflecting deeper ideological divides in how diversity is understood and supported in the public sphere.

In summary, as depicted in Figure 89, while men are more likely than women overall to express concern about expressing their sexual orientation, both profiles point to a broader landscape in which political identity, religious affiliation, family structure, and gendered identification intersect with lived experiences of visibility, stigma, or inclusion. These concerns are not solely rooted in personal identity, but reflect how individuals position themselves within broader social and institutional frameworks that shape what is possible, permissible, or protected in matters of sexual expression.

Figure 90: Odds ratios predicting the selection of being able to express my sexual orientation as a challenge (by gender)

The profile of individuals who are more likely to perceive expressing their sexual orientation as a challenge continues to show clear gender differentiation as shown in Figure 90. While this concern is more prevalent among men, specific patterns also emerge among women, reflecting distinct experiences of social visibility, normative pressures, and political alignment.

Among men, the likelihood of expressing concern is higher overall, and the profile is shaped by identity-related, relational, and political factors. Men with a stronger feminine gendered collective identity are more likely to report this issue, which may suggest a departure from traditional masculine norms and a closer alignment with inclusive values, emotional openness, or spaces where sexual diversity is more recognised and defended. This may also reflect increased sensitivity to environments in which deviation from hegemonic masculinity remains socially sanctioned or institutionally overlooked.

Single men are more likely to perceive expressing their orientation as a challenge than married men, indicating that relational context may offer different degrees of social legitimacy or protection. Similarly, men with fewer children than the average are more likely to report this concern, potentially reflecting a life context where conventional family structures—and the social acceptance often tied to them—are absent or less central.

In political terms, men who support radical left parties are more likely to express this concern than those aligned with right-wing populist formations. This pattern aligns with broader ideological divides: left-wing political cultures are more likely to frame sexual diversity as a matter of public recognition and rights, whereas populist-right discourses often emphasise traditional norms and collective identities, which may marginalise expressions of sexual difference.

Among women, although this concern is less prevalent overall, a distinct and socially grounded profile can still be observed. Younger women are more likely to report concern than older women, suggesting that newer generations are more attuned to issues of sexual diversity and more likely to identify or empathise with the barriers that still exist. Divorced women show a higher likelihood of reporting this concern than married women, which may reflect experiences of social repositioning or increased autonomy that expose tensions between individual identity and normative expectations.

Political orientation once again plays a role. Women who support radical left parties are more likely to express this concern than those who support right-wing populist parties, echoing the ideological divide observed among men. This suggests that exposure to political discourses centred on inclusion, rights, and recognition may enhance awareness of the constraints that persist in certain social or institutional contexts.

A particularly noteworthy factor in the female profile is the heightened concern reported by women identified as losers of globalisation. This association may indicate a convergence of perceived marginality: women who experience socio-economic disempowerment may also feel that the freedom to express non-normative sexual identities is unevenly distributed or insufficiently protected. The intersection of structural vulnerability with identity-based exclusion may therefore generate a deeper sensitivity to restrictions on sexual expression—not merely as a private issue, but as a reflection of broader patterns of institutional distance or cultural non-belonging.

In summary, while men remain more likely overall to express concern about being able to express their sexual orientation, women's profiles reveal meaningful and differentiated dynamics. Across both genders, these concerns are shaped not only by identity but by political alignment, relational status, and social positioning. The capacity to express sexual orientation freely thus emerges as a socially mediated experience, where individual expression intersects with broader questions of legitimacy, visibility, and institutional recognition.

Profile of individuals displaying higher probabilities of perceiving being physically safe as a challenge

Figure 91: Odds ratios predicting the selection of being physically safe as a challenge (overall dataset)

Figure 91 displays that the profile of individuals who are more likely to perceive being physically safe as a challenge is shaped by gender, age, family composition, religious affiliation, employment status, and political orientation. This concern is more commonly reported by women than men, suggesting a gendered experience of physical vulnerability. Women may be more exposed to, or more aware of, risks in public and private spaces, reflecting broader patterns of perceived and actual threat that disproportionately affect female populations.

Age also plays a significant role in shaping this profile. Older individuals are more likely than younger people to report concern about their physical safety. This may reflect increased vulnerability linked to physical decline, reduced mobility, or heightened awareness of environmental risks in later stages of life. In terms of family composition, individuals with fewer children than the average are more likely to express concern. This could suggest that those in smaller or less traditional households experience a reduced sense of security, possibly due to limited informal support or protection.

Regarding religious affiliation, Roman Catholics are more likely to report concern than Protestants. This difference may reflect varying religious or cultural narratives related to protection, exposure to risk, or trust in public safety systems.

Employment status also differentiates the profile. Individuals in full-time work are more likely to perceive physical safety as a challenge compared to those who are unemployed. This may be linked to increased exposure to public environments through commuting or occupational settings, or to time-related constraints that reduce the capacity to avoid or mitigate risk.

Finally, political orientation marks a clear divide. Individuals who support right-wing populist parties are more likely to express concern about physical safety than those aligned with other political families. This pattern is consistent with broader populist discourses that emphasise personal insecurity, threats to public order, and a perceived erosion of state protection (Mudde & Rovira Kaltwasser, 2017).

In sum, as illustrated in Figure 91, the profile of those most concerned about physical safety includes women, older individuals, people with fewer children, full-time workers, Roman Catholics, and supporters of right-wing populist parties. Their concerns reflect a complex interplay of demographic, social, and ideological factors that shape how safety is experienced and politicised in everyday life.

Figure 92: Odds ratios predicting the selection of being physically safe as a challenge (by gender)

Figure 92 presents that the profile of men and women who perceive being physically safe as a challenge reveals both shared and gender-specific patterns, shaped by age, family

structure, employment status, income, educational attainment, political orientation, and identification with broader globalisation-related narratives.

Among men, concern about physical safety is more likely to be expressed by those in the adult and elder age brackets. Older men tend to report this issue more frequently than younger men, reflecting a general pattern of age-related vulnerability observed across the population. This may stem from increased perceived physical fragility or a stronger sense of exposure to societal changes that are interpreted as destabilising.

A defining feature of the male profile is the presence of men identified as losers of globalisation. This group shows a higher likelihood of expressing concern about physical safety, suggesting that perceived socio-economic displacement or marginalisation may translate into a heightened sensitivity to risks in the physical and social environment.

Political orientation also plays a key role. Men who support right-wing populist parties (RWPP) are more likely to report concern than those aligned with the mainstream left (ML). This reflects a broader tendency within RWPP electorates to emphasise personal insecurity and social disorder (Arzheimer, 2017) which may be internalised by male voters as a sense of diminished physical safety or institutional protection.

Among women, concern about physical safety follows several of the general trends observed in the overall population but also includes distinct features. Older women, particularly those aged 55 and over, are more likely to express concern than younger women. This again points to an age-related perception of vulnerability, shaped by physical, social, or contextual factors.

Family composition is also relevant: women with fewer children than average are more likely to perceive physical safety as a challenge. This may reflect lower perceived protection within the household or less access to informal support networks.

Employment status differentiates the female profile further. Women in full-time work report more concern than unemployed women, possibly due to increased exposure to public spaces or time constraints that limit the capacity to manage personal safety. At the same time, income plays a significant role: women who report it is very difficult to live on their current income are more likely to report concern than those living comfortably. This suggests that material vulnerability may intensify feelings of exposure or limit perceived access to protective resources or environments.

A specifically female factor emerges in relation to educational attainment. Women with higher education are more likely to report concern than those with only primary education or none. This may indicate a heightened awareness of structural risks, greater social engagement, or more active participation in public life, all of which may increase sensitivity to issues of safety.

Political orientation also features prominently in the female profile. Women who support RWPP are more likely to express concern than those aligned with any other major party family, including the ML, MR, and RL. This broader contrast suggests that the emphasis on physical insecurity present in RWPP discourse resonates particularly strongly among female voters, perhaps amplifying perceived threats to personal safety beyond the patterns observed among male voters, where the distinction is primarily between RWPP and the mainstream left.

In summary, while age and family structure are shared predictors across genders, male concern is shaped more by political identity and perceived socio-economic marginalisation, while female concern is more closely tied to employment status, financial strain, and education level—reflecting distinct pathways through which vulnerability to physical insecurity is experienced and interpreted.

Profile of individuals displaying higher probabilities of perceiving being a good mother/father as a challenge

Figure 93: Odds ratios predicting the selection of being a good mother/father as a challenge (overall dataset)

The profile of individuals who are more likely to perceive being a good mother or father as a challenge, displayed in Figure 93, is shaped by gender, age, family structure, educational attainment, and religious affiliation. Gender emerges as a key factor. Men are more likely than women to report this concern, marking a notable divergence from patterns observed in other domains such as the balance between paid work and family duties. In this case, the concern among men appears to reflect less the immediate pressures of caregiving and more the internalised weight of fulfilling an idealised paternal role. This may suggest that, for many men, being a good parent is tied to notions of adequacy, authority, or moral responsibility, rather than to daily caregiving tasks.

Age is also a significant differentiator. Younger individuals are more likely to perceive this challenge than older adults and elders, indicating that concerns about parenting are most salient during the active parenting years, when expectations and responsibilities are at their peak. As individuals age, these concerns may diminish due to changing roles or increased confidence in one's parenting legacy.

In terms of educational attainment, those with primary education are more likely to report this concern than individuals with higher levels of education. This may reflect differences in access to parenting resources, support networks, or institutional knowledge. It

may also point to lower perceived preparedness or greater uncertainty in navigating modern parenting expectations among those with more limited formal education.

Civil status further shapes this profile. Married individuals are more likely to report this concern than those who are divorced, widowed, cohabiting, or single. This may suggest that the marital context brings with it heightened role expectations or a stronger sense of accountability in parental performance, especially when parenting is perceived as a central pillar of the marital relationship.

Family composition is a key contributor. Individuals with more children than the average are more likely to express concern about being a good parent. This is consistent with the increased demands—emotional, logistical, and financial—associated with larger families, where the perceived challenge may stem from balancing individual attention, maintaining consistency, or meeting diverse needs.

Finally, religious affiliation also plays a role. Concern is highest among Protestants, followed by Roman Catholics, and lowest among those identifying as Eastern Orthodox. This gradient may reflect varying religious or cultural models of family life, moral responsibility, or parental authority. Traditions that emphasise individual moral accountability or scriptural ideals of parenting may produce stronger internalised expectations, contributing to a greater sense of challenge in fulfilling the parental role.

In summary, as shown in Figure 93, the individuals most likely to perceive being a good mother or father as a challenge are younger, more often male, married, with more children than average, lower levels of formal education, and more likely to belong to Protestant or Catholic religious traditions. This profile reflects a confluence of structural pressures and normative expectations, where the role of the parent is not only lived but also measured against internalised ideals shaped by social, cultural, and institutional frameworks.

Figure 94: Odds ratios predicting the selection of being a good mother/father as a challenge (by gender)

Figure 94 presents that the profile of men and women who perceive being a good parent as a challenge reflects gender-specific configurations of demographic, educational, occupational, religious, and political factors. These concerns appear to be shaped not only by lived experiences of parenting but also by broader cultural expectations, normative roles, and internalised ideals around fatherhood and motherhood.

Among men, the perception of being a good father as a challenge increases with several key factors. Men with more children than the average are more likely to report this concern, reflecting the greater logistical, emotional, and economic demands associated with larger families. This pattern is gender-specific, as it does not appear among women. Similarly, marital status plays a role: married men are more likely to express concern than single men, which may reflect the intensified social expectations surrounding paternal performance within marriage.

Educational attainment is also associated with this perception. Men with only primary education are more likely to report concern than those with higher education levels. This may indicate differences in perceived preparedness, access to parenting resources, or confidence in fulfilling normative expectations around fatherhood.

Religiosity is positively associated with concern: the more religious the individual, the greater the likelihood of perceiving being a good father as a challenge. This suggests that for more devout men, parenting may be viewed as a moral responsibility, closely tied to religious ideals of duty, guidance, and discipline. This interpretation is supported by differences in religious affiliation: Roman Catholic men are more likely to report this concern than those identifying with Eastern religions or Eastern Orthodoxy, possibly reflecting differences in religious teachings on family life and paternal roles.

Among women, the profile of those who perceive being a good mother as a challenge involves a distinct set of dynamics. Age is a significant factor: older women, particularly those aged 55 and above, are more likely to express concern than younger women under 24. This may reflect a retrospective evaluation of one's parenting role, or a sustained sense of responsibility beyond the active parenting years.

Marital status is again relevant: married women report higher levels of concern than those who are divorced, widowed, single, in cohabitation, or in a civil union. This pattern suggests that, as with men, the marital context reinforces a sense of heightened accountability or normative expectations around motherhood.

Employment status also plays a role. Women in full-time work are more likely to report concern than those in military service. This may reflect the tension between professional demands and expectations around intensive, emotionally available motherhood—particularly in contexts where work-family reconciliation is limited.

Identity also contributes meaningfully to this profile. Women with a stronger feminine gendered collective identity are more likely to perceive being a good mother as a challenge. This may indicate that those who strongly identify with traditional or relational aspects of femininity experience greater pressure to meet idealised standards of maternal performance, or are more attuned to the emotional and moral complexities of the maternal role.

Political orientation further differentiates the female profile. Women who support right-wing populist parties (RWPP) are more likely to report this concern than those aligned with the radical left (RL). This suggests that political cultures emphasising traditional family structures and gender roles may intensify perceived expectations around motherhood, contributing to a stronger internalisation of the role and, consequently, to greater concern about fulfilling it adequately.

In summary, men's concern about being a good father is more strongly associated with family size, education, religiosity, and religious affiliation, while women's concern about being a good mother is shaped by age, marital and employment status, gendered identity, and political orientation. These gendered profiles point to different models of parental challenge: for men, shaped by structural expectations and moral authority; for women, influenced by relational, normative, and political-cultural frameworks of maternal responsibility.

Profile of individuals displaying higher probabilities of perceiving raising and educating children as a challenge

Figure 95: Odds ratios predicting the selection of raising and educating children as a challenge (overall dataset)

The profile of individuals who are more likely to perceive raising and educating children as a challenge, displayed in Figure 95, is shaped by family size, age, partnership status, household income, gendered collective identity, and political orientation. Age plays a notable role. Individuals under the age of 55 are more likely to report this challenge than those aged 55 and over. This suggests that the perception of difficulty is most acute during the active parenting years, when individuals are more directly engaged in the day-to-day responsibilities of raising and educating children, and when competing demands—such as employment, financial pressures, and time constraints—are more likely to converge.

Family composition is a strong predictor. Individuals with more children than the average are more likely to perceive raising and educating children as a challenge. This is expected, as the demands of time, financial resources, and emotional investment increase with family size, particularly in relation to educational support, extracurricular activities, and planning for the future.

Partnership status also differentiates the profile. Married individuals are more likely to report concern than those who are single or in cohabiting relationships. This may suggest that within marriage, child-rearing is experienced as a shared and structured responsibility, with potentially higher expectations or more formalised roles that intensify the perceived challenge.

Income introduces an interesting dynamic. Individuals with higher household income are more likely to report this concern than those with lower income. This may reflect the heightened standards, expectations, or competitive pressures that often accompany parenting in middle- and upper-income households, where educational investment, lifestyle demands, and long-term planning for children's success become central concerns.

Gendered identity further shapes this profile. Individuals with a less masculinised gendered collective identity are more likely to perceive raising and educating children as a challenge. This may point to a greater emotional or practical engagement in caregiving among those who depart from traditional masculine norms, and who may therefore carry or acknowledge a larger share of parenting labour, planning, and emotional responsibility.

In sum, as shown in Figure 95, individuals who perceive raising and educating children as a challenge tend to be older, married, have more children than average, live in higher-income households, and identify with less rigid or traditional masculine norms. This profile reflects the intersection of structural responsibility and internalised expectations, where the challenge of child-rearing is experienced not only as a logistical burden but also as a function of social roles, values, and aspirations for children's futures.

Figure 96: Odds ratios predicting the selection of raising and educating children as a challenge (by gender)

Figure 96 outlines that the profile of men and women who are more likely to perceive raising and educating children as a challenge is shaped by a distinct combination of demographic, family, economic, occupational, and identity-related factors. While some elements are shared across genders, others reflect gender-specific pathways through which the responsibilities and expectations of child-rearing are experienced and internalised.

Among men, the perception of raising and educating children as a challenge is more common among younger individuals. Men under the age of 55 are more likely to report this concern than their older and elder counterparts, suggesting that this issue is most salient during the active parenting years. This pattern may be linked to less parenting experience, less household stability, or heightened uncertainty regarding long-term demands related to children's upbringing.

Partnership status also differentiates the male profile. Divorced men are more likely to perceive this challenge than married men, who in turn report higher concern than those who are single or cohabiting. This pattern may point to the strain associated with shared custody, disrupted family dynamics, or reduced support networks following separation. Family size is also a strong predictor. Men with more children than the average are notably more likely to report this challenge, underscoring the cumulative emotional, logistical, and financial demands associated with larger families.

Income also plays a significant role. Men with higher household income are more likely to report concern, a pattern that may reflect rising expectations regarding the quality of education, extracurricular support, and life opportunities they wish to provide for their children. Financial abundance may increase not only the means to invest in child-rearing but also the pressure to meet perceived standards of “successful” parenting.

Finally, gender identity contributes meaningfully to this profile. Men who express a less masculinised gendered collective identity are more likely to report concern about raising and educating children. This suggests that those who distance themselves from traditional masculine norms may engage more deeply in the day-to-day and emotional aspects of parenting, and may be more attuned to its challenges as a result.

Among women, the profile follows several similar patterns, while also revealing distinctive elements. Younger women are more likely to report this challenge than those in older age brackets, indicating that active parenting years bring with them the most direct pressures and concerns. As with men, women with more children than the average also report higher levels of concern, reinforcing the link between family size and the practical intensity of child-rearing.

Marital status is also a relevant factor. Married women are more likely to report this concern than women who are single or cohabiting. This differs from the male pattern, where divorced men showed the highest probability of concern, suggesting that for women, formal partnership may be associated with increased expectations or shared responsibility that intensifies the perceived challenge.

Income again functions as a driver of concern. Women in higher-income households are more likely to report this issue than those with fewer resources, mirroring the male profile. This may point to a cross-gender pattern where economic capacity increases not only opportunities but also perceived obligations to secure the best possible educational and developmental outcomes for children.

Employment status further differentiates the female profile. Women in full-time work are more likely to report concern than those in military service. This contrast may reflect differences in schedule flexibility, institutional support, or the cultural framing of parenting roles in different occupational sectors.

Finally, gendered identity is again a relevant factor. Women with a less masculinised gendered collective identity are more likely to perceive this challenge, a pattern consistent with that of the general population. This association is somewhat more pronounced among women, suggesting that distancing from traditional masculine norms—and possibly aligning more with relational or care-based self-concepts—intensifies awareness of the demands of child-rearing.

In summary, the perception of raising and educating children as a challenge is most likely to be reported by younger individuals of both genders, those with larger families, higher household income, and less traditionally masculine gender identities. Among men, concern is especially elevated among those who are divorced and less traditionally masculine, while among women it is more prominent among those who are married, in full-time employment, and more relationally attuned to the parenting role. Together, these profiles reflect the combined weight of practical responsibility and internalised expectation across varying family and social contexts.

Profile of individuals displaying higher probabilities of perceiving forming a family as a challenge

Figure 97: Odds ratios predicting the selection of forming a family as a challenge (overall dataset)

The profile of individuals more likely to perceive forming a family as a challenge, presented in Figure 97, is shaped by gender, age, partnership status, education, employment, parental experience, personal income, and gender-based positionality. Men are more likely than women to report this concern. This may reflect social expectations around male roles in family formation, such as financial stability or long-term commitment. Younger individuals

show higher concern than adults and elders, suggesting this is a challenge felt most strongly during early adult life.

Those who are single or in cohabiting arrangements are more likely to report difficulty than married individuals, possibly due to uncertainty about future stability or readiness. People with only primary education are also more likely to express concern, which may reflect limited access to resources or lower perceived preparedness.

In terms of employment, those in full-time work show higher concern than the unemployed. This may relate to the time demands of work or pressure to meet perceived standards before forming a family. Individuals with higher personal income are also more likely to report this challenge, possibly due to rising expectations about what family life should include.

Finally, concern is more common among individuals who do not strongly align with traditional gender norms. This may reflect greater sensitivity to social or institutional barriers linked to non-normative gender roles within family structures.

Figure 98: Odds ratios predicting the selection of forming a family as a challenge (by gender)

Figure 98 depicts that the profile of individuals more likely to perceive forming a family as a challenge shows a clear gendered pattern. Among men, this concern is more common

among younger individuals. Students are more likely to report this difficulty than those in full-time employment, suggesting that perceived instability or life transitions may play a role. Single and cohabiting men also report more concern than married men, which may reflect uncertainty about long-term relationship prospects. Higher personal income is also associated with increased concern, possibly linked to higher expectations or perceived standards around family formation.

Among women, the profile is less prevalent but still distinct. Younger women are more likely to report this challenge than older ones. Married women show higher concern than those who are divorced, suggesting that expectations within formal partnership may contribute to perceived pressure. Women with only primary education are more likely to express this difficulty than those with secondary or higher education, pointing to differences in perceived preparedness.

Political orientation also matters: women aligned with mainstream right parties are more likely to report this concern than those aligned with RWPP. In addition, women with higher levels of gender positional deprivation are more likely to express this difficulty, suggesting that feeling disadvantaged within gendered social hierarchies may limit perceived access to family formation.

Overall, these patterns—reflected in the comparative distribution shown in Figure 98—highlight how perceptions of difficulty in forming a family are shaped by different combinations of age, social position, and gendered expectations across men and women.

Profile of individuals displaying higher probabilities of perceiving gaining the respect of others as a challenge

Figure 99: Odds ratios predicting the selection of gaining the respect of others as a challenge (overall dataset)

The profile of individuals more likely to perceive gaining the respect of others as a challenge, shown in Figure 99, is shaped by age, partnership status, household composition, income, labour status, collective gender identity, religiosity, and globalisation-related positionality. Younger individuals are more likely to report this concern than older adults. This may reflect differences in life stage, where younger people are more focused on identity formation or feel more exposed to external judgement. Married individuals report higher levels of concern than those who are separated or divorced, suggesting that maintaining respect may carry particular weight within formal partnerships.

Concern is also higher among individuals with fewer children, possibly reflecting less perceived social recognition or support in family life. An income dynamic also emerges: individuals with higher personal income but lower household income are more likely to report difficulty gaining respect. This may point to tensions between individual achievement and perceived status within the broader household context. In terms of labour status, those in part-time work are more likely to express concern than those in full-time employment. This may relate to perceptions of lower social valuation attached to part-time roles. Individuals with stronger alignment to the Female GCI also report more concern, possibly reflecting greater sensitivity to social recognition or higher emotional investment in relational standing.

Religiosity adds another layer: individuals with higher levels of religious involvement are more likely to perceive gaining respect as a challenge, which may be linked to stricter moral frameworks or heightened expectations around behaviour and public image. Overall, the distribution of this concern—outlined in Figure 99—suggests that perceived difficulty in gaining respect reflects the intersection of age, role visibility, and social valuation across different spheres of life.

Figure 100: Odds ratios predicting the selection of gaining the respect of others as a challenge (by gender)

As shown in Figure 100, the profile of individuals more likely to perceive gaining the respect of others as a challenge varies across gender, with distinct patterns among men and women. Among men, this concern is shaped by partnership status, parenthood, religiosity, and gendered identity. Married men are more likely to report this challenge than those who are separated, suggesting that maintaining respect may be especially relevant within formal partnerships. Men with fewer children also report higher concern, possibly reflecting a perceived lack of social validation tied to family roles. The likelihood of reporting this challenge increases with higher levels of religiosity, as well as stronger alignment with traditional masculine norms (higher Male GCI), which may point to heightened sensitivity to perceived status or social judgement.

Among women, the profile reflects a different configuration. Age plays a key role: younger women are more likely to report this concern than adults, in line with the overall age gradient. Partnership status also matters—married women report more difficulty than separated women, again suggesting that expectations around respect may be more acute within marital relationships. Concern is also higher among women with stronger alignment to traditional feminine norms (higher Female GCI), which may reflect greater emotional investment in social recognition or relational standing. Together, these gendered patterns—outlined in Figure 100—suggest that perceptions of difficulty in gaining respect are linked to different configurations of identity, family roles, and social expectation across men and women.

3.9. Closeness to RWPP

Closeness to RWPP reveals more than partisan alignment—it offers insight into how individuals interpret their position within ongoing processes of social, economic, and cultural transformation. Expressing proximity to this political party signals not only agreement with its ideological stance, but often a deeper identification with narratives of loss, displacement, or resistance to perceived societal shifts.

The following analyses explore the profiles of individuals who report feeling close to RWPP, based on statistical models that incorporate both structural indicators and subjective perceptions. Two key theoretical constructs guide this approach: *Losers of Globalisation*—those who report having been negatively affected by global economic change—and *Losers of Feminism*—individuals who perceive themselves as disadvantaged within evolving gender orders.

In addition to these attitudinal dimensions, sociodemographic factors such as gender, parenthood, religiosity, partnership status, and collective gender identity further shape patterns of closeness to RWPP. As shown in Figure X, these factors operate differently across groups: men and women report proximity for partially distinct reasons, with gendered forms of grievance, economic strain, and role expectations playing divergent roles.

Among men, closeness to RWPP is higher among those who report coping or struggling financially, those in part-time employment, and those who are divorced. These associations point to a broader alignment between RWPP support and experiences of economic and relational precarity. Closeness also increases with religiosity and number of children, suggesting a link to value-based and family-centred worldviews. Most notably, it is men who identify as losers of feminism or globalisation who account for the strongest levels of

closeness—highlighting perceived gendered and structural displacement as central components of male populist alignment.

Among women, the profile is more limited. Voting behaviour remains a predictor of closeness, and identification with RWPP increases among those with lower scores on Female GCI—suggesting that ideological distance from gender-progressive values is the main route of alignment. In contrast to men, variables such as economic strain, part-time employment, or parenthood are not significant predictors in the female profile.

Taken together, the profiles presented here offer a model-based understanding of who feels close to RWPP, and under what conditions. Proximity to RWPP is structured not only by ideology, but also by how individuals locate themselves—materially, culturally, and symbolically—within contested transformations in gender, economy, and society.

Profile of individuals displaying closeness to RWPP

Figure 101: Odds ratios displaying closeness to RWPP (overall dataset)

As shown in Figure 101, the profile of individuals who feel closer to right-wing populist parties (RWPP) is shaped by gender, family structure, religiosity, gendered identity, and perceived loss related to feminism and globalisation. Men are more likely than women to report closeness to RWPP, marking gender as a defining feature of this profile. Closeness also increases with the number of children, suggesting that larger families may be more aligned with the values or narratives promoted by RWPP platforms. Religiosity plays a role as well. Individuals with higher levels of religious practice are more likely to report closeness to these parties, consistent with the emphasis RWPP often place on traditional values and moral order.

In terms of gendered identity, individuals with lower scores on the Female GCI are more likely to feel close to RWPP. This suggests a weaker alignment between feminised collective identities and populist-right positions, which may be associated with differing views on gender roles or equality.

Perceived positional loss also shapes this profile. Closeness increases among those who identify as losers of feminism or globalisation. Although the difference is not statistically significant, closeness is even higher among those identified as losers of feminism than among those positioned as losers of globalisation, indicating that reactions to gender-related change may be especially relevant within this political orientation.

Together, these patterns—reflected in Figure 101—suggest that closeness to RWPP is associated with traditional gender roles, religious alignment, larger families, and perceived loss linked to cultural or structural change.

Figure 102: Odds ratios displaying closeness to RWPP (by gender)

As shown in Figure 102, the profile of individuals reporting greater closeness to right-wing populist parties (RWPP) reveals clear gendered differences, especially in relation to perceived loss and structural dislocation. Among men, closeness to RWPP is strongly associated with feelings of personal or group-level loss. Men who identify as losers of feminism or globalisation are significantly more likely to report closeness—unlike women in the same categories, who do not follow this pattern. This makes perceived loss a distinctly male pathway into populist-right identification.

Economic strain is also part of the male profile. Men who find it difficult or are just coping on their current income are more likely to express closeness than those living comfortably. Similarly, men in part-time work report greater closeness than those employed full-time, possibly reflecting perceptions of economic insecurity or marginalisation.

Closeness also increases among men with more children than the average and among those with higher levels of religiosity, pointing to a value-driven alignment tied to family size and traditional moral frameworks. Divorced men report higher levels of closeness than married men, further suggesting that relational disruption or perceived loss of status contributes to this political orientation.

Among women, the profile is more limited but still reflects relevant trends. Women who recall voting for RWPP report greater closeness than those aligned with other parties. A clear pattern emerges in relation to gender identity: closeness to RWPP increases as Female GCI decreases, indicating that distance from feminised collective identity is associated with greater alignment with RWPP.

These gendered patterns—summarised in Figure 102—show that closeness to RWPP is shaped by different mechanisms: among men, it is closely linked to economic strain, family disruption, religiosity and perceived loss; among women, it is more narrowly tied to ideological distance from gender-progressive values.

3.10. Instrumentality of Vote

This section examines the extent to which voting for different party families is driven by instrumental motivations, based on voters' perceptions regarding a party's likelihood of gaining parliamentary representation, its policy-making capacity, and its overall credibility. The analysis draws on data structured according to the UNTWIST scheme. In contrast to instrumental voting, expressive voting is understood as the propensity to support a party despite perceiving it as unlikely to enter parliament, lacking the strength to influence policy, or being generally seen as not credible. In such cases, the vote is not cast on utilitarian grounds, but rather reflects ideological alignment, symbolic expression, or protest against other political actors.

To operationalise these distinctions, three types of vote are defined. First, a type of vote is classified as instrumental when an individual's propensity to vote for a given party family (as defined by the UNTWIST scheme) exceeds 6 on a 0–10 scale, and the same individual also assigns a value greater than 6 (on the same scale) in at least two of the following three dimensions: perceived likelihood of gaining parliamentary representation, policy strength, and credibility. Second, a vote is classified as expressive when the individual's propensity to vote for a party family again exceeds 6, but scores below 5 in at least two of the three aforementioned dimensions. In this case, voting intention is decoupled from expectations of effectiveness, and instead expresses identity, values, or disaffection.

Finally, a vote is considered mixed when the propensity to vote exceeds 6, but the individual does not meet the criteria for either instrumental or expressive voting as defined above. The analysis begins by mapping this typology of voting—instrumental, expressive, or mixed—across the four main party families identified in the UNTWIST framework. This is followed by a gender-disaggregated examination of the same voting typology.

Figure 103: Descriptives on typology of voters regarding instrumentality (overall dataset)

Figure 103 presents the distribution of voting typologies in aggregate terms. Instrumental voting emerges as the predominant type overall and is clearly more prevalent than expressive voting. The potential electorates of mainstream parties display very similar patterns: more than half of individuals prone to vote for mainstream parties are classified as instrumental voters. Just over one-third are categorised as mixed voters, while fewer than 10% are classified as expressive voters.

Compared to mainstream parties, individuals prone to vote for RWPP are slightly less likely to be instrumental voters—approximately 5 percentage points lower—while the proportion of mixed voters increases correspondingly. The most notable contrast, however, concerns the potential electorate of radical left (RL) parties. Among these individuals, the proportion of instrumental voters is significantly lower, with mixed voting becoming the dominant pattern. Most strikingly, expressive voting among those prone to vote for RL parties reaches around 20%, which is roughly double the level observed in the electorates of other party families.

Figure 104: Descriptives on typology of voters regarding instrumentality (men dataset)

Figure 104 and 105 further disaggregate the distribution of voting typologies by gender, beginning with men. Here in Figure 104, a clearer divergence emerges: men prone to vote for RWPP are substantially less likely to be instrumental voters than their mainstream counterparts, with a difference of just over 10 percentage points. Moreover, the share of expressive voters among male RWPP supporters is double that observed in the mainstream electorate (10% compared to 5%). Nevertheless, the highest levels of expressive voting remain among men who are potential voters of RL parties, consistent with the aggregate findings.

Figure 105: Descriptives on typology of voters regarding instrumentality (women dataset)

Finally, Figure 105 shows the distribution of voting typologies among women. In this case, the differences across party families are more muted. The distribution of voting types appears more evenly balanced, and the distinctions observed in the aggregate are less pronounced. Notably, women prone to vote for RWPP exhibit levels of instrumental voting similar to those of mainstream party supporters, while the proportion of expressive voters in this group is comparatively lower.

3.11. Explanatory analyses of voting RWPP

This section presents explanatory models of the propensity to vote for RWPP, aiming to identify the social profiles most aligned with this political choice. As in the previous section on political proximity, the models are offered in two specifications. Each of these includes a distinct conceptualisation of positional disadvantage. In the first set of models, Losers of Globalisation and Losers of Feminism are included in their more restrictive forms—that is, individuals who not only perceive themselves as disadvantaged by economic or gender-related transformations, but who also attribute that disadvantage to specific social groups, such as migrants or feminists. In the second set, these blame-attributing components are

removed. The gender-related indicator becomes Gender Positional Deprivation, and the globalisation-related variable retains a broader definition that captures structural exclusion without explicit attribution of cause. These models allow not only for the identification of general patterns but also for the detection of gender-specific dynamics.

All models also incorporate ideological self-placement as an independent variable, capturing respondents' subjective positioning along the left–right spectrum. This variable plays a consistently strong explanatory role, confirming the expected association between right-wing orientation and RWPP support, while allowing for a clearer distinction between structural factors and ideological alignment.

Across both model specifications, several consistent patterns emerge: younger age, lower education, financial strain, and right-wing ideological self-placement are all associated with a higher propensity to vote for RWPP. However, the inclusion or exclusion of blame attribution in the explanatory variables introduces important variations. While Losers of Globalisation and Losers of Feminism are significant in the more restrictive models, Gender Positional Deprivation becomes relevant—particularly among men—when blame is removed. Among women, by contrast, economic dislocation measured through the analytical category Losers of Globalisation (even without explicit blaming) remains a significant predictor, whereas GPD does not.

Together, these models provide a nuanced picture of the attitudinal, demographic, and structural conditions under which support for RWPP emerges—highlighting both shared mechanisms and gender-differentiated patterns.

Profile of individuals displaying propensity to vote for RWPP

Figure 106: Coefficients predicting the propensity to vote for RWPP (overall dataset by gender)

Figure 106 shows that the profile of individuals with a greater propensity to vote for right-wing populist parties (RWPP) reflects a combination of socio-demographic, economic, ideological, and cultural factors. Younger individuals are more likely to report this voting intention than adults and elders, suggesting a generational dynamic that may reflect disaffection or political contestation among younger groups. Those with only primary education or no formal education show a higher propensity to vote RWPP than those with secondary or higher qualifications, highlighting the role of educational background in shaping political preferences.

Partnership status also plays a role. Individuals in civil unions or who are separated are more likely to express voting propensity than married individuals, possibly reflecting lower perceived stability or greater distance from mainstream social institutions. Similarly, those with more children than average are more likely to report support for RWPP, pointing to the influence of family structure on political orientation.

The economic profile is marked by a dual pattern. Individuals with above-average personal income show higher voting propensity, as do those with lower household income.

This apparent contradiction may reflect tensions between individual achievement and broader household vulnerability. Moreover, financial strain is a clear predictor: voting propensity increases stepwise from those who report coping to those who find it very difficult to live on their income, compared to those living comfortably. Together, these indicators suggest that both perceived and actual insecurity—at the individual or household level—can contribute to RWPP support.

Religiosity is also positively associated with RWPP voting. Individuals with higher levels of religious practice, particularly those identifying as Eastern Orthodox, report greater voting propensity than Roman Catholics. This may reflect stronger alignment with traditionalist values or institutional distance from dominant religious-cultural norms.

As expected, political ideology plays a key role. Propensity to vote for RWPP increases clearly with self-placement further to the right on the ideological spectrum. Finally, both losers of globalisation and losers of feminism are significantly more likely to report RWPP voting propensity. While the association is slightly stronger among those who identify as losers of globalisation, the difference in magnitude is not statistically significant. This suggests that both types of perceived structural loss—economic and gender-related—are central to understanding alignment with populist-right platforms, as explored in the broader UNTWIST framework.

Figure 107: Coefficients predicting the propensity to vote for RWPP (by gender)

Figure 107 illustrates that the profile of individuals with greater propensity to vote for right-wing populist parties (RWPP) reflects both common patterns and marked gendered distinctions, shaped by ideology, religiosity, economic status, educational background, family situation, and perceptions of structural loss.

Across the population, support for RWPP increases with self-placement on the right of the ideological spectrum and with higher levels of religiosity. These associations are robust across gender, indicating a shared alignment with value-based or traditionalist narratives. However, the ways in which other variables operate vary notably between men and women.

Perceived structural loss is one of the clearest points of divergence. Among men, both identification as a loser of globalisation and as a loser of feminism are significant and equally strong predictors of RWPP voting propensity. In contrast, among women, only the perception of having lost out in the context of globalisation is associated with greater support. The feminism-related dimension does not play a meaningful role for women, suggesting that grievances linked to gender order transformations are a predominantly male entry point into populist-right alignment.

Economic strain is predictive of RWPP voting across both genders, but the mechanisms differ. Among men, subjective financial difficulty—ranging from coping to very difficult—correlates with higher voting propensity. Income levels themselves, however, are not significant. Among women, by contrast, a combined pattern emerges: those with higher personal income but lower household income show greater propensity to support RWPP. This suggests that for women, perceived mismatch between individual contribution and collective household outcomes may drive political disaffection—a pattern not observed among men.

Age plays a role for women but not for men. Younger women are more likely to report support for RWPP than older age groups, consistent with the general trend. Among men, however, support appears more evenly distributed across age brackets, indicating that populist-right alignment is not concentrated in any particular generation.

Educational attainment plays a significant role in the female profile but not in the male one. Among women, having only primary education or none is associated with greater RWPP voting propensity, suggesting that lower levels of formal education may reinforce feelings of distance from political institutions or scepticism toward mainstream agendas. This effect is not observed among men, for whom education does not significantly differentiate voting behaviour.

Employment status differentiates the two profiles. Among women, those in full-time employment report greater RWPP propensity than students—possibly reflecting generational divides or workplace-driven exposure to certain ideological framings. Among men, part-time workers show higher voting propensity than those in full-time employment, suggesting a link between precariousness and support for RWPP narratives of displacement.

Partnership and family structure also show gendered contrasts. In the general population, being in a civil union or separated is associated with higher RWPP support. Among men, however, widowed status is the strongest predictor of increased voting propensity—potentially reflecting relational loss or isolation. In both genders, having more children than average is associated with greater support, reinforcing the idea that larger family units may align more closely with RWPP discourses on tradition, protection, and social order.

Religiosity strengthens voting propensity across both groups, with Eastern Orthodox affiliation more predictive of RWPP support than Roman Catholicism. This may reflect cultural or institutional distance from mainstream religious-national models, combined with stronger emphasis on identity politics within minority faith groups.

In sum, as depicted in Figure 107, while some predictors of RWPP voting are broadly shared—such as ideological orientation, religiosity, and low education—men and women arrive at this alignment through partly distinct pathways. For men, the profile is structured around perceived loss—particularly related to gender and structural change—and economic marginality. For women, support emerges more selectively, shaped by generational, occupational, and household-level dynamics, and closely tied to distance from feminised identities and mainstream political institutions.

Figure 108: Odds ratio predicting having voted for RWPP (overall dataset)

Figure 108 presents the overall predictors of having voted for right-wing populist parties (RWPP), showing that this voting behaviour is shaped by a multidimensional profile combining demographic, socio-economic, ideological, and attitudinal factors. Across the total sample, men are more likely than women to report RWPP support, and younger individuals—especially those under 24—show higher voting propensity than older age groups, particularly those aged 65 and above.

Education is a strong differentiator: individuals with secondary, primary or no formal education report significantly higher RWPP support than those with higher education, suggesting a clear educational gradient. Labour market position also matters; full-time workers are more likely to vote RWPP than retirees or students, pointing to a greater politicisation of those in active employment. Religious affiliation shows a descending pattern of support: individuals identifying with non-Christian religions are most likely to report RWPP voting, followed by Roman Catholics, with support lowest among Muslims. Lower self-placement on the social scale and reporting financial strain (coping or finding it difficult) are also associated with higher voting propensity. Ideological self-placement on the right strongly predicts RWPP support.

Crucially, the strongest predictors are attitudinal: individuals identifying as losers of globalisation and losers of feminism are markedly more likely to support RWPP, underscoring the centrality of perceived structural and identity-based loss in populist-right alignment.

Figure 109: Odds ratio predicting having voted for RWPP (by gender)

Figure 109 disaggregates these patterns by gender, revealing important convergences and divergences in the profiles of men and women who report having voted for RWPP. Among men, voting propensity is significantly higher among those with lower educational attainment—particularly those with secondary, primary or no education. Full-time workers are more likely to report RWPP support than those in part-time roles, and individuals with lower self-placement on the social scale are also more likely to align with RWPP. Right-wing ideological self-placement remains a key predictor. The most distinctive feature of the male profile, however, is the combined effect of both perceived economic and gendered loss: men identifying as losers of globalisation and losers of feminism report the highest odds of RWPP voting.

Among women, a different combination of factors emerges. Age plays a stronger role than in the male profile: young women (under 24) are significantly more likely than older women (65+) to report RWPP support, suggesting a generational effect specific to women. As with men, lower educational attainment is associated with higher support. Women in civil unions report greater voting propensity than those who are married, and those with more children than average are also more likely to support RWPP—indicating a potential link between family structure and political alignment. Employment status shows a distinct pattern: full-time employed women are more likely to support RWPP than female students, possibly reflecting age or workplace-related dynamics. Lower self-placement on the social

scale and financial strain are again predictive, as is ideological positioning on the right. However, the attitudinal profile differs from men: only identification as a loser of globalisation is associated with higher RWPP support. In contrast to men, perceiving oneself as a loser of feminism is not a significant predictor for women.

Taken together, these findings shown in Figures 109 highlight that while some predictors are shared across genders—such as lower education, right-wing ideology, and economic strain—others reflect gendered pathways into RWPP support. For men, political alignment is more clearly structured around perceived displacement in both economic and gender orders. For women, RWPP support appears to stem from a mix of socio-economic pressure, family dynamics, and selective identification with broader structural change, notably excluding grievance linked to feminism. This suggests that gender not only mediates political outcomes but also reshapes the meaning of loss and representation within populist-right narratives.

4. References

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5. Appendixes

Data handling of party families

It is necessary to clarify some points regarding the data handling. Firstly, the variables relating to voting recall were located in the database for the six countries. These variables are listed as follows in the database: q41_uk, q41_dk, q41_hu, q41_es, q41_dk, and q41_ch.

Secondly, the possible options for answering these questions were collected (i.e. different political parties). Then, these political parties were coded according to the MARPOR database (<https://manifesto-project.wzb.eu/>), which uses a widely accepted party families scheme:

Table A 1: Party families from MARPOR dataset

MARPOR scheme
10 ECO Ecological parties
20 LEF Socialist or other left parties
30 SOC Social democratic parties
40 LIB Liberal parties
50 CHR Christian democratic parties
60 CON Conservative parties
70 NAT Nationalist and radical right parties
80 AGR Agrarian parties
90 ETH Ethnic and regional parties
95 SIP Special issue parties
98 DIV Electoral alliances of diverse origin without dominant party

To make our analyses more straightforward, we decided to simplify the MARPOR scheme. Thus, we translated the MARPOR scheme into a 5-party family classification: right-wing populist parties, mainstream right, mainstream left, radical left, and others. The table with the specific codification for each party can be consulted in the appendix. In some cases, for example when there was no data in MARPOR, decisions were made based on knowledge of the topic. In any case, partners can suggest any changes relating to their country.

Table A 2: UNTWIST party families scheme and MARPOR equivalence

MARPOR scheme	UNTWIST party scheme	Acronym in the UNTWIST party scheme
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10 ECO Ecological parties	Mainstream left	ML
30 SOC Social democratic parties		
20 LEF Socialist or other left parties	Radical left	RL
40 LIB Liberal parties	Mainstream right	MR
50 CHR Christian democratic parties		
60 CON Conservative parties		
70 NAT Nationalist and radical right parties	Right-wing populist parties	RWPP
80 AGR Agrarian parties	Other	OTHER
90 ETH Ethnic and regional parties		
95 SIP Special issue parties		
98 DIV Electoral alliances of diverse origin without dominant party		

Also, frequencies and percentages for each party family in each country are shown further below in table A3. It should be noted that the total frequency shown does not include the boost.

Table A 3: Frequencies for each party family in the six countries analysed

Country	Party family										Overall
	RWPP		MR		ML		RL		Other		
	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	
UK	297	18.1	557	34.0	727	44.4	0	0.0	57	3.5	1638
DK	235	23.7	301	30.3	241	24.3	215	21.7	0	0.0	992
HU	413	53.6	56	7.27	49	6.36	140	18.18	112	14.55	770
ES	193	13.7	418	29.7	468	33.2	185	13.1	144	10.2	1408
DE	209	13.4	321	20.5	834	53.3	92	5.9	110	7.02	1566
CH	280	27.4	312	30.6	412	40.4	13	1.3	4	0.39	1021
Overall	1627	22.0	1965	26.6	2731	36.9	645	8.72	427	5.77	7395

Operationalisation of variables

The following table presents the operationalisation of the variables included in the analyses within this deliverable.

Table A 4: Operationalisation of variables included in the analyses

groups of variables	variable	theoretical concept	wording	categories	observations
Sociodemographics	gender_re	Gender	Are you...?	1 = male 2 = female	
	agegp	Age	And in what year were you born?	1= 25-39 2= 40-54 3 = 55-64 4 = 65+	
	educ2	Education	Which is the highest level of education you have successfully completed?	1 = ISCED 0-2 2= ISCED 3-4 3 = ISCED 5-8	
	q49	Civil status	What is your current civil partnership status?	1 = married 2= Civil union 3 = Cohabitation 4 = Divorced 5 = Separated 6 = Widowed 7 = Single	
	children_c ent	Number of sons/daughters/non/binary children (over average)	How many children do you have?	Number of sons/daughters/non/binary children (over average).	The average value in the dataset is 1.35, which is used to operationalise this variable.
	q56	Employment	Are you yourself gainfully employed at the moment or not? Please select the	1 = 30h. pw 2 = <30h. pw 3 = Self-employed 4 = Military serv. ⁵	

⁵ It is important to note that the response option Military service was available in only two of the six countries included in the project—Denmark and Switzerland—accounting for just 7 and 13 cases respectively (0.65% and 1% of each national sample). This is due to the distinction made between military employment and compulsory military service, the latter being treated as a separate labour market category. This limitation has clear implications for the interpretation of related findings, as they cannot be extrapolated to the full sample

groups of variables	variable	theoretical concept	wording	categories	observations
			employment status that applies to you.	5 = Retired 6 = Housemaker 7 = Student 8 = Unemployed 9 = Disabled 10 = Other	
	q57_cent	Respondent's income (over average)	Using this card, please tell me which letter describes your personal total income, after tax and compulsory deductions, from all sources? If you don't know the exact figure, please give an estimate.	The response categories correspond to net income deciles for each country, based on data from official national sources. For detailed information on the specific income deciles used in each country, the reader is referred to Ruiz Jiménez, A. M., Bartolomé Peral, E., & Sendra, M. (2025). UNTWIST representative survey on gendered political behaviour in six European countries, with RWPP voters oversampling [Data set]. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15083114	The average value in the dataset is 4.55, which is used to operationalise this variable.
	q58_cent	Household's income (over average)	Which of the descriptions on this card comes closest to how you feel about your household's income nowadays?	UNTWIST representative survey on gendered political behaviour in six European countries, with RWPP voters oversampling [Data set]. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15083114	The average value in the dataset is 5.85, which is used to operationalise this variable.
	q53	Religion	Do you consider yourself as belonging to any particular religion or denomination? Which one?	1 = Roman Catholic 2 = Protestant 3 = Eastern Orthodox 4 = Other Christian = Jewish 6 = Islam 7 = Eastern religions 8 = Other non-Christian	

by default. While other low-frequency response categories—such as those related to religion, partnership status, or employment situation—may also yield wide confidence intervals, the Military service category is particularly affected. Given that it was only recorded in one-third of the surveyed countries, estimates for this group will systematically exhibit very wide confidence intervals.

groups of variables	variable	theoretical concept	wording	categories	observations
				9 = No denomination 10 = Other 11 = None	
Attitudes and perceptions	q30	Status loss	If you think about the lives of people like you in the past, which of these statements best represents your thoughts?	1 = Life was better for people like me in the past 2 = Life was about the same for people like me in the past 3 = Life was worse for people like me in the past	
	q32	Status threat	Now, if you think about what the future will be like for people like you, which of these statements best represents your thoughts?	1 = Life will be better for people like me in the future 2 = Life will be about the same for people like me in the future 3 = Life will be worse for people like me in the future	
	q31	Anger regarding status loss	*Note: question asked regarding q30 (status loss) And how does this make you feel?	1 = Depressed 2 = Angry 3 = Indifferent 4 = Excited	
	q33	Anger regarding status threat	*Note: question asked regarding q31 (status threat) And how does this make you feel?	1 = Depressed 2 = Angry 3 = Indifferent 4 = Excited	
	q55_1	Ideology: right/left self-placement	In politics, people sometimes talk of the 'left' and the 'right'. Where would you place yourself on this scale, where 0 means left and 10 means right?	0 = left 10 = right	

groups of variables	variable	theoretical concept	wording	categories	observations
	q59	Satisfaction income	Which of the descriptions on this card comes closest to how you feel about your household's income nowadays?	1 = Comfortably 2 = Coping 3 = Difficult 4 = Very Difficult	
	soscale_cent	Self-placement in social scale	In our society, there are groups which tend to be towards the top and groups which tend to be towards the bottom. Below is a scale that runs from the top (10 on the scale) to the bottom (01 on the scale). Where would you put yourself on this scale?	0 (bottom) to 10 (top)	The average value in the dataset is 5.5, which is used to operationalise this variable.
	q54_1_cent	Religiosity (over average)	Regardless of whether you belong to a particular religion, how religious would you say you are? Please use this scale from 0 to 10, where 0 means not at all religious, and 10 means very religious.	0 (not all religious) to 10 (very religious).	The average value in the dataset is 3.63, which is used to operationalise this variable.
	q36_1	Own deservingness	On a scale from 1 to 5, where 1 means you totally disagree with the statement and 5 means that you totally agree with the statement, please tell me how much you	1 = Totally disagree (People like me are more deserving than others based on the benefits we bring to our society) 2 = Totally agree (People like me are more deserving than others based on the	

groups of variables	variable	theoretical concept	wording	categories	observations
			agree with the following statement: People like me are more deserving than others	benefits we bring to our society)	
Gendered Collective Identity (GCI)	male_gci	Male Gendered Collective Identity (GCI)	*Note: This variable is not asked directly but is created from other variables. See the next row for more information	0 (when the individual does not identify with male gender and any of the other identities at the same time) to 6 (when the individual identifies with male gender and all the identities presented at the same time). Identities provided are class, age, ethnicity, religion, sexual orientation, nationality	
	female_gci	Female Gendered Collective Identity (GCI)	*Note: This variable is not asked directly but is created from other variables. See the next row for more information	0 (when the individual does not identify with female gender - and any of the other identities at the same time) to 6 (when the individual identifies with female gender and all the identities presented at the same time). Identities provided are class, age, ethnicity, religion, sexual orientation, nationality	
Losers of Feminism & Globalisation	If	Losers of feminism	*Note: This variable is not asked directly, but is created from other variables. See the next row for more information	1 = when individuals have the following characteristics. This profile has been operationalized by selecting individuals with non-zero level of Gendered Collective Identity (male or female GCI), a	

groups of variables	variable	theoretical concept	wording	categories	observations
				<p>perception that life was better in the past or will be worse in the future for people like them (and that this causes anger), a propensity to blame feminism for this, and perceiving men or women as enjoying unfair advantages in society</p> <p>0 = the rest</p>	
	lg	Losers of globalisation	<p>*Note: This variable is not asked directly but is created from other variables. See the next row for more information</p>	<p>1 = Individuals with the following characteristics. Believing that life used to be better for people like them, that life will be worse for people like them in the future, that this makes you feel angry, blaming to globalization, capitalism, elites or European Union, and perceiving immigrants as enjoying unfair advantages in society</p> <p>0 = the rest</p>	
	gpd	Gendered Positional Deprivation	<p>*Note: This variable is not asked directly but is created from other variables. See the next row for more information</p>	<p>1 = This profile includes individuals (male or female) with a non-zero level of Gendered Collective Identity (male or female GCI) and a perception that life was better in the past or will be worse in the future for people like them.</p> <p>0= the rest</p>	
	rd_lg	Relative Deprivation	<p>*Note: This variable is not</p>	<p>1 = Individuals with the following characteristics. that</p>	

groups of variables	variable	theoretical concept	wording	categories	observations
			asked directly but is created from other variables. See the next row for more information	life used to be better for people like me, that life will be worse for people like me in the future, 0 = the rest	
Voting behaviour	vr_parfam	Voting recall for party families	Which party did you vote for at the General Election in [<i>last year of national elections in each country</i>]?	1 = RWPP (right-wing populist parties) 2 = ML (mainstream left) 3 = MR (mainstream right) 4 = RL (radical left) 5 = Other	The equivalence of each party with the party families scheme can be consulted in the appendix (table A1).
	ptv	Propensity to vote	We have a number of parties in [<i>each country</i>], each of which would like to get your vote. How likely is it that you will ever vote for the following parties? Please answer on a scale where 0 means not at all likely and 10 means very likely.	*Note: A list of the main parties is provided for each country. Parties are classified using UNTWIST party scheme (see tables 2 and A1). 0 = not all likely 10 = very likely	The equivalence of each party with the party families scheme can be consulted in the appendix (table A1).
	q45	Closeness to parties	Considering those challenging aspects you mentioned in the previous question, rate the three parties that best represent your thoughts on a scale from 0 to 10, where 0 means that the party does not represent your thoughts at all, and 10 means	A list of the main parties is provided for each country. Parties are classified using UNTWIST party scheme (see tables 2 and A1).	The equivalence of each party with the party families scheme can be consulted in the appendix (table A1).

groups of variables	variable	theoretical concept	wording	categories	observations
			that the party represents perfectly your thoughts.		
	q46	Instrumental vote	In your opinion, how likely are those three parties that best represent your thoughts to gain representation in the parliament? Please use this scale from 0 to 10, where 0 means that the party is not likely to gain representation in parliament, and 10 means that the party is very likely to gain representation in parliament.	<p>Respondents are asked about the three parties mentioned in the variable q45 (closeness to parties).</p> <p>0 = the party is not likely to gain representation on parliament</p> <p>10 = the party is very likely to gain representation on parliament</p>	
	q47	Perception of strength to push policies)		<p>Respondents are asked about the three parties mentioned in the variable q45 (closeness to parties).</p> <p>0 = No strength to push policies in the direction that best represents my thoughts</p> <p>10 = A lot of strength to push policies in the direction that best represents my thoughts.</p>	
	q48	Perception of credibility to push policies		Respondents are asked about the three parties mentioned in the variable q45 (closeness to parties).	

groups of variables	variable	theoretical concept	wording	categories	observations
				<p>0 = The party is not credible at all to push policies in the direction that best represents my thoughts</p> <p>10 = The party is totally credible in pushing policies in the direction that best represents my thoughts.</p>	
Countries	hcountry	Country	<p>*Note: This variable is not asked in the survey but is included in the database after collection.</p>	<p>1 = UK 2 = Denmark 3 = Hungary 4 = Spain 5 = Germany 6 = Switzerland</p>	

Specification of Statistical Models for Cross-Country Multivariate Analyses

In this section, we provide a systematic description of the models to be implemented in the empirical component of the study. This description presented in Table 5, specifies for each substantive variable of interest, the dependent variable (DV), the type of statistical analysis employed—whether linear regression models (OLS), logistic regression (logit), or correlational analyses—selected according to the nature of the DV and the research question. Additionally, for each model, the table lists the independent variables and control variables included, with justification grounded in theory and prior empirical work. This approach is designed to ensure methodological transparency and facilitate replication by clearly delineating how each model accounts for confounding variables and addresses cross-national heterogeneity (through country-fixed effects). Table 5 will thus serve as the central reference for the modelling strategy adopted in the forthcoming Cross-Country Multivariate Analyses section, providing a detailed and structured overview of the analytical choices made for each research question.

Table A 5: Overview of statistical analyses and variables

Section	Model	Dependent variable	Independent Variables				
			Sociodemographics ⁶	Attitudes and perceptions ⁷	Gendered Collective Identity (GCI) ⁸	Losers of Feminism & Globalisation	Voting behaviour
3.1. Gendered Collective Identity	Linear (country fixed effects)	Gendered Collective Identity (GCI; male and female)	✓	✓ (all variables are included, except for ideological self-placement)			✓ (only voting recall for party families is included)
3.2. Relative Deprivation (cognitive dimension)	Logit (country fixed effects)	Relative Deprivation	✓	✓ (all variables are included, except for ideological self-placement)	✓		✓ (only voting recall for party families is included)
3.3. Relative Deprivation (affective dimension)	Logit (country fixed effects)	Anger on Relative Deprivation	✓	✓ (all variables are included, except	✓		✓ (only voting recall for

⁶ Sociodemographics systematically includes: gender, age groups, level of education, partnership status, religious belonging, employment status, respondents' personal income, respondents' household income. When analyses are disaggregated by gender, the gender variable is logically omitted from the set of covariates, as the models are estimated separately for male and female subsamples.

⁷ Attitudes and perceptions systematically include: level of religiosity, income satisfaction, social scale self-placement

⁸ When analyses are disaggregated by gender, the variable Gendered Collective Identity (GCI) is specified accordingly: in models estimated for women, only the female GCI measure is included, while in models for men, only the male GCI measure is employed. Although it is both empirically and theoretically valid to recognise that men may exhibit a feminised collective identity and women a masculinised one, these cross-collective gender identity dynamics fall outside the scope of this deliverable and will not be examined here. This modelling choice is intended to maintain conceptual clarity and to focus the analysis on gender-specific patterns of collective identification within each subsample.

Section	Model	Dependent variable	Independent Variables				
			Sociodemographics ⁶	Attitudes and perceptions ⁷	Gendered Collective Identity (GCI) ⁸	Losers of Feminism & Globalisation	Voting behaviour
				for ideological self-placement			party families is included)
3.4. Unfairly Advantaged Social Groups	Logit (country fixed effects)	Unfair advantaged groups	✓	✓ (all variables are included , except for ideological self-placement)	✓		✓ (only voting recall for party families is included) ✓ ✓
3.5. Losers of Feminism and Gender Positional Deprivation	Logit (country fixed effects)	Losers of Feminism	✓	✓ (all variables are included , except for ideological self-placement)	✓		✓ (only voting recall for party families is included)
	Logit (country fixed effects E	Aggrieved male/female groups	✓	✓ (all variables are included , except for ideological self-	✓		✓ (only voting recall for party families is

Section	Model	Dependent variable	Independent Variables				
			Sociodemographics ⁶	Attitudes and perceptions ⁷	Gendered Collective Identity (GCI) ⁸	Losers of Feminism & Globalisation	Voting behaviour
				placement			included)
3.6. Losers of Globalisation	Correlational	Losers of Globalisation	✓	✓ (all variables are included, except for ideological self-placement)	✓		✓ (only voting recall for party families is included)
3.7. Losers of Feminism and Losers of Globalisation	Logit (country fixed effects E	Losers of Feminism vs. Globalisation					
3.8. Perceived Challenges	Logit (country fixed effects	Perceived challenges	✓	✓ (all variables are included, except for ideological self-placement)	✓	✓	✓ (only voting recall for party families is included)
3.9. Closeness to RWPP	Correlational	RWPP closeness	✓ (✓ (all variables are included, except	✓	✓	✓ (only voting recall for

Section	Model	Dependent variable	Independent Variables				
			Sociodemographics ⁶	Attitudes and perceptions ⁷	Gendered Collective Identity (GCI) ⁸	Losers of Feminism & Globalisation	Voting behaviour
				for ideological self-placement			party families included)
3.10. Instrumentality of Vote	Linear (country fixed effects)	Instrumentality of vote					
3.11. Explanatory analyses of voting RWPP	Linear (country fixed effects)	Propensity to vote RWPP	✓	✓	✓	✓	

Table A 6: UNTWIST party family scheme

Country	variable (voting recall)	numerical category	party name	MARP OR party family	MARP OR party family revised	Notes	UNTWIST party classification
UK	q41_uk	1	Conservative Party	con	con		MR
		2	Labour Party	soc	soc		ML
		3	Liberal Democrats	lib	lib		MR
		4	Green Party	eco	eco		ML
		5	UKIP	sip	nat	*In MARPOR, it is categorised as a special issue party, but we consider it a nationalist (RWPP).	RWPP
		8	Scottish National Party	eth	eth		OTHER
		9	Plaid Cymru	etch	eth		OTHER
		60	Reform UK	/	nat	*Not listed in MARPOR. We categorise it as nationalist	RWPP

Country	variable (voting recall)	numerical category	party name	MARP OR party family	MARP OR party family revised	Notes	UNTWIS T party classification
						based on our knowledge.	
DENMARK	q41_dk	1	Dansk Folkeparti	nat	nat		RWPP
		2	Nye Borgerlige	nat	nat		RWPP
		3	Danmarksdemokraterne	/	nat	*Not listed in MARPOR. We categorise it as nationalist based on our knowledge.	RWPP
		4	Socialdemokratiet	soc	soc		ML
		5	Liberal Alliance	lib	lib		MR
		6	Venstre	lib	lib		MR
		7	Det Konservative Folkeparti	con	con		MR
		8	Enhedslisten	lef	lef		RL
		9	Socialistisk Folkeparti	lef	lef		RL
		10	Moderaterne	lib	lib		MR

Country	variable (voting recall)	numerical category	party name	MARP OR party family	MARP OR party family revised	Notes	UNTWIST party classification
HUNGARY	q41_hu	1	Democratic Koalitin	lef	lef		ML
		2	FIDESZ	con	nat	*In MARPOR, it is categorised as a conservative party, but UNTWIST project considers it	RWPP

Country	variable (voting recall)	numerical category	party name	MARPOR party family	MARPOR party family revised	Notes	UNTWIST party classification
						a nationalist (RWPP).	
		3	Jobbik	nat	con	*In MARPOR, it is categorised as a nationalist, but UNTWIST project considers it a conservative)	MR
		4	Kereszténydemokrata Néppárt	con	con		RWPP
		5	Lehet Más A Politika	eco	eco		OTHER
		6	Memo	/	oth	*Not listed in MARPOR. We categorise it as other based on our knowledge.	
		7	Mi Hazánk	/	nat	*Not listed in MARPOR. We categorise it as nationalist based on our knowledge.	RWPP

Country	variable (voting recall)	numerical category	party name	MARPOR party family	MARPOR party family revised	Notes	UNTWIS T party classification
		8	MKKP	/	oth	*Not listed in MARPOR. We categorise it as other based on our knowledge.	OTHER
		9	Momentum	/	oth	*Not listed in MARPOR. We categorise it as other based on our knowledge.	OTHER
		10	Magyar Szocialista Párt	soc	soc		ML
		11	Normális Párt	/	oth	*Not listed in MARPOR. We categorise it as other based on our knowledge.	OTHER
		12	Párbeszéd	lef	lef		ML

Country	variable (voting recall)	numerical category	party name	MARP OR party family	MARP OR party family revised	Notes	UNTWIS T party classification
SPAIN	q41_ es	1	PP	con	con		MR
		2	PSOE	soc	soc		ML
		3	VOX	nat	nat		RWPP
		4	Sumar	lef	lef		RL
		5	ERC	eth	eth		OTHER
		6	Junts x Cat	eth	eth		OTHER
		7	EH Bildu	eth	eth		OTHER
		8	EAJ-PNV	eth	eth		OTHER
		9	BN	eth	eth		OTHER
		10	Coalición Canaria	eth	eth		OTHER
		14	Teruel Existe	eth	eth		OTHER

Country	variable (voting recall)	numerical category	party name	MARP OR party family	MARP OR party family revised	Notes	UNTWIS T party classification
GERMANY	q41_de	1	SPD	soc	soc		ML
		2	CDU	chr	chr		MR
		3	Bündnis 90/Die Grünen	eco	eco		ML
		4	FDP	lib	lib		MR

Country	variable (voting recall)	numerical category	party name	MARP OR party family	MARPOR party family revised	Notes	UNTWIS T party classification
		5	AfD	nat	nat		RWPP
		6	CSU	chr	chr		MR
		7	Die Linke	lef	lef		RL
		8	SSW	eth	eth		OTHER
		9	FREIE WÄHLER	/	oth	*Not listed in MARPOR. We categorise it as other based on our knowledge.	OTHER
		10	Tierschutzpartei	/	oth	*Not listed in MARPOR. We categorise it as other based on our knowledge.	OTHER
		11	dieBasis	/	oth	*Not listed in MARPOR. We categorise it as other based on our knowledge.	OTHER
		12	Die PARTEI	/	oth	*Not listed in MARPOR. We categorise it as other based on our knowledge.	OTHER

Country	variable (voting recall)	numerical category	party name	MARP OR party family	MARP OR party family revised	Notes	UNTWIS T party classification
		13	Team Todenhöfer	/	oth	*Not listed in MARPOR. We categorise it as other based on our knowledge.	OTHER
		14	PIRATEN	/	oth	*Not listed in MARPOR. We categorise it as other based on our knowledge.	OTHER
		15	Volt	/	oth	*Not listed in MARPOR. We categorise it as other based on our knowledge.	OTHER
		16	ÖDP	/	oth	*Not listed in MARPOR. We categorise it as other based on our knowledge.	OTHER
		17	NPD	/	nat	*Not listed in MARPOR. We categorise it as	RWPP

Country	variable (voting recall)	numerical category	party name	MARP OR party family	MARP OR party family revised	Notes	UNTWIS T party classification
						nationalist based on our knowledge.	
SWITZERLAND	q41_ch	1	UDC	nat	nat		RWPP
		2	PS	soc	soc		ML
		3	PLR	lib	lib		MR
		4	PES	eco	eco		ML
		5	PDC	chr	chr		MR
		6	PVL	eco	eco		ML
		7	PEV	chr	chr		MR
		8	UDF	nat	nat		RWPP

Country	variable (voting recall)	numerical category	party name	MARPOR party family	MARPOR party family revised	Notes	UNTWIST party classification
		9	Lega Ticino	eth	nat	*In MARPOR, it is categorised as a ethnic party, but UNTWIST project considers it a nationalist (RWPP).	RWPP
		10	PST-POP	lef	lef		RL
		11	EáG/AL	lef	lef		RL
		12	CG-PCS	chr	chr		MR
		13	LDP	lib	lib		MR
		14	MCR	eth	nat	*In MARPOR, it is categorised as a ethnic party, but UNTWIST project considers it a nationalist (RWPP).	RWPP
		15	Pirate	/	oth	*Not listed in MARPOR. We categorise it as other based on our knowledge.	OTHER

Models

Table A 7. Linear regression. DV: GCI

Variables	(1) Male GCI - Overall	(2) Male GCI - Men	(3) Female GCI - Overall	(4) Female GCI - Women
Vote recall (UNTWIST scheme) (<i>ref. cat. RWPP</i>)				
MR	-0.104* (0.0611)	-0.216** (0.110)	0.0317 (0.0462)	0.0999 (0.0986)
ML	-0.162*** (0.0542)	-0.335*** (0.0978)	0.173*** (0.0460)	0.378*** (0.0954)
RL	-0.222*** (0.0723)	-0.384*** (0.136)	0.240*** (0.0753)	0.483*** (0.147)
Other	-0.0684 (0.0867)	-0.164 (0.175)	0.140 (0.0882)	0.371** (0.164)
Gender (<i>ref. cat. Men</i>)				
Women	-0.782*** (0.0339)		1.286*** (0.0359)	
Age group (<i>ref. cat. 18-24</i>)				
25-39	-0.105 (0.0935)	-0.312* (0.177)	0.00976 (0.0843)	-0.0242 (0.159)
40-54	-0.211** (0.0978)	-0.585*** (0.190)	-0.146* (0.0865)	-0.315* (0.161)
55-64	-0.235** (0.102)	-0.662*** (0.198)	-0.225** (0.0924)	-0.512*** (0.174)
65+	-0.273** (0.113)	-0.811*** (0.213)	-0.502*** (0.105)	-1.011*** (0.192)
Education (<i>ref. cat. ISCED 0-2</i>)				
ISCED 3-4	-0.0186 (0.0550)	-0.0820 (0.110)	0.0934* (0.0508)	0.171* (0.0964)
ISCED 5-8	0.0411 (0.0551)	0.0709 (0.109)	0.235*** (0.0503)	0.451*** (0.0989)
Social scale self-placement (centered)	0.0171 (0.0128)	0.0298 (0.0253)	0.0170 (0.0126)	0.0412* (0.0242)
Civil status (<i>ref. cat. Married</i>)				
Civil union	0.0559 (0.138)	0.117 (0.253)	-0.190* (0.100)	-0.335* (0.184)
Cohabitation	-0.0852 (0.0546)	-0.171 (0.110)	-0.0317 (0.0579)	-0.118 (0.112)
Divorced	-0.0651 (0.0488)	-0.189* (0.107)	0.0235 (0.0664)	0.105 (0.116)
Separated	-0.214*** (0.0732)	-0.499*** (0.144)	0.229* (0.135)	0.410* (0.243)
Widowed	0.00550 (0.0738)	0.0147 (0.211)	-0.203** (0.0824)	-0.142 (0.128)
Single	-0.0437 (0.0564)	-0.145 (0.113)	-0.0420 (0.0587)	-0.0815 (0.115)

Variables	(1) Male GCI - Overall	(2) Male GCI - Men	(3) Female GCI - Overall	(4) Female GCI - Women
Number of children (centered)	0.00436 (0.0112)	-0.00247 (0.0278)	0.00377 (0.0162)	0.0127 (0.0301)
Religion (<i>ref. cat. Roman-Catholic</i>)				
Protestant	0.0379 (0.0523)	0.0842 (0.106)	0.131** (0.0567)	0.272*** (0.104)
Eastern Orthodox	0.0822 (0.210)	0.0982 (0.327)	-0.00918 (0.165)	0.131 (0.365)
Other Christian	-0.153 (0.105)	-0.309 (0.225)	-0.0357 (0.132)	-0.0563 (0.242)
Jewish	-0.307* (0.174)	-0.604** (0.272)	-0.243 (0.199)	-0.123 (0.420)
Islam	0.279 (0.228)	0.752* (0.453)	0.0995 (0.141)	0.162 (0.258)
Eastern religions	-0.203 (0.136)	-0.306 (0.248)	-0.0961 (0.153)	-0.195 (0.329)
Other non-Christian	-0.282*** (0.100)	-0.392** (0.171)	-0.277** (0.123)	-0.427* (0.243)
No denomination	-0.0975* (0.0530)	-0.152 (0.103)	0.0788 (0.0566)	0.147 (0.110)
Other	-0.154 (0.123)	-0.250 (0.269)	0.718* (0.408)	1.050 (0.675)
None	0.00518 (0.0552)	0.0562 (0.109)	0.0932 (0.0614)	0.154 (0.118)
Level of religiosity (centered)	-0.00556 (0.00612)	-0.00440 (0.0118)	0.00921 (0.00699)	0.0162 (0.0131)
Employment (<i>ref. cat. >30h. pw</i>)				
<30h. pw	-0.152*** (0.0444)	-0.430*** (0.129)	0.0481 (0.0771)	0.00376 (0.112)
Self-empl.	-0.0276 (0.0914)	-0.0194 (0.160)	0.0178 (0.0793)	0.00491 (0.176)
Military serv.	0.597 (0.680)	1.743** (0.821)	0.849 (0.615)	2.154*** (0.435)
Retired	-0.113 (0.0725)	-0.0923 (0.134)	0.116* (0.0657)	0.122 (0.131)
Housemaker	0.0282 (0.0619)	0.323 (0.392)	-0.0876 (0.139)	-0.00361 (0.163)
Student	-0.00901 (0.105)	-0.0598 (0.199)	0.183 (0.115)	0.346 (0.227)
Unemployed	-0.0537 (0.127)	-0.0568 (0.267)	-0.0947 (0.0934)	-0.132 (0.166)
Disable	-0.209*** (0.0620)	-0.448*** (0.131)	-0.377*** (0.115)	-0.610*** (0.176)
Other	-0.130* (0.0720)	-0.155 (0.178)	0.177 (0.128)	0.165 (0.212)
Income satisfaction (<i>ref. cat. Comfortably</i>)				

Variables	(1) Male GCI - Overall	(2) Male GCI - Men	(3) Female GCI - Overall	(4) Female GCI - Women
Coping	-0.00576 (0.0384)	-0.0439 (0.0729)	-0.0965** (0.0424)	-0.172** (0.0852)
Difficult	0.00558 (0.0630)	-0.0209 (0.130)	-0.197*** (0.0643)	-0.352*** (0.119)
Very difficult	-0.124 (0.0845)	-0.268 (0.179)	-0.0957 (0.105)	-0.188 (0.181)
Personal income (centered)	-3.48e-05 (0.00863)	0.00672 (0.0188)	-0.0130 (0.00960)	-0.0231 (0.0176)
Household income (centered)	-0.00846 (0.00858)	-0.0212 (0.0187)	0.00683 (0.00949)	0.00367 (0.0169)
Country (<i>ref. cat. UK</i>)				
Denmark	0.0499 (0.0600)	0.0852 (0.114)	-0.136** (0.0622)	-0.334*** (0.125)
Hungary	0.147* (0.0830)	0.429*** (0.158)	0.261*** (0.0828)	0.483*** (0.165)
Spain	-0.0921 (0.0584)	-0.178 (0.117)	-0.167** (0.0653)	-0.341*** (0.125)
Germany	0.0142 (0.0504)	-0.00576 (0.0990)	0.00274 (0.0560)	0.0861 (0.109)
Switzerland	-0.0184 (0.0670)	-0.0746 (0.130)	-0.0411 (0.0645)	-0.0197 (0.125)
Index of Pop-up flags (GCI)	0.378*** (0.0988)	0.153* (0.0925)	0.427*** (0.0859)	0.334*** (0.126)
Constant	1.177*** (0.143)	1.740*** (0.265)	-0.00814 (0.116)	1.265*** (0.221)
Observations	7,044	3,145	7,044	3,899
R-squared	0.159	0.072	0.253	0.106

Standard errors in parentheses
*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

Table A 8. Logit. DV: Relative Deprivation - Cognitive dimension

Variables	(1) Status Loss - Overall	(2) Status Loss - Men	(3) Status Loss - Women	(4) Status Threat - Overall	(5) Status Threat - Men	(6) Status Threat - Women
Vote recall (UNTWIST scheme) (<i>ref. cat. RWPP</i>)						
MR	0.603*** (0.0596)	0.709** (0.0991)	0.464*** (0.0666)	0.700*** (0.0648)	0.709** (0.0991)	0.464*** (0.0666)
ML	0.412*** (0.0399)	0.462*** (0.0642)	0.342*** (0.0471)	0.598*** (0.0527)	0.462*** (0.0642)	0.342*** (0.0471)
RL	0.518*** (0.0827)	0.539*** (0.120)	0.461*** (0.104)	0.953 (0.142)	0.539*** (0.120)	0.461*** (0.104)
Other	0.712** (0.105)	0.533*** (0.119)	0.820 (0.162)	0.723** (0.103)	0.533*** (0.119)	0.820 (0.162)
Gender (<i>ref. cat. Men</i>)						
Women	0.803*** (0.0674)			0.936 (0.0707)		
Age group (<i>ref. cat. 18-24</i>)						
25-39	0.880 (0.139)	0.664* (0.159)	1.254 (0.271)	1.232 (0.198)	0.664* (0.159)	1.254 (0.271)
40-54	0.932 (0.153)	0.713 (0.180)	1.293 (0.288)	1.753*** (0.290)	0.713 (0.180)	1.293 (0.288)
55-64	0.719* (0.126)	0.499*** (0.133)	1.066 (0.258)	2.205*** (0.387)	0.499*** (0.133)	1.066 (0.258)
65+	0.601** (0.127)	0.340*** (0.107)	1.059 (0.315)	1.891*** (0.384)	0.340*** (0.107)	1.059 (0.315)
Education (<i>ref. cat. ISCED 0-2</i>)						
ISCED 3-4	1.011 (0.114)	1.273 (0.207)	0.821 (0.131)	1.070 (0.113)	1.273 (0.207)	0.821 (0.131)
ISCED 5-8	0.917 (0.102)	1.211 (0.193)	0.694** (0.110)	0.977 (0.102)	1.211 (0.193)	0.694** (0.110)
Social scale self- placement (centered)	0.922*** (0.0239)	0.888*** (0.0331)	0.961 (0.0339)	0.872*** (0.0210)	0.888*** (0.0331)	0.961 (0.0339)
Civil status (<i>ref. cat. Married</i>)						
Civil union	1.014 (0.228)	0.950 (0.312)	1.146 (0.317)	0.558*** (0.120)	0.950 (0.312)	1.146 (0.317)
Cohabitation	1.149 (0.133)	1.027 (0.172)	1.329* (0.213)	1.082 (0.116)	1.027 (0.172)	1.329* (0.213)
Divorced	0.909 (0.119)	0.924 (0.186)	0.928 (0.164)	0.964 (0.113)	0.924 (0.186)	0.928 (0.164)
Separated	0.900 (0.222)	1.162 (0.454)	0.732 (0.243)	0.845 (0.170)	1.162 (0.454)	0.732 (0.243)
Widowed	1.274 (0.230)	1.625 (0.512)	1.139 (0.261)	0.786 (0.119)	1.625 (0.512)	1.139 (0.261)
Single	0.936 (0.102)	0.781 (0.124)	1.147 (0.175)	0.899 (0.0915)	0.781 (0.124)	1.147 (0.175)

Variables	(1) Status Loss - Overall	(2) Status Loss - Men	(3) Status Loss - Women	(4) Status Threat - Overall	(5) Status Threat - Men	(6) Status Threat - Women
Number of children (centered)	1.021 (0.0279)	1.040 (0.0460)	1.001 (0.0333)	0.952** (0.0236)	1.040 (0.0460)	1.001 (0.0333)
Religion (<i>ref. cat. Roman-Catholic</i>)						
Protestant	0.891 (0.0940)	0.790 (0.121)	0.963 (0.144)	0.938 (0.0915)	0.790 (0.121)	0.963 (0.144)
Eastern Orthodox	1.424 (0.502)	1.100 (0.531)	1.742 (0.846)	0.358*** (0.138)	1.100 (0.531)	1.742 (0.846)
Other Christian	0.867 (0.195)	0.842 (0.268)	0.888 (0.272)	0.787 (0.173)	0.842 (0.268)	0.888 (0.272)
Jewish	1.696 (0.850)	0.854 (0.578)	3.764** (2.496)	0.967 (0.420)	0.854 (0.578)	3.764** (2.496)
Islam	1.164 (0.343)	1.027 (0.481)	1.325 (0.512)	0.597* (0.177)	1.027 (0.481)	1.325 (0.512)
Eastern religions	0.538 (0.216)	0.213*** (0.105)	1.360 (0.756)	0.807 (0.258)	0.213*** (0.105)	1.360 (0.756)
Other non-Christian	0.963 (0.415)	0.936 (0.486)	0.765 (0.573)	1.151 (0.456)	0.936 (0.486)	0.765 (0.573)
No denomination	1.000 (0.118)	0.896 (0.147)	1.093 (0.189)	1.032 (0.110)	0.896 (0.147)	1.093 (0.189)
Other	0.954 (0.701)	0.525 (0.719)	1.676 (1.427)	0.919 (0.546)	0.525 (0.719)	1.676 (1.427)
None	0.838 (0.0975)	0.688** (0.112)	1.005 (0.170)	1.059 (0.115)	0.688** (0.112)	1.005 (0.170)
Level of religiosity (centered)	1.005 (0.0138)	0.995 (0.0194)	1.015 (0.0198)	0.973** (0.0123)	0.995 (0.0194)	1.015 (0.0198)
Employment (<i>ref. cat. >30h. pw</i>)						
<30h. pw	0.773** (0.100)	0.942 (0.240)	0.715** (0.112)	1.000 (0.120)	0.942 (0.240)	0.715** (0.112)
Self-empl.	0.789 (0.134)	0.865 (0.203)	0.684 (0.173)	0.820 (0.132)	0.865 (0.203)	0.684 (0.173)
Military serv.	1.705 (1.238)	2.110 (2.172)	1.427 (1.406)	0.331 (0.299)	2.110 (2.172)	1.427 (1.406)
Retired	0.684*** (0.100)	0.860 (0.169)	0.551*** (0.120)	1.090 (0.145)	0.860 (0.169)	0.551*** (0.120)
Housemaker	0.830 (0.159)	1.101 (0.666)	0.745 (0.157)	0.832 (0.159)	1.101 (0.666)	0.745 (0.157)
Student	0.597** (0.131)	0.636 (0.197)	0.576* (0.179)	1.018 (0.217)	0.636 (0.197)	0.576* (0.179)
Unemployed	0.682* (0.133)	0.614 (0.183)	0.795 (0.195)	1.227 (0.228)	0.614 (0.183)	0.795 (0.195)
Disable	0.757 (0.222)	0.796 (0.351)	0.769 (0.291)	1.060 (0.266)	0.796 (0.351)	0.769 (0.291)
Other	0.854	1.493	0.628*	1.625***	1.493	0.628*

Variables	(1) Status Loss - Overall	(2) Status Loss - Men	(3) Status Loss - Women	(4) Status Threat - Overall	(5) Status Threat - Men	(6) Status Threat - Women
	(0.171)	(0.473)	(0.174)	(0.305)	(0.473)	(0.174)
Income satisfaction (<i>ref. cat. Comfortably</i>)						
Coping	1.472*** (0.123)	1.872*** (0.212)	1.090 (0.133)	1.199** (0.0884)	1.872*** (0.212)	1.090 (0.133)
Difficult	2.638*** (0.321)	3.155*** (0.564)	2.178*** (0.361)	1.546*** (0.177)	3.155*** (0.564)	2.178*** (0.361)
Very difficult	2.934*** (0.591)	3.150*** (0.970)	2.556*** (0.663)	2.076*** (0.426)	3.150*** (0.970)	2.556*** (0.663)
Personal income (centered)	0.970 (0.0184)	0.964 (0.0278)	0.966 (0.0251)	1.015 (0.0171)	0.964 (0.0278)	0.966 (0.0251)
Household income (centered)	1.033* (0.0189)	1.052* (0.0296)	1.024 (0.0257)	1.002 (0.0164)	1.052* (0.0296)	1.024 (0.0257)
Country (<i>ref. cat. UK</i>)						
Denmark	0.278*** (0.0378)	0.256*** (0.0482)	0.297*** (0.0591)	0.320*** (0.0380)	0.256*** (0.0482)	0.297*** (0.0591)
Hungary	0.759* (0.111)	0.670* (0.141)	0.779 (0.164)	0.418*** (0.0568)	0.670* (0.141)	0.779 (0.164)
Spain	0.570*** (0.0727)	0.529*** (0.0956)	0.579*** (0.107)	0.694*** (0.0823)	0.529*** (0.0956)	0.579*** (0.107)
Germany	0.756*** (0.0764)	0.659*** (0.0932)	0.817 (0.119)	1.165 (0.110)	0.659*** (0.0932)	0.817 (0.119)
Switzerland	0.464*** (0.0610)	0.408*** (0.0748)	0.499*** (0.0948)	0.725*** (0.0864)	0.408*** (0.0748)	0.499*** (0.0948)
Male GCI	1.084*** (0.0326)	1.087*** (0.0343)	1.159 (0.187)	1.006 (0.0273)	1.087*** (0.0343)	1.159 (0.187)
Female GCI	0.952* (0.0244)	0.843 (0.176)	0.957* (0.0251)	0.941*** (0.0218)	0.843 (0.176)	0.957* (0.0251)
Constant	1.604** (0.382)	1.711 (0.603)	1.322 (0.436)	1.053 (0.241)	1.711 (0.603)	1.322 (0.436)
Observations	7,044	3,145	3,899	7,044	3,145	3,899

Standard errors in parentheses
*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

Table A 9. Logit. DV: Relative Deprivation - Affective dimension

Variables	(1) Status Loss - Overall	(2) Status Loss - Men	(3) Status Loss - Women	(4) Status Threat - Overall	(5) Status Threat - Men	(6) Status Threat - Women
Vote recall (UNTWIST scheme) (<i>ref. cat. RWPP</i>)						
MR	0.681** (0.114)	0.795 (0.187)	0.562** (0.135)	0.650*** (0.0829)	0.795 (0.187)	0.562** (0.135)
ML	0.394*** (0.0678)	0.503*** (0.117)	0.286*** (0.0736)	0.588*** (0.0714)	0.503*** (0.117)	0.286*** (0.0736)
RL	0.733 (0.202)	0.874 (0.326)	0.635 (0.262)	0.888 (0.172)	0.874 (0.326)	0.635 (0.262)
Other	0.506*** (0.104)	0.561* (0.180)	0.425*** (0.121)	0.716* (0.125)	0.561* (0.180)	0.425*** (0.121)
Gender (<i>ref. cat. Men</i>)						
Women	0.855 (0.113)			0.961 (0.0958)		
Age group (<i>ref. cat. 18-24</i>)						
25-39	0.781 (0.192)	0.834 (0.342)	0.751 (0.243)	0.913 (0.186)	0.834 (0.342)	0.751 (0.243)
40-54	0.859 (0.225)	0.854 (0.366)	0.860 (0.302)	1.063 (0.223)	0.854 (0.366)	0.860 (0.302)
55-64	0.966 (0.261)	0.843 (0.367)	1.041 (0.385)	1.204 (0.266)	0.843 (0.367)	1.041 (0.385)
65+	0.819 (0.291)	0.473 (0.240)	1.425 (0.673)	0.907 (0.247)	0.473 (0.240)	1.425 (0.673)
Education (<i>ref. cat. ISCED 0-2</i>)						
ISCED 3-4	1.263 (0.220)	1.545* (0.404)	1.051 (0.267)	0.959 (0.122)	1.545* (0.404)	1.051 (0.267)
ISCED 5-8	1.401* (0.250)	1.504 (0.411)	1.399 (0.356)	1.002 (0.125)	1.504 (0.411)	1.399 (0.356)
Social scale self- placement (centered)	0.882*** (0.0349)	0.805*** (0.0435)	0.953 (0.0542)	0.876*** (0.0271)	0.805*** (0.0435)	0.953 (0.0542)
Civil status (<i>ref. cat. Married</i>)						
Civil union	0.728 (0.229)	0.931 (0.443)	0.602 (0.245)	0.581* (0.178)	0.931 (0.443)	0.602 (0.245)
Cohabitation	0.922 (0.168)	0.834 (0.220)	1.038 (0.267)	0.951 (0.132)	0.834 (0.220)	1.038 (0.267)
Divorced	0.879 (0.184)	0.955 (0.284)	0.881 (0.255)	0.736* (0.117)	0.955 (0.284)	0.881 (0.255)
Separated	0.583 (0.268)	0.633 (0.365)	0.570 (0.389)	0.715 (0.217)	0.633 (0.365)	0.570 (0.389)
Widowed	1.029 (0.314)	1.556 (0.786)	0.808 (0.295)	0.689 (0.159)	1.556 (0.786)	0.808 (0.295)
Single	0.818 (0.148)	0.674 (0.168)	1.063 (0.275)	0.806 (0.109)	0.674 (0.168)	1.063 (0.275)

Variables	(1) Status Loss - Overall	(2) Status Loss - Men	(3) Status Loss - Women	(4) Status Threat - Overall	(5) Status Threat - Men	(6) Status Threat - Women
Number of children (centered)	0.955 (0.0539)	0.945 (0.0709)	0.992 (0.0755)	0.973 (0.0333)	0.945 (0.0709)	0.992 (0.0755)
Religion (<i>ref. cat. Roman-Catholic</i>)						
Protestant	0.988 (0.170)	1.094 (0.278)	0.898 (0.216)	0.697*** (0.0948)	1.094 (0.278)	0.898 (0.216)
Eastern Orthodox	1.067 (0.566)	1.495 (0.919)	0.272 (0.283)	0.282** (0.147)	1.495 (0.919)	0.272 (0.283)
Other Christian	0.813 (0.326)	1.236 (0.731)	0.466 (0.225)	0.649 (0.231)	1.236 (0.731)	0.466 (0.225)
Jewish	4.620* (3.658)		22.30*** (19.76)	1.735 (1.048)		22.30*** (19.76)
Islam	0.936 (0.490)	0.0979** (0.105)	2.089 (1.379)	1.029 (0.402)	0.0979** (0.105)	2.089 (1.379)
Eastern religions	0.764 (0.659)	0.262 (0.278)	1.566 (1.512)	0.199** (0.127)	0.262 (0.278)	1.566 (1.512)
Other non-Christian	0.0587*** (0.0611)		0.111** (0.123)	0.811 (0.509)		0.111** (0.123)
No denomination	0.924 (0.160)	0.807 (0.193)	1.043 (0.269)	0.771* (0.105)	0.807 (0.193)	1.043 (0.269)
Other	0.723 (0.703)		1.620 (1.587)	0.0455*** (0.0486)		1.620 (1.587)
None	0.815 (0.149)	0.876 (0.228)	0.750 (0.200)	0.779* (0.111)	0.876 (0.228)	0.750 (0.200)
Level of religiosity (centered)	0.955** (0.0222)	0.970 (0.0330)	0.943* (0.0313)	0.954** (0.0174)	0.970 (0.0330)	0.943* (0.0313)
Employment (<i>ref. cat. >30h. pw</i>)						
<30h. pw	1.031 (0.221)	1.030 (0.451)	1.015 (0.256)	1.336* (0.209)	1.030 (0.451)	1.015 (0.256)
Self-empl.	1.298 (0.348)	0.939 (0.328)	2.011* (0.750)	0.846 (0.190)	0.939 (0.328)	2.011* (0.750)
Military serv.	7.940** (6.962)	11.33** (11.66)	2.266 (3.731)		11.33** (11.66)	2.266 (3.731)
Retired	0.770 (0.195)	1.224 (0.384)	0.438** (0.161)	1.179 (0.222)	1.224 (0.384)	0.438** (0.161)
Housemaker	0.677 (0.209)	0.381 (0.397)	0.672 (0.221)	0.676 (0.176)	0.381 (0.397)	0.672 (0.221)
Student	0.625 (0.238)	0.504 (0.309)	0.862 (0.411)	1.221 (0.325)	0.504 (0.309)	0.862 (0.411)
Unemployed	0.678 (0.177)	0.641 (0.261)	0.743 (0.258)	1.074 (0.240)	0.641 (0.261)	0.743 (0.258)
Disable	0.792 (0.321)	0.328 (0.243)	1.267 (0.601)	1.176 (0.317)	0.328 (0.243)	1.267 (0.601)

Variables	(1) Status Loss - Overall	(2) Status Loss - Men	(3) Status Loss - Women	(4) Status Threat - Overall	(5) Status Threat - Men	(6) Status Threat - Women
Other	1.082 (0.406)	2.945** (1.524)	0.367* (0.200)	1.536* (0.373)	2.945** (1.524)	0.367* (0.200)
Income satisfaction (<i>ref. cat. Comfortably</i>)						
Coping	1.621*** (0.234)	1.613** (0.316)	1.593** (0.338)	1.411*** (0.151)	1.613** (0.316)	1.593** (0.338)
Difficult	2.760*** (0.509)	2.346*** (0.634)	3.323*** (0.845)	1.882*** (0.275)	2.346*** (0.634)	3.323*** (0.845)
Very difficult	3.021*** (0.882)	2.504** (1.061)	4.033*** (1.679)	2.085*** (0.482)	2.504** (1.061)	4.033*** (1.679)
Personal income (centered)	1.009 (0.0342)	1.055 (0.0507)	0.975 (0.0467)	1.050** (0.0254)	1.055 (0.0507)	0.975 (0.0467)
Household income (centered)	1.001 (0.0292)	0.980 (0.0419)	1.022 (0.0421)	0.990 (0.0222)	0.980 (0.0419)	1.022 (0.0421)
Country (<i>ref. cat. UK</i>)						
Denmark	0.249*** (0.0802)	0.269*** (0.115)	0.215*** (0.0966)	0.334*** (0.0608)	0.269*** (0.115)	0.215*** (0.0966)
Hungary	2.565*** (0.556)	2.987*** (0.899)	2.453*** (0.816)	1.287 (0.222)	2.987*** (0.899)	2.453*** (0.816)
Spain	2.162*** (0.439)	2.327*** (0.688)	2.110*** (0.594)	1.265 (0.195)	2.327*** (0.688)	2.110*** (0.594)
Germany	1.274 (0.222)	1.189 (0.285)	1.391 (0.349)	0.964 (0.127)	1.189 (0.285)	1.391 (0.349)
Switzerland	0.414*** (0.106)	0.481** (0.170)	0.383** (0.146)	0.606*** (0.108)	0.481** (0.170)	0.383** (0.146)
Male GCI	0.989 (0.0465)	0.996 (0.0485)	0.504 (0.242)	0.999 (0.0384)	0.996 (0.0485)	0.504 (0.242)
Female GCI	0.940 (0.0397)	0.896 (0.247)	0.956 (0.0419)	0.923** (0.0325)	0.896 (0.247)	0.956 (0.0419)
Constant	0.0908*** (0.0365)	0.0726*** (0.0444)	0.0864*** (0.0471)	0.297*** (0.0872)	0.0726*** (0.0444)	0.0864*** (0.0471)
Observations	7,044	3,103	3,899	7,030	3,103	3,899

Standard errors in parentheses
*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

Table A 10. Logit. DV: Unfairly advantaged social groups – Overall (1/2)

Variables	(1) Men	(2) Women	(3) Younger people	(4) Older people	(5) LGBT Q+	(6) Heterosex ual people	(7) Immigra nts	(8) Worki ng class people
Vote recall (UNTWIST scheme) (<i>ref. cat. RWPP</i>)								
MR	1.609** * (0.265)	0.640** * (0.105)	0.889 (0.136)	1.121 (0.154)	0.695* ** (0.0814)	0.952 (0.205)	0.563** * (0.0563)	1.026 (0.143)
ML	2.888** * (0.441)	0.593** * (0.0990)	0.909 (0.134)	1.374* * (0.178)	0.397* ** (0.0512)	1.066 (0.205)	0.246** * (0.0257)	0.869 (0.124)
RL	4.867** * (0.987)	0.328** * (0.0995)	0.862 (0.226)	1.311 (0.284)	0.303* ** (0.0731)	1.656* (0.442)	0.125** * (0.0244)	0.411* ** (0.111)
Other	1.861** * (0.420)	0.662 (0.177)	0.927 (0.219)	0.887 (0.193)	0.619* * (0.127)	1.021 (0.317)	0.451** * (0.0740)	1.111 (0.249)
Gender (<i>ref. cat. Men</i>)								
Women	3.363** * (0.378)	1.385** (0.194)	1.487** * (0.185)	1.094 (0.118)	0.781* * (0.0849)	0.600*** (0.112)	1.097 (0.0937)	1.859* ** (0.224)
Age group (<i>ref. cat. 18-24</i>)								
25-39	1.169 (0.218)	1.030 (0.262)	0.628* (0.161)	1.000 (0.195)	0.885 (0.193)	0.870 (0.255)	0.866 (0.147)	0.797 (0.157)
40-54	1.013 (0.202)	0.738 (0.201)	0.620* (0.166)	0.586* (0.125)	0.754 (0.173)	0.738 (0.241)	0.995 (0.173)	0.629* (0.134)
55-64	0.762 (0.165)	0.555** (0.167)	0.611* (0.175)	0.553* (0.128)	0.831 (0.201)	0.786 (0.289)	1.054 (0.195)	0.708 (0.160)
65+	1.065 (0.279)	0.532 (0.208)	0.782 (0.242)	0.469* (0.138)	0.786 (0.227)	0.770 (0.336)	0.893 (0.195)	0.762 (0.210)
Education (<i>ref. cat. ISCED 0-2</i>)								
ISCED 3-4	1.215 (0.207)	0.900 (0.166)	0.706** (0.114)	0.667* ** (0.099 5)	0.988 (0.137)	1.191 (0.280)	1.001 (0.114)	0.818 (0.121)
ISCED 5-8	1.765** * (0.293)	0.782 (0.145)	0.714** (0.111)	0.608* ** (0.088 5)	1.069 (0.145)	1.416 (0.343)	0.826* (0.0938)	0.633* ** (0.090 0)

Variables	(1) Men	(2) Women	(3) Younger people	(4) Older people	(5) LGBT Q+	(6) Heterosexual people	(7) Immigrants	(8) Working class people
Social scale self-placement (centered)	1.009 (0.0344)	1.073 (0.0470)	1.000 (0.0380)	0.986 (0.0345)	0.925* (0.0293)	1.033 (0.0580)	0.941** (0.0259)	0.957 (0.0364)
<i>Civil status (ref. cat. Married)</i>								
Civil union	1.747** (0.483)	1.240 (0.426)	1.235 (0.386)	1.254 (0.354)	0.876 (0.263)	2.001* (0.795)	0.802 (0.195)	0.589 (0.214)
Cohabitation	1.227 (0.165)	0.587** (0.140)	0.951 (0.172)	1.106 (0.160)	0.942 (0.149)	1.510* (0.340)	1.003 (0.125)	0.936 (0.169)
Divorced	1.518** (0.233)	1.352 (0.278)	1.001 (0.173)	1.041 (0.178)	0.869 (0.161)	0.713 (0.196)	0.948 (0.126)	0.914 (0.169)
Separated	1.180 (0.328)	1.539 (0.542)	0.498* (0.203)	1.417 (0.468)	1.113 (0.370)	1.230 (0.533)	0.605* (0.169)	2.054* (0.633)
Widowed	1.346 (0.271)	1.096 (0.323)	1.063 (0.228)	0.866 (0.216)	0.772 (0.177)	0.547 (0.242)	0.989 (0.183)	0.674 (0.190)
Single	1.034 (0.140)	1.104 (0.215)	0.927 (0.162)	1.088 (0.152)	1.000 (0.147)	1.666** (0.366)	0.916 (0.109)	0.904 (0.143)
Number of children (centered)	0.865** (0.0366)	0.909* (0.0479)	1.019 (0.0309)	0.983 (0.0317)	1.080* (0.0420)	1.088 (0.0848)	1.018 (0.0277)	1.027 (0.0326)
<i>Religion (ref. cat. Roman-Catholic)</i>								
Protestant	1.074 (0.147)	0.618** (0.124)	1.591** (0.246)	0.965 (0.134)	0.971 (0.131)	1.005 (0.212)	1.037 (0.117)	0.863 (0.143)
Eastern Orthodox	0.649 (0.339)	1.225 (0.565)	2.027 (0.947)	1.105 (0.533)	0.792 (0.345)	1.509 (1.056)	1.996** (0.677)	1.382 (0.611)
Other Christian	1.249 (0.374)	1.329 (0.473)	0.996 (0.381)	1.311 (0.364)	0.862 (0.217)	0.421* (0.197)	1.517* (0.343)	0.444* (0.148)
Jewish	1.053 (0.631)	3.914** (2.377)	1.329 (0.836)	0.558 (0.395)	1.762 (0.942)	1.332 (1.084)	0.641 (0.334)	0.317 (0.277)
Islam	0.956 (0.345)	0.966 (0.365)	0.656 (0.320)	1.255 (0.445)	1.146 (0.361)	1.149 (0.483)	0.576 (0.203)	0.706 (0.280)
Eastern religions	1.800 (0.771)	1.685 (0.797)	1.315 (0.616)	0.285* (0.217)	0.936 (0.407)	0.452 (0.469)	0.959 (0.403)	0.572 (0.275)

Variables	(1) Men	(2) Women	(3) Younger people	(4) Older people	(5) LGBT Q+	(6) Heterosexual people	(7) Immigrants	(8) Working class people
Other non-Christian	0.244** (0.152)	1.043 (0.629)	0.271* (0.204)	0.823 (0.492)	1.198 (0.792)	4.250** (3.019)	1.002 (0.542)	2.543* (1.185)
No denomination	1.386** (0.209)	0.684* (0.139)	1.143 (0.212)	0.767 (0.124)	0.911 (0.142)	1.343 (0.328)	0.994 (0.127)	0.694* (0.127)
Other	0.605 (0.525)	0.605 (0.659)			0.754 (0.611)		1.405 (0.843)	
None	1.077 (0.172)	0.853 (0.187)	1.271 (0.228)	1.095 (0.161)	0.896 (0.139)	1.137 (0.265)	1.076 (0.135)	0.795 (0.145)
Level of religiosity (centered)	0.993 (0.0187)	1.014 (0.0240)	1.015 (0.0222)	0.972 (0.0175)	1.051* (0.0182)	1.035 (0.0276)	0.991 (0.0145)	1.022 (0.0216)
Employment (<i>ref. cat. >30h. pw</i>)								
<30h. pw	1.113 (0.160)	0.887 (0.203)	1.541** (0.309)	0.833 (0.142)	1.029 (0.172)	0.935 (0.244)	1.062 (0.142)	0.951 (0.168)
Self-empl.	0.765 (0.161)	0.841 (0.291)	1.126 (0.282)	0.626* (0.155)	1.515* (0.307)	1.174 (0.353)	1.522** (0.254)	0.928 (0.225)
Military serv.	0.602 (0.885)	0.587 (0.414)	3.088 (2.784)	0.593 (0.669)	1.072 (0.927)	3.569 (3.386)	1.640 (0.986)	0.104* (0.115)
Retired	1.013 (0.193)	1.440 (0.402)	1.417* (0.271)	1.083 (0.242)	0.910 (0.179)	0.902 (0.267)	1.100 (0.168)	0.708 (0.151)
Housemaker	1.017 (0.252)	1.530 (0.441)	1.077 (0.302)	0.856 (0.234)	1.126 (0.264)	1.126 (0.460)	0.935 (0.200)	1.099 (0.268)
Student	1.582* (0.376)	0.573 (0.208)	0.952 (0.377)	1.210 (0.310)	1.103 (0.314)	1.079 (0.402)	1.046 (0.244)	0.749 (0.247)
Unemployed	1.349 (0.370)	0.503** (0.156)	0.991 (0.281)	1.325 (0.321)	0.589* (0.162)	1.008 (0.381)	0.653* (0.149)	0.748 (0.206)
Disable	1.190 (0.421)	0.926 (0.453)	1.237 (0.474)	0.702 (0.249)	0.875 (0.299)	1.100 (0.486)	0.907 (0.240)	0.493* (0.192)
Other	1.124 (0.278)	0.975 (0.348)	0.658 (0.240)	0.816 (0.236)	0.998 (0.270)	0.907 (0.444)	1.154 (0.244)	0.724 (0.247)
Income satisfaction (<i>ref. cat. Comfortably</i>)								
Coping	1.056 (0.104)	1.044 (0.150)	1.196 (0.143)	0.863 (0.0945)	1.057 (0.108)	1.050 (0.171)	1.275** (0.111)	0.958 (0.124)
Difficult	1.100	1.137	1.025	1.140	0.947	1.102	1.397**	1.189

Variables	(1) Men	(2) Women	(3) Younger people	(4) Older people	(5) LGBT Q+	(6) Heterosexual people	(7) Immigrants	(8) Working class people
Very difficult	(0.174) 0.793	(0.252) 1.270	(0.184) 1.096	(0.176) 1.026	(0.154) 0.756	(0.283) 1.386	(0.186) 1.536*	(0.207) 1.873*
Personal income (centered)	(0.213) 0.968	(0.450) 1.027	(0.304) 1.082** *	(0.260) 1.038	(0.216) 0.999	(0.571) 1.033	(0.352) 1.001	(0.500) 1.042
Household income (centered)	(0.0208) 1.042**	(0.0320) 0.952	(0.0296) 0.926** *	(0.0270) 0.972	(0.0237) 1.032	(0.0389) 0.969	(0.0200) 1.017	(0.0297) 0.944*
Country (<i>ref. cat. UK</i>)	(0.0210) 0.881	(0.0294) 1.395	(0.0246) 0.673**	(0.0217) 0.666* *	(0.0242) 0.668* *	(0.0353) 0.676	(0.0200) 1.091	(0.0248) 0.492**
Denmark	(0.150) 0.851	(0.315) 0.621*	(0.118) 1.104	(0.113) 1.020	(0.107) 0.496**	(0.173) 0.923	(0.148) 0.349** *	(0.105) 0.741
Hungary	(0.172) 0.713*	(0.164) 2.245** *	(0.236) 0.804	(0.195) 0.684* *	(0.0944) 1.321*	(0.260) 1.083	(0.0578) 1.482** *	(0.163) 0.844
Spain	(0.123) 1.424** *	(0.495) 1.107	(0.152) 0.620** *	(0.119) 0.940	(0.202) 0.530**	(0.254) 0.612**	(0.204) 1.157	(0.163) 0.754*
Germany	(0.173) 1.296	(0.208) 0.926	(0.100) 0.760	(0.126) 1.058	(0.0731) 0.671* **	(0.127) 0.855	(0.130) 0.779*	(0.118) 0.568**
Switzerland	(0.208) 1.172** *	(0.209) 1.138** *	(0.152) 1.051	(0.169) 0.986	(0.0996) 1.098* **	(0.203) 1.077	(0.111) 0.942*	(0.115) 1.037
Male GCI	(0.0603) 1.340** *	(0.0524) 1.039	(0.0491) 1.013	(0.0411) 0.997	(0.0379) 0.922* *	(0.0606) 1.194***	(0.0309) 0.893** *	(0.0527) 0.882**
Female GCI	(0.0331) 0.880** *	(0.0427) 1.166** *	(0.0363) 1.193** *	(0.0313) 1.070* *	(0.0330) 1.073* *	(0.0535) 1.059	(0.0252) 1.248** *	(0.0333) 1.250**
Own deservingness	(0.0304) 0.880** *	(0.0544) 1.166** *	(0.0531) 1.193** *	(0.038) 1.070* *	(0.0376) 1.073* *	(0.0588) 1.059	(0.0364) 1.248** *	(0.052) 1.250**

Variables	(1) Men	(2) Women	(3) Younger people	(4) Older people	(5) LGBT Q+	(6) Heterosexual people	(7) Immigrants	(8) Working class people
Constant	0.0220* ** (0.00755)	0.0824* ** (0.0349)	0.0926* ** (0.0366)	0.266* ** (0.0867)	0.395* ** (0.132)	0.0365*** (0.0179)	0.436** * (0.115)	0.164* ** (0.0565)
Observations	7,038	7,038	7,023	7,023	7,038	7,023	7,038	7,023

Standard errors in parentheses
*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

Table A 11. Logit. DV: Unfairly advantaged social groups – Overall (2/2)

Variables	(9) Middle class people	(10) Upper class people	(11) Religious minorities	(12) Religious majorities	(13) Non- disabled people	(14) Disabled people	(15) Ethnic minorities
Vote recall (UNTWIST scheme) (<i>ref. cat. RWPP</i>)							
MR	0.948 (0.189)	1.145 (0.115)	0.788* (0.0990)	1.110 (0.254)	1.268 (0.285)	0.917 (0.122)	0.788* (0.102)
ML	1.034 (0.192)	2.574*** (0.245)	0.389*** (0.0521)	1.505** (0.282)	2.034*** (0.397)	0.792* (0.106)	0.496*** (0.0665)
RL	1.951** (0.636)	4.440*** (0.664)	0.236*** (0.0596)	2.364*** (0.617)	2.859*** (0.777)	0.542** (0.130)	0.341*** (0.0857)
Other	1.359 (0.368)	1.875*** (0.269)	0.708* (0.146)	1.367 (0.306)	1.531 (0.448)	0.773 (0.178)	0.283*** (0.0678)
Gender (<i>ref. cat. Men</i>)							
Women	0.703** (0.108)	0.675*** (0.0526)	0.642*** (0.0728)	0.487*** (0.0781)	1.045 (0.154)	2.107** (0.242)	1.112 (0.128)
Age group (<i>ref. cat. 18-24</i>)							
25-39	1.360 (0.428)	1.183 (0.185)	1.363 (0.310)	0.769 (0.202)	0.781 (0.199)	0.649** (0.130)	1.022 (0.221)
40-54	1.140 (0.369)	1.364* (0.221)	1.509* (0.347)	0.676 (0.188)	0.615* (0.164)	0.565** (0.118)	0.968 (0.213)
55-64	1.125 (0.408)	1.462** (0.252)	1.587* (0.389)	0.697 (0.205)	0.570* (0.164)	0.574** (0.130)	0.872 (0.210)
65+	1.215 (0.491)	1.558** (0.314)	1.935** (0.573)	0.945 (0.309)	0.569* (0.191)	0.654 (0.181)	0.810 (0.229)
Education (<i>ref. cat. ISCED 0-2</i>)							
ISCED 3-4	0.787 (0.154)	1.332*** (0.145)	1.048 (0.143)	0.965 (0.195)	0.769 (0.161)	1.087 (0.155)	1.040 (0.156)
ISCED 5-8	0.556*** (0.110)	1.604*** (0.171)	1.075 (0.150)	1.033 (0.205)	0.913 (0.180)	0.703** (0.0973)	0.899 (0.136)
Social scale self- placement (centered)	0.939 (0.0444)	0.922*** (0.0222)	0.942* (0.0338)	0.948 (0.0452)	0.951 (0.0472)	0.987 (0.0350)	0.986 (0.0333)
Civil status (<i>ref. cat. Married</i>)							
Civil union	1.474 (0.517)	0.858 (0.175)	0.964 (0.263)	0.789 (0.255)	1.956* (0.761)	0.756 (0.229)	0.945 (0.286)
Cohabitation	0.968 (0.228)	0.956 (0.106)	0.901 (0.140)	1.297 (0.256)	1.601** (0.318)	1.107 (0.190)	0.845 (0.149)
Divorced	0.858 (0.212)	1.280** (0.156)	0.987 (0.174)	0.960 (0.215)	1.625** (0.341)	0.703* (0.135)	1.107 (0.204)
Separated	0.788 (0.382)	0.875 (0.185)	0.927 (0.300)	0.330** (0.159)	1.218 (0.439)	1.854** (0.515)	0.453* (0.189)
Widowed	0.939	1.500**	1.065	0.430**	1.914**	0.862	0.747

Variables	(9) Middle class people	(10) Upper class people	(11) Religious minorities	(12) Religious majorities	(13) Non- disabled people	(14) Disabled people	(15) Ethnic minorities
Single	(0.318) 1.115 (0.236)	(0.247) 1.058 (0.112)	(0.257) 1.036 (0.158)	(0.163) 1.108 (0.208)	(0.542) 1.394* (0.270)	(0.205) 1.025 (0.162)	(0.196) 0.839 (0.126)
Number of children (centered)	1.064 (0.0448)	0.935** (0.0246)	1.011 (0.0364)	1.066* (0.0403)	0.949 (0.0436)	1.072** (0.0326)	0.907** (0.0402)
Religion (<i>ref. cat. Roman-Catholic</i>)							
Protestant	0.631** (0.129)	1.088 (0.110)	1.241 (0.181)	1.155 (0.304)	1.162 (0.248)	0.710** (0.111)	1.218 (0.206)
Eastern Orthodox	0.179** (0.120)	0.617 (0.240)	0.828 (0.424)	2.222 (1.237)	1.149 (0.685)	0.806 (0.386)	0.792 (0.397)
Other Christian	1.205 (0.452)	0.894 (0.196)	1.936** (0.510)	2.093 (1.042)	0.836 (0.365)	0.941 (0.271)	0.720 (0.243)
Jewish	3.747 (3.341)	0.785 (0.412)	0.583 (0.465)	1.786 (1.959)	1.405 (0.911)	0.352 (0.300)	0.892 (0.973)
Islam	2.126* (0.836)	1.303 (0.363)	1.888* (0.647)	3.786*** (1.823)	1.036 (0.538)	0.813 (0.289)	1.254 (0.515)
Eastern religions	2.482* (1.234)	1.023 (0.315)	1.981 (0.888)	1.604 (1.111)	1.424 (0.737)	0.582 (0.318)	0.999 (0.521)
Other non- Christian	1.040 (1.091)	1.404 (0.500)	2.452** (1.098)	13.43*** (6.593)	0.354 (0.290)	1.812 (0.900)	0.518 (0.264)
No denominatio n	0.644* (0.149)	1.189 (0.128)	1.147 (0.178)	3.510*** (0.688)	1.226 (0.274)	0.623** (0.112)	1.321* (0.217)
Other		1.034 (0.531)	0.569 (0.561)	2.990 (2.108)		0.517 (0.559)	4.103** (2.302)
None	1.288 (0.258)	1.163 (0.129)	0.904 (0.151)	1.787** (0.447)	1.548* (0.367)	0.712** (0.121)	1.085 (0.191)
Level of religiosity (centered)	1.058** (0.0273)	0.972** (0.0126)	0.996 (0.0174)	1.024 (0.0280)	1.076*** (0.0300)	1.016 (0.0197)	0.993 (0.0190)
Employment (<i>ref. cat. >30h. pw</i>)							
<30h. pw	0.900 (0.231)	0.798* (0.0946)	1.215 (0.217)	0.815 (0.196)	2.172*** (0.474)	0.660** (0.126)	0.680* (0.142)
Self-empl.	0.535* (0.202)	0.667*** (0.102)	1.042 (0.263)	0.955 (0.266)	0.952 (0.352)	1.001 (0.255)	1.217 (0.286)
Military serv.	0.0407** (0.0587)	0.0299** (0.0371)		10.76*** (8.405)	1.678 (2.258)	2.827 (2.885)	3.596 (2.859)

Variables	(9) Middle class people	(10) Upper class people	(11) Religious minorities	(12) Religious majorities	(13) Non- disabled people	(14) Disable d people	(15) Ethnic minorities
Retired	0.838 (0.223)	0.903 (0.122)	0.940 (0.198)	1.359 (0.318)	2.162*** (0.543)	1.073 (0.226)	1.118 (0.236)
Housemaker	1.372 (0.415)	0.756 (0.148)	1.176 (0.314)	0.946 (0.390)	3.258*** (1.005)	0.888 (0.232)	1.239 (0.336)
Student	0.872 (0.409)	0.963 (0.197)	1.019 (0.333)	0.509* (0.190)	1.276 (0.497)	0.527** (0.163)	1.170 (0.352)
Unemployed	0.559* (0.196)	1.116 (0.232)	0.751 (0.233)	0.938 (0.333)	1.384 (0.585)	0.921 (0.222)	0.723 (0.208)
Disable	0.386* (0.204)	0.974 (0.251)	0.906 (0.324)	1.156 (0.514)	5.130*** (1.605)	1.584 (0.447)	0.798 (0.272)
Other	0.349* (0.196)	1.501** (0.292)	1.303 (0.325)	0.711 (0.334)	1.689 (0.543)	0.762 (0.237)	1.065 (0.315)
Income satisfaction (<i>ref. cat. Comfortably</i>)							
Coping	1.072 (0.166)	1.192** (0.0902)	1.125 (0.126)	0.943 (0.135)	1.135 (0.173)	0.835 (0.102)	1.221* (0.146)
Difficult	1.370 (0.285)	1.028 (0.120)	1.147 (0.204)	0.911 (0.197)	1.633** (0.344)	1.017 (0.172)	1.087 (0.196)
Very difficult	1.957** (0.605)	0.733 (0.143)	0.969 (0.309)	0.947 (0.325)	2.062** (0.665)	1.234 (0.316)	1.125 (0.326)
Personal income (centered)	1.016 (0.0390)	0.935*** (0.0165)	0.997 (0.0254)	0.995 (0.0329)	1.103*** (0.0386)	0.992 (0.0270)	1.013 (0.0267)
Household income (centered)	0.949 (0.0323)	1.060*** (0.0181)	1.016 (0.0249)	0.996 (0.0311)	1.021 (0.0329)	0.937** (0.0249)	0.991 (0.0257)
Country (<i>ref. cat. UK</i>)							
Denmark	0.476*** (0.123)	1.056 (0.123)	1.576*** (0.254)	0.376*** (0.135)	0.915 (0.197)	0.754 (0.134)	0.139*** (0.0325)
Hungary	0.632* (0.149)	1.321** (0.184)	0.567*** (0.119)	3.774*** (1.020)	0.782 (0.227)	0.484** (0.0960)	0.877 (0.169)
Spain	0.505*** (0.119)	0.629*** (0.0773)	1.740*** (0.306)	3.256*** (0.888)	0.710 (0.171)	0.665** (0.118)	0.854 (0.150)
Germany	0.360*** (0.0763)	1.120 (0.110)	0.949 (0.146)	1.563* (0.362)	0.806 (0.154)	0.376** (0.0619)	0.282*** (0.0471)
Switzerland	0.940 (0.209)	0.931 (0.114)	0.667** (0.119)	0.574* (0.184)	0.962 (0.245)	0.494** (0.0935)	0.208*** (0.0423)
Male GCI	0.970 (0.0535)	0.949* (0.0285)	1.058 (0.0396)	0.932 (0.0514)	1.037 (0.0728)	1.006 (0.0508)	0.991 (0.0409)
Female GCI	1.056 (0.209)	1.084*** (0.114)	1.012 (0.119)	1.074* (0.184)	1.026 (0.245)	0.894** (0.0935)	0.862*** (0.0423)

Variables	(9) Middle class people	(10) Upper class people	(11) Religious minorities	(12) Religious majorities	(13) Non- disabled people	(14) Disabled people	(15) Ethnic minorities
Own deservingness	(0.0446) 1.111**	(0.0243) 0.886***	(0.0356) 1.311***	(0.0463) 0.964	(0.0464) 0.915*	(0.0309) 1.055	(0.0332) 1.030
Constant	(0.0581) 0.0984** *	(0.0227) 0.410***	(0.0471) 0.0611** *	(0.0454) 0.0317** *	(0.0467) 0.0346** *	(0.0430) 0.356** *	(0.0403) 0.335***
	(0.0440)	(0.101)	(0.0205)	(0.0147)	(0.0147)	(0.121)	(0.117)
Observations	7,023	7,038	7,024	7,038	7,023	7,038	7,038

Standard errors in parentheses
*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

Table A 12. Logit. DV: Unfairly advantaged social groups – Men (1/2)

Variables	(1) Men	(2) Women	(3) Younger people	(4) Older people	(5) LGBT Q+	(6) Heterosex- ual people	(7) Immigra- nts	(8) Worki- ng class people
Vote recall (UNTWIST scheme) (<i>ref. cat. RWPP</i>)								
MR	0.796	0.583**	0.960	1.442*	0.753*	1.070	0.474** *	1.376
	(0.220)	(0.132)	(0.222)	(0.312)	(0.120)	(0.297)	(0.0665)	(0.304)
ML	1.496*	0.437** *	1.119	1.870* **	0.377* **	1.050	0.198** *	1.207
	(0.353)	(0.117)	(0.254)	(0.388)	(0.0683)	(0.260)	(0.0302)	(0.286)
RL	3.231** *	0.139** *	1.389	2.582* **	0.284* **	1.793	0.0795* **	0.224* **
	(1.013)	(0.0609)	(0.513)	(0.815)	(0.0995)	(0.656)	(0.0250)	(0.115)
Other	1.067	0.399**	0.961	1.220	0.578*	1.366	0.394** *	1.092
	(0.431)	(0.152)	(0.367)	(0.414)	(0.163)	(0.593)	(0.0903)	(0.415)
Age group (<i>ref. cat. 18-24</i>)								
25-39	1.127	1.662	0.764	0.927	1.068	0.770	0.749	0.901
	(0.393)	(0.660)	(0.321)	(0.256)	(0.324)	(0.315)	(0.200)	(0.302)
40-54	0.999	1.169	0.616	0.524* *	0.956	1.199	0.841	0.750
	(0.377)	(0.494)	(0.282)	(0.165)	(0.313)	(0.531)	(0.231)	(0.273)
55-64	0.965	1.079	0.680	0.461* *	1.130	1.426	0.979	0.764
	(0.393)	(0.485)	(0.316)	(0.159)	(0.383)	(0.708)	(0.281)	(0.292)
65+	1.154	0.840	0.925	0.504* *	0.928	1.351	0.848	0.594
	(0.550)	(0.495)	(0.457)	(0.205)	(0.368)	(0.813)	(0.284)	(0.270)
Education (<i>ref. cat. ISCED 0-2</i>)								
ISCED 3-4	1.157	2.051**	0.573**	0.741	0.915	1.537	1.074	0.699
	(0.351)	(0.651)	(0.150)	(0.170)	(0.176)	(0.538)	(0.177)	(0.166)
ISCED 5-8	1.539	2.512** *	0.532**	0.715	1.009	1.904*	0.821	0.510* **
	(0.455)	(0.791)	(0.133)	(0.156)	(0.187)	(0.677)	(0.133)	(0.117)
Social scale self- placement (centered)	1.029	1.009	0.974	0.981	0.893* *	0.992	0.958	1.094
	(0.0644)	(0.0611)	(0.0620)	(0.049 7)	(0.0393)	(0.0736)	(0.0402)	(0.069 9)
Civil status (<i>ref. cat. Married</i>)								
Civil union	1.059	1.302	0.910	1.382	1.083	3.343**	0.805	0.519
	(0.530)	(0.681)	(0.571)	(0.622)	(0.476)	(1.837)	(0.329)	(0.386)

Variables	(1) Men	(2) Women	(3) Younger people	(4) Older people	(5) LGBT Q+	(6) Heterosex ual people	(7) Immigra nts	(8) Worki ng class people
Cohabitation	1.497*	0.551*	0.856	1.484*	0.983	1.676	0.804	1.022
	(0.343)	(0.195)	(0.262)	(0.311)	(0.230)	(0.568)	(0.150)	(0.326)
Divorced	1.051	3.059** *	1.140	1.034	0.777	0.293**	1.016	1.012
	(0.335)	(0.848)	(0.319)	(0.292)	(0.221)	(0.149)	(0.216)	(0.312)
Separated	2.037	1.074	0.434	0.990	2.186*	1.311	0.727	2.621* *
	(0.882)	(0.839)	(0.284)	(0.564)	(0.919)	(0.774)	(0.314)	(1.282)
Widowed	0.892	1.824	1.568	0.760	0.950	0.360	1.446	1.085
	(0.461)	(0.935)	(0.545)	(0.319)	(0.358)	(0.272)	(0.452)	(0.578)
Single	0.865	1.420	1.133	1.227	0.969	1.625	0.778	1.239
	(0.232)	(0.364)	(0.316)	(0.261)	(0.206)	(0.515)	(0.141)	(0.316)
Number of children (centered)	0.784** *	0.909	1.017	1.007	1.066	0.878	1.028	1.105*
	(0.0633)	(0.0728)	(0.0605)	(0.056 6)	(0.0634)	(0.0958)	(0.0483)	(0.065 4)
Religion (<i>ref. cat. Roman-Catholic</i>)								
Protestant	1.441	0.606*	2.085** *	0.873	1.000	0.707	1.060	0.985
	(0.403)	(0.176)	(0.541)	(0.197)	(0.184)	(0.218)	(0.175)	(0.280)
Eastern Orthodox	1.466	0.957	1.338	1.435	0.637	2.345	2.669**	2.656*
	(1.056)	(0.707)	(0.820)	(0.909)	(0.411)	(2.076)	(1.217)	(1.439)
Other Christian	1.221	0.620	0.243*	1.176	0.924	0.203	1.120	0.190* *
	(0.672)	(0.345)	(0.189)	(0.592)	(0.337)	(0.214)	(0.360)	(0.153)
Jewish	4.180**	2.296	2.251	0.242	0.821	2.544	0.531	0.403
	(2.783)	(1.717)	(1.792)	(0.312)	(0.624)	(2.153)	(0.423)	(0.480)
Islam	0.820	0.120**	1.208	2.289	1.023	0.706	0.309*	1.060
	(0.497)	(0.127)	(0.825)	(1.159)	(0.436)	(0.431)	(0.192)	(0.676)
Eastern religions	2.800	1.336	0.712	0.213	1.096	0.462	2.287*	0.925
	(1.860)	(0.893)	(0.770)	(0.223)	(0.636)	(0.532)	(1.013)	(0.538)
No denominati on	1.696*	0.674	1.290	0.786	0.838	1.113	0.767	0.794
	(0.457)	(0.194)	(0.394)	(0.186)	(0.179)	(0.366)	(0.146)	(0.245)
Other	5.023	1.343						
	(5.402)	(1.284)						
None	1.688*	0.800	1.280	1.342	0.748	0.948	0.945	0.912
	(0.502)	(0.238)	(0.373)	(0.300)	(0.155)	(0.317)	(0.169)	(0.281)
Level of religiosity	1.072**	1.014	0.996	0.936* *	1.060* *	1.078*	0.993	1.027

Variables	(1) Men	(2) Women	(3) Younger people	(4) Older people	(5) LGBT Q+	(6) Heterosexual people	(7) Immigrants	(8) Working class people
(centered)	(0.0368)	(0.0345)	(0.0340)	(0.0288)	(0.0253)	(0.0413)	(0.0213)	(0.0370)
Employment (<i>ref. cat. >30h. pw</i>)								
<30h. pw	1.143 (0.435)	0.414** (0.186)	2.141** (0.767)	0.874 (0.281)	1.098 (0.325)	2.020* (0.753)	1.187 (0.306)	1.222 (0.423)
Self-empl.	0.331** (0.155)	1.155 (0.469)	1.552 (0.540)	0.759 (0.254)	1.207 (0.311)	1.002 (0.393)	1.342 (0.314)	0.850 (0.279)
Military serv.	5.048 (6.443)		8.578* (9.531)	1.523 (1.780)	1.876 (1.935)		2.068 (1.771)	
Retired	0.895 (0.305)	0.983 (0.381)	1.654* (0.446)	0.835 (0.239)	0.961 (0.252)	0.722 (0.304)	1.089 (0.241)	0.767 (0.248)
Housemaker	2.662 (2.040)	2.153 (2.025)	0.190 (0.226)	1.771 (1.298)	0.124* (0.132)	0.264 (0.256)	1.184 (0.841)	0.353 (0.468)
Student	0.816 (0.382)	0.765 (0.397)	1.494 (0.926)	1.720 (0.626)	1.662 (0.607)	0.362* (0.199)	0.896 (0.335)	0.495 (0.287)
Unemployed	1.452 (0.619)	0.255** (0.172)	1.012 (0.500)	1.759 (0.638)	0.395* (0.180)	1.205 (0.588)	0.614 (0.224)	0.936 (0.419)
Other	0.850 (0.564)	1.692 (0.744)	0.332 (0.264)	0.695 (0.381)	1.461 (0.536)	0.682 (0.522)	1.892** (0.585)	0.832 (0.529)
Income satisfaction (<i>ref. cat. Comfortably</i>)								
Coping	0.957 (0.190)	1.053 (0.208)	1.243 (0.239)	0.670* (0.110)	1.134 (0.155)	0.810 (0.183)	1.615** (0.204)	1.063 (0.225)
Difficult	1.452 (0.423)	1.267 (0.420)	1.108 (0.332)	0.827 (0.202)	1.018 (0.238)	0.862 (0.261)	2.103** (0.409)	1.618 (0.480)
Very difficult	0.765 (0.412)	0.820 (0.569)	1.076 (0.578)	0.844 (0.336)	0.533 (0.231)	1.466 (0.766)	1.937* (0.712)	3.279* (1.532)
Personal income (centered)	1.023 (0.0460)	0.975 (0.0437)	1.140** (0.0550)	1.040 (0.0431)	0.999 (0.0358)	1.034 (0.0554)	0.999 (0.0329)	1.067 (0.0513)
Household income (centered)	0.974 (0.0393)	1.043 (0.0478)	0.941 (0.0385)	0.951 (0.0322)	1.020 (0.0360)	0.941 (0.0442)	1.036 (0.0333)	0.934 (0.0391)
Country (<i>ref. cat. UK</i>)								
Denmark	0.858	1.650	0.603*	0.401*	0.623*	0.763	1.178	0.484*

Variables	(1) Men	(2) Women	(3) Younger people	(4) Older people	(5) LGBT Q+	(6) Heterosexual people	(7) Immigrants	(8) Working class people
				**	*			*
Hungary	(0.278) 1.438	(0.542) 0.288** *	(0.168) 1.550	(0.107) 0.711	(0.139) 0.474* **	(0.272) 0.792	(0.229) 0.224** *	(0.165) 0.950
Spain	(0.440) 1.162	(0.123) 2.948** *	(0.487) 0.673	(0.210) 0.547* *	(0.131) 1.336	(0.310) 0.891	(0.0556) 1.535**	(0.353) 0.958
Germany	(0.337) 1.037	(0.879) 0.648	(0.223) 0.808	(0.142) 0.747	(0.284) 0.530* **	(0.290) 0.523**	(0.310) 1.192	(0.313) 0.664
Switzerland	(0.244) 1.213	(0.177) 0.877	(0.201) 1.158	(0.144) 1.130	(0.102) 0.571* **	(0.156) 0.717	(0.193) 0.558** *	(0.166) 0.440* *
Male GCI	(0.372) 1.147** *	(0.294) 1.161** *	(0.340) 1.064	(0.262) 0.984	(0.122) 1.109* **	(0.248) 1.121*	(0.113) 0.940*	(0.141) 1.040
Female GCI	(0.0573) 1.739** *	(0.0560) 1.170	(0.0521) 1.763**	(0.0440) 0.843	(0.0411) 1.005	(0.0663) 2.533***	(0.0337) 0.654	(0.0533) 0.334* *
Own deservingness	(0.353) 0.983	(0.389) 1.078	(0.461) 1.259** *	(0.199) 1.098*	(0.241) 1.124* *	(0.597) 1.152*	(0.231) 1.286** *	(0.166) 1.234* **
Other non-Christian	(0.0571)	(0.0718)	(0.0906)	(0.0599)	(0.0552)	(0.0900)	(0.0538)	(0.0851)
Constant	0.0267* **	(0.409) 0.0354* **	(0.405) 0.0477* **	(0.996) 0.214* **	(0.911) 0.300* **	(5.845) 0.0223***	(0.476) 0.496*	(1.100) 0.111* **
	(0.0153)	(0.0226)	(0.0292)	(0.104)	(0.140)	(0.0163)	(0.198)	(0.0646)
Observations	3,080	3,139	3,138	3,138	3,138	3,133	3,138	3,133

Standard errors in parentheses
*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

Table A 13. Logit. DV: Unfairly advantaged social groups – Men (2/2)

Variables	(9) Middle class people	(10) Upper class people	(11) Religious minorities	(12) Religious majorities	(13) Non- disabled people	(14) Disabled people	(15) Ethnic minorities
Vote recall (UNTWIST scheme) (<i>ref. cat. RWPP</i>)							
MR	0.772 (0.222)	1.206 (0.167)	0.699** (0.113)	1.003 (0.307)	1.566 (0.535)	1.150 (0.247)	0.645** (0.119)
ML	0.919 (0.236)	3.101** (0.422) *	0.318*** (0.0583)	1.715** (0.442)	2.838*** (0.844)	0.978 (0.223)	0.459*** (0.0894)
RL	2.702** (1.071)	5.207** (1.150) *	0.212*** (0.0707)	2.234** (0.776)	6.662*** (2.690)	0.598 (0.250)	0.380*** (0.128)
Other	1.401 (0.538)	2.171** (0.452) *	0.621* (0.171)	1.169 (0.358)	3.208*** (1.344)	0.732 (0.265)	0.278*** (0.0836)
Age group (<i>ref. cat. 18-24</i>)							
25-39	0.963 (0.447)	1.295 (0.302)	1.690 (0.556)	0.833 (0.350)	1.189 (0.526)	0.594 (0.190)	1.195 (0.353)
40-54	1.070 (0.514)	1.373 (0.334)	1.690 (0.572)	0.565 (0.247)	0.974 (0.459)	0.512* (0.183)	0.838 (0.263)
55-64	1.003 (0.538)	1.707** (0.437)	1.601 (0.565)	0.832 (0.374)	0.986 (0.492)	0.430** (0.172)	0.644 (0.220)
65+	1.225 (0.760)	1.689* (0.499)	1.762 (0.744)	1.066 (0.536)	1.137 (0.632)	0.465 (0.218)	0.577 (0.233)
Education (<i>ref. cat. ISCED 0-2</i>)							
ISCED 3-4	0.703 (0.187)	1.373* (0.223)	1.149 (0.223)	0.723 (0.186)	0.751 (0.224)	1.072 (0.247)	1.007 (0.227)
ISCED 5-8	0.459*** (0.123)	1.418** (0.222)	1.264 (0.248)	0.822 (0.203)	0.585* (0.169)	0.777 (0.167)	1.033 (0.227)
Social scale self- placement (centered)	0.925 (0.0671)	0.922** (0.0332)	0.888** (0.0442)	0.983 (0.0624)	1.050 (0.0787)	1.014 (0.0605)	0.968 (0.0488)
Civil status (<i>ref. cat. Married</i>)							
Civil union	2.119 (0.980)	0.610 (0.193)	0.806 (0.337)	0.522 (0.268)	2.422** (1.078)	0.693 (0.368)	1.590 (0.624)
Cohabitation	1.155 (0.370)	1.021 (0.175)	0.837 (0.182)	1.482 (0.414)	1.896** (0.550)	0.943 (0.268)	0.666 (0.188)
Divorced	0.963 (0.353)	1.021 (0.194)	1.227 (0.290)	1.361 (0.442)	1.801* (0.644)	0.828 (0.269)	1.044 (0.304)
Separated	0.764 (0.473)	0.813 (0.261)	1.555 (0.672)	0.348* (0.219)	2.081 (1.017)	1.863 (0.899)	0.828 (0.422)
Widowed	0.376 (0.248)	1.240 (0.358)	1.135 (0.462)	0.449 (0.222)	1.568 (0.727)	0.451 (0.260)	0.824 (0.377)
Single	1.386	0.905	1.078	1.158	1.369	0.749	0.850

Variables	(9) Middle class people	(10) Upper class people	(11) Religious minorities	(12) Religious majorities	(13) Non- disabled people	(14) Disabled people	(15) Ethnic minorities
Number of children (centered)	(0.441) 1.074	(0.143) 0.916**	(0.231) 1.030	(0.268) 1.087	(0.428) 0.967	(0.203) 0.968	(0.178) 0.934
Religion (<i>ref. cat. Roman-Catholic</i>)	(0.0810)	(0.0395)	(0.0571)	(0.0679)	(0.0683)	(0.0794)	(0.0637)
Protestant	0.735 (0.237)	1.043 (0.158)	1.347 (0.267)	1.586 (0.547)	1.178 (0.376)	0.694 (0.193)	1.272 (0.298)
Eastern Orthodox		0.739	0.748		0.563	1.112	0.502
Other Christian	1.562 (0.932)	1.127 (0.400)	2.129** (0.545)	1.110	0.265 (0.650)	0.770 (0.955)	0.870 (0.402)
Other non-Christian		2.770* (0.372)	4.408** (0.701)	31.43*** (0.882)	0.274 (0.217)		0.496 (0.452)
Jewish	10.37** (9.817)	0.951 (0.679)	0.673 (0.756)	(19.57)	0.894 (1.035)	0.527 (0.600)	(0.368)
Islam	3.203* (1.926)	0.964 (0.414)	1.341 (0.744)	2.438 (2.347)	1.427 (0.840)	1.243 (0.730)	1.751 (1.008)
Eastern religions	0.954 (0.686)	1.400 (0.571)	3.164** (1.814)	3.459 (2.659)	0.955 (0.798)	0.893 (0.757)	0.571 (0.420)
No denomination	1.246 (0.385)	1.061 (0.167)	1.016 (0.210)	4.871*** (1.309)	1.120 (0.389)	0.648 (0.190)	1.174 (0.278)
Other		1.983 (1.694)		9.126** (9.600)			1.672 (1.685)
None	1.742* (0.541)	1.254 (0.200)	0.920 (0.200)	2.432*** (0.821)	1.273 (0.467)	0.677 (0.212)	1.356 (0.333)
Level of religiosity (centered)	1.065* (0.0379)	0.968* (0.0186)	0.962 (0.0240)	1.021 (0.0403)	1.129*** (0.0450)	0.974 (0.0335)	0.992 (0.0268)
Employment (<i>ref. cat. >30h. pw</i>)							
<30h. pw	1.083 (0.482)	0.806 (0.179)	1.390 (0.432)	0.833 (0.307)	2.698*** (1.034)	0.219** (0.120)	0.529 (0.207)
Self-empl.	0.565 (0.274)	0.814 (0.165)	0.697 (0.225)	1.172 (0.417)	0.927 (0.417)	0.737 (0.309)	1.089 (0.313)
Military serv.					3.941 (5.132)		
Retired	0.961	0.970	1.290	1.259	1.505	1.293	1.475

Variables	(9) Middle class people	(10) Upper class people	(11) Religious minorities	(12) Religious majorities	(13) Non- disabled people	(14) Disabled people	(15) Ethnic minorities
Housemaker	(0.379) 2.371 (1.577)	(0.181) 1.335 (0.702)	(0.354) 0.217 (0.231)	(0.402) 3.103 (2.676)	(0.551) 0.226 (0.311)	(0.426) 0.809 (0.845)	(0.412) 0.265 (0.249)
Student	1.247 (0.721)	1.086 (0.329)	1.353 (0.571)	0.346* (0.219)	0.803 (0.586)	0.429 (0.221)	0.952 (0.373)
Unemployed	0.762 (0.394)	1.002 (0.321)	0.557 (0.292)	1.158 (0.537)	1.651 (0.971)	0.717 (0.323)	0.782 (0.335)
Disable	0.247* (0.196)	0.507 (0.233)	1.126 (0.575)	0.598 (0.418)	3.494** (2.051)	1.914 (0.929)	1.088 (0.488)
Other	0.357 (0.390)	1.347 (0.399)	1.708 (0.558)	0.434 (0.254)	0.293 (0.239)	0.647 (0.442)	1.615 (0.732)
Income satisfaction (<i>ref. cat. Comfortably</i>)							
Coping	1.224 (0.274)	1.020 (0.109)	1.135 (0.166)	1.045 (0.201)	0.964 (0.208)	0.780 (0.152)	1.379** (0.219)
Difficult	1.566 (0.503)	1.092 (0.190)	0.994 (0.244)	0.952 (0.289)	1.319 (0.396)	0.898 (0.256)	0.932 (0.253)
Very difficult	2.707** (1.251)	1.075 (0.348)	0.811 (0.396)	0.855 (0.420)	1.089 (0.671)	0.742 (0.372)	1.344 (0.574)
Personal income (centered)	1.102* (0.0634)	0.971 (0.0270)	0.975 (0.0344)	1.004 (0.0457)	1.125** (0.0617)	0.928 (0.0448)	0.978 (0.0403)
Household income (centered)	0.918* (0.0445)	1.033 (0.0278)	1.046 (0.0369)	0.976 (0.0393)	0.981 (0.0490)	0.930 (0.0434)	1.002 (0.0403)
Country (<i>ref. cat. UK</i>)							
Denmark	0.351*** (0.120)	1.103 (0.181)	1.794*** (0.396)	0.437* (0.208)	0.575* (0.186)	0.790 (0.229)	0.164*** (0.0515)
Hungary	0.597 (0.215)	1.454* (0.293)	0.556** (0.160)	4.745*** (1.678)	0.628 (0.257)	0.450** (0.163)	0.721 (0.212)
Spain	0.402*** (0.138)	0.642** (0.112)	2.088*** (0.483)	4.945*** (1.714)	0.512* (0.181)	0.776 (0.248)	0.840 (0.207)
Germany	0.341*** (0.105)	1.277* (0.183)	0.986 (0.214)	1.743* (0.569)	0.620* (0.169)	0.206** (0.0653)	0.223*** (0.0531)
Switzerland	1.124 (0.366)	1.147 (0.202)	0.875 (0.213)	0.521 (0.245)	0.911 (0.339)	0.438** (0.144)	0.205*** (0.0613)
Male GCI	0.983 (0.0580)	0.950* (0.0286)	1.071* (0.0420)	0.969 (0.0531)	1.035 (0.0730)	1.016 (0.0516)	0.978 (0.0396)
Female GCI		0.722* (0.126)	0.986 (0.233)	1.342 (0.301)	1.427 (0.386)	0.494* (0.193)	0.489* (0.207)
Own deservingnes s	1.040	0.925**	1.354***	0.943	1.034	1.116	0.997

Variables	(9) Middle class people	(10) Upper class people	(11) Religious minorities	(12) Religious majorities	(13) Non- disabled people	(14) Disabled people	(15) Ethnic minorities
Constant	(0.0784) 0.0973** *	(0.0334) 0.321** *	(0.0649) 0.0430** *	(0.0601) 0.0221** *	(0.0740) 0.0227** *	(0.0803) 0.386*	(0.0534) 0.409*
	(0.0634)	(0.114)	(0.0207)	(0.0136)	(0.0158)	(0.220)	(0.199)
Observations	3,036	3,139	3,133	3,099	3,138	3,112	3,124

Standard errors in parentheses
*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

Table A 14. Logit. DV: Unfairly advantaged social groups – Women (1/2)

Variables	(1) Men	(2) Wome n	(3) Young er people	(4) Older people	(5) LGBT Q+	(6) Heterosex ual people	(7) Immigra nts	(8) Workin g class people
Vote recall (UNTWIST scheme) (<i>ref. cat. RWPP</i>)								
MR	2.439** *	0.714	0.789	0.940	0.620* **	0.726	0.687**	0.838
	(0.488)	(0.176)	(0.162)	(0.171)	(0.106)	(0.243)	(0.101)	(0.155)
ML	4.434** *	0.852	0.710* *	1.064	0.414* **	0.913	0.308***	0.697* *
	(0.843)	(0.190)	(0.136)	(0.181)	(0.0760)	(0.279)	(0.0457)	(0.126)
RL	6.518** *	0.655	0.609	0.711	0.322* **	1.307	0.178***	0.480* *
	(1.675)	(0.258)	(0.200)	(0.201)	(0.103)	(0.505)	(0.0458)	(0.158)
Other	2.716** *	0.969	0.827	0.683	0.705	0.529	0.556***	1.107
	(0.747)	(0.324)	(0.240)	(0.196)	(0.204)	(0.281)	(0.125)	(0.303)
Age group (<i>ref. cat. 18-24</i>)								
25-39	1.216	0.809	0.574* (0.170)	0.904 (0.247)	0.730 (0.229)	1.005 (0.428)	1.058 (0.235)	0.736 (0.177)
40-54	1.052	0.598	0.631 *	0.529* *	0.590	0.501	1.306	0.552* *
	(0.252)	(0.205)	(0.195)	(0.153)	(0.190)	(0.238)	(0.295)	(0.145)
55-64	0.658	0.358* **	0.620	0.607	0.565	0.455	1.220	0.649
	(0.173)	(0.139)	(0.213)	(0.188)	(0.201)	(0.245)	(0.300)	(0.182)
65+	0.964 (0.314)	0.430* (0.213)	0.782 (0.301)	0.463* (0.191)	0.613 (0.261)	0.425 (0.244)	0.994 (0.293)	0.864 (0.302)
Education (<i>ref. cat. ISCED 0-2</i>)								
ISCED 3-4	1.152	0.570* *	0.869	0.630* *	1.137	0.845	0.950	0.882
	(0.228)	(0.134)	(0.162)	(0.119)	(0.225)	(0.273)	(0.155)	(0.168)
ISCED 5-8	1.813** *	0.332* **	0.874	0.545* **	1.197	0.987	0.817	0.724* *
	(0.354)	(0.0861)	(0.160)	(0.104)	(0.242)	(0.341)	(0.133)	(0.131)
Social scale self- placement (centered)	0.995 (0.0396)	1.120* (0.0698)	1.028 (0.0468)	1.007 (0.0490)	0.971 (0.0461)	1.067 (0.0949)	0.921** (0.0348)	0.874* ** (0.0424)
Civil status (<i>ref. cat. Married</i>)								
Civil union	1.997* (0.713)	1.470 (0.641)	1.547 (0.558)	1.148 (0.358)	0.649 (0.232)	0.524 (0.298)	0.746 (0.213)	0.591 (0.242)
Cohabitati	1.129	0.612	0.983	0.858	0.830	1.130	1.254	0.948

Variables	(1) Men	(2) Wome n	(3) Young er people	(4) Older people	(5) LGBT Q+	(6) Heterosex ual people	(7) Immigra nts	(8) Workin g class people
on								
Divorced	(0.184) 1.701** *	(0.186) 0.710	(0.215) 0.942	(0.172) 0.934	(0.170) 0.979	(0.341) 1.016	(0.211) 0.870	(0.208) 0.823
Separated	(0.312) 0.817	(0.216) 1.836	(0.210) 0.565	(0.208) 1.796	(0.246) 0.461*	(0.375) 0.963	(0.155) 0.518*	(0.198) 1.870
Widowed	(0.262) 1.559*	(0.731) 0.644	(0.304) 0.849	(0.691) 0.682	(0.202) 0.728	(0.650) 0.638	(0.186) 0.922	(0.745) 0.557*
Single	(0.362) 1.086	(0.244) 0.860	(0.223) 0.810	(0.200) 0.941	(0.220) 1.018	(0.383) 1.315	(0.214) 1.059	(0.180) 0.750
Number of children (centered)	(0.173) 0.900**	(0.238) 0.902	(0.171) 1.016	(0.176) 0.962	(0.208) 1.094* *	(0.416) 1.159***	(0.169) 1.014	(0.149) 0.999
	(0.0431)	(0.0665)	(0.0366)	(0.0430)	(0.0466)	(0.0531)	(0.0336)	(0.0429)
Religion (<i>ref. cat. Roman-Catholic</i>)								
Protestant	0.978 (0.157)	0.600* (0.165)	1.296 (0.239)	0.949 (0.174)	0.950 (0.194)	1.531 (0.473)	1.024 (0.163)	0.796 (0.162)
Eastern Orthodox	0.345 (0.243)	1.655 (0.782)	1.683 (0.692)	0.934 (0.478)	1.298 (0.559)	0.610 (0.569)	1.318 (0.693)	0.494 (0.256)
Other Christian	1.277 (0.464)	1.948 (0.804)	1.442 (0.594)	1.351 (0.461)	0.889 (0.286)	0.838 (0.411)	1.912** (0.604)	0.571 (0.215)
Jewish	0.424 (0.353)	5.402* (4.236)	0.952 (0.872)	0.968 (0.887)	3.914* (2.622)		0.775 (0.474)	0.153* (0.163)
Islam	1.144 (0.503)	1.561 (0.640)	0.426 (0.267)	0.583 (0.296)	1.474 (0.676)	1.486 (0.965)	0.980 (0.415)	0.470 (0.236)
Eastern religions	1.469 (0.737)	1.529 (1.197)	2.032 (1.209)	0.405 (0.442)	0.828 (0.537)		0.116*** (0.0722)	0.316 (0.239)
Other non- Christian	0.483 (0.331)	1.246 (1.135)	0.232 (0.246)	0.343 (0.295)	1.185 (1.306)		1.083 (0.894)	5.364* (3.437)
No denominati on	1.323 (0.245)	0.698 (0.202)	1.041 (0.246)	0.666* (0.147)	1.025 (0.229)	1.706 (0.609)	1.288 (0.225)	0.644* (0.147)
Other	0.345 (0.388)				1.706 (1.595)		4.567* (3.590)	
None	0.920 (0.175)	0.914 (0.269)	1.312 (0.296)	0.831 (0.171)	1.140 (0.267)	1.506 (0.519)	1.184 (0.215)	0.737 (0.169)
Level of religiosity	0.959* (0.175)	1.021 (0.269)	1.035 (0.296)	0.989 (0.171)	1.042* (0.267)	1.004 (0.519)	0.988 (0.215)	1.024 (0.169)

Variables	(1) Men	(2) Women	(3) Younger people	(4) Older people	(5) LGBT Q+	(6) Heterosex ual people	(7) Immigra nts	(8) Workin g class people
(centered)	(0.0205)	(0.0329)	(0.0286)	(0.0227)	(0.0256)	(0.0371)	(0.0203)	(0.0271)
Employment (<i>ref. cat. >30h. pw</i>)								
<30h. pw	1.090 (0.177)	1.006 (0.267)	1.168 (0.265)	0.802 (0.166)	1.022 (0.210)	0.481** (0.160)	1.008 (0.161)	0.930 (0.193)
Self-empl.	0.968 (0.241)	0.572 (0.392)	0.789 (0.278)	0.437* (0.141)	2.061* (0.629)	1.181 (0.520)	1.955*** (0.477)	0.934 (0.345)
Military serv.	0.0814 (0.126)	0.615 (0.666)	2.183 (2.138)	0.291 (0.348)	0.192 (0.237)	10.28** (9.307)	1.564 (1.122)	0.280 (0.353)
Retired	1.043 (0.252)	1.923* (0.729)	1.221 (0.334)	1.292 (0.413)	0.871 (0.259)	1.433 (0.546)	1.059 (0.223)	0.685 (0.197)
Housemak er	0.998 (0.274)	1.290 (0.424)	0.955 (0.289)	0.677 (0.206)	1.423 (0.348)	1.303 (0.570)	0.933 (0.217)	1.185 (0.300)
Student	2.185** *	0.484 (0.424)	0.507 (0.289)	0.741 (0.206)	0.571 (0.348)	2.357* (0.570)	1.327 (0.217)	1.065 (0.300)
Unemploy ed	1.222 (0.636)	0.566 (0.233)	0.861 (0.212)	1.082 (0.283)	0.822 (0.273)	0.921 (1.173)	0.652 (0.409)	0.590 (0.420)
Disable	1.458 (0.387)	0.852 (0.214)	1.060 (0.312)	0.723 (0.349)	0.739 (0.298)	0.465* (0.540)	0.920 (0.182)	0.521 (0.199)
Other	1.179 (0.574)	0.528 (0.523)	0.708 (0.504)	0.816 (0.295)	0.638 (0.340)	1.013 (0.196)	0.789 (0.310)	0.716 (0.244)
Income satisfaction (<i>ref. cat. Comfortably</i>)								
Coping	1.083 (0.130)	1.090 (0.232)	1.187 (0.178)	1.164 (0.177)	0.975 (0.152)	1.435 (0.336)	0.987 (0.121)	0.865 (0.142)
Difficult	0.909 (0.172)	1.134 (0.341)	0.981 (0.219)	1.651* (0.346)	0.902 (0.202)	1.534 (0.652)	0.989 (0.179)	0.979 (0.208)
Very difficult	0.792 (0.253)	1.521 (0.686)	1.162 (0.376)	1.350 (0.444)	1.088 (0.419)	1.008 (0.719)	1.210 (0.360)	1.251 (0.397)
Personal income (centered)	0.959* (0.0243)	1.048 (0.0460)	1.048 (0.0342)	1.056* (0.0347)	1.006 (0.0326)	1.063 (0.0594)	0.988 (0.0260)	1.024 (0.0370)
Household income (centered)	1.053** (0.0261)	0.901* (0.0383)	0.909* (0.0320)	0.985 (0.0301)	1.046 (0.0336)	0.996 (0.0578)	0.999 (0.0253)	0.944* (0.0324)

Variables	(1) Men	(2) Wome n	(3) Young er people	(4) Older people	(5) LGBT Q+	(6) Heterosex ual people	(7) Immigra nts	(8) Workin g class people
<i>Country (ref. cat. UK)</i>								
Denmark	0.875	1.219	0.763	1.116	0.703	0.534	1.000	0.489*
	(0.177)	(0.390)	(0.172)	(0.247)	(0.164)	(0.207)	(0.197)	(0.136)
Hungary	0.716	0.913	0.804	1.372	0.488*	1.015	0.474***	0.624*
	(0.183)	(0.325)	(0.229)	(0.359)	(0.133)	(0.485)	(0.109)	(0.177)
Spain	0.573**	1.667*	0.926	0.861	1.317	1.365	1.383*	0.801
	(0.126)	(0.514)	(0.215)	(0.204)	(0.297)	(0.507)	(0.268)	(0.194)
Germany	1.713**	1.560*	0.510*	1.067	0.514*	0.784	1.167	0.818
	*		**		**			
Switzerlan d	1.344	0.956	0.531*	0.962	0.809	1.111	1.048	0.668
	(0.255)	(0.400)	(0.109)	(0.201)	(0.104)	(0.233)	(0.187)	(0.169)
Male GCI	1.260	1.141	0.765	0.696	0.886	0.793	1.107	0.945
	(0.242)	(0.286)	(0.130)	(0.212)	(0.173)	(0.394)	(0.209)	(0.179)
Female GCI	1.347**	1.040	1.014	1.027	0.906*	1.134***	0.879***	0.895*
	*				**			**
Own deservingn ess	0.838**	1.277*	1.131*	1.036	1.022	0.951	1.235***	1.280*
	*	**	*					**
Constant	0.0606*	0.133*	0.212*	0.368*	0.405*	0.0395***	0.376***	0.366*
	**	**	**	*				*
	(0.0249)	(0.0720)	(0.106)	(0.166)	(0.195)	(0.0282)	(0.133)	(0.154)
Observatio ns	3,894	3,885	3,885	3,885	3,894	3,820	3,894	3,885

Standard errors in parentheses
*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

Table A 15. Logit. DV: Unfairly advantaged social groups – Women (2/2)

Variables	(9) Middle class people	(10) Upper class people	(11) Religious minorities	(12) Religious majorities	(13) Non- disabled people	(14) Disabled people	(15) Ethnic minorities
Vote recall (UNTWIST scheme) (<i>ref. cat. RWPP</i>)							
MR	1.083 (0.305)	1.035 (0.152)	1.025 (0.215)	1.184 (0.414)	1.043 (0.303)	0.802 (0.136)	1.086 (0.199)
ML	1.073 (0.290)	2.109** (0.283) *	0.545*** (0.117)	1.106 (0.336)	1.523* (0.383)	0.714** (0.119)	0.568*** (0.105)
RL	1.089 (0.643)	3.890** (0.786) *	0.275*** (0.105)	2.194* (0.926)	1.435 (0.506)	0.477** (0.136) *	0.278*** (0.107)
Other	1.389 (0.535)	1.610** (0.321)	0.924 (0.291)	1.724 (0.587)	0.742 (0.349)	0.818 (0.238)	0.281*** (0.111)
Age group (<i>ref. cat. 18-24</i>)							
25-39	1.853 (0.791)	1.045 (0.216)	1.128 (0.358)	0.751 (0.261)	0.627 (0.183)	0.683 (0.181)	0.917 (0.304)
40-54	1.110 (0.496)	1.309 (0.281)	1.375 (0.432)	0.867 (0.315)	0.527** (0.166)	0.592* (0.160)	1.147 (0.376)
55-64	1.205 (0.567)	1.250 (0.288)	1.640 (0.566)	0.595 (0.247)	0.430** (0.152)	0.637 (0.187)	1.148 (0.412)
65+	1.102 (0.553)	1.512 (0.417)	2.192* (0.919)	0.882 (0.420)	0.434* (0.199)	0.788 (0.289)	1.038 (0.449)
Education (<i>ref. cat. ISCED 0-2</i>)							
ISCED 3-4	1.041 (0.263)	1.278* (0.185)	0.963 (0.183)	1.450 (0.555)	0.787 (0.224)	1.098 (0.201)	1.050 (0.217)
ISCED 5-8	0.762 (0.199)	1.788** (0.259) *	0.864 (0.175)	1.499 (0.556)	1.363 (0.362)	0.700** (0.126)	0.775 (0.167)
Social scale self- placement (centered)	0.970 (0.0607)	0.924** (0.0297)	1.011 (0.0488)	0.882* (0.0663)	0.884* (0.0567)	0.974 (0.0432)	0.980 (0.0459)
Civil status (<i>ref. cat. Married</i>)							
Civil union	0.920 (0.448)	1.193 (0.307)	1.364 (0.480)	1.193 (0.508)	1.247 (0.676)	0.881 (0.320)	0.564 (0.250)
Cohabitation	0.776 (0.250)	0.914 (0.135)	0.984 (0.211)	1.103 (0.307)	1.401 (0.390)	1.195 (0.265)	1.102 (0.250)
Divorced	0.826 (0.259)	1.602** (0.259) *	0.677 (0.193)	0.616 (0.207)	1.610* (0.420)	0.664* (0.160)	1.168 (0.283)
Separated	0.816 (0.557)	0.947 (0.267)	0.455* (0.213)	0.263* (0.205)	0.892 (0.487)	1.914* (0.668)	0.170*** (0.0941)
Widowed	1.279	1.884** *	0.923	0.378	2.278**	1.012	0.650

Variables	(9) Middle class people	(10) Upper class people	(11) Religious minorities	(12) Religious majorities	(13) Non- disabled people	(14) Disabled people	(15) Ethnic minorities
Single	(0.525) 1.057 (0.295)	(0.381) 1.318** (0.185)	(0.288) 0.904 (0.202)	(0.225) 1.025 (0.320)	(0.840) 1.494 (0.375)	(0.276) 1.183 (0.235)	(0.208) 0.788 (0.173)
Number of children (centered)	1.039 (0.0564)	0.944* (0.0304)	1.010 (0.0459)	1.062 (0.0527)	0.905 (0.0609)	1.129** (0.0404) *	0.891* (0.0527)
Religion (<i>ref. cat. Roman-Catholic</i>)							
Protestant	0.561** (0.151)	1.143 (0.155)	1.170 (0.259)	0.826 (0.335)	1.136 (0.325)	0.696* (0.131)	1.192 (0.281)
Eastern Orthodox	0.525 (0.352)	0.528 (0.268)	1.094 (0.591)	3.693* (2.558)	1.632 (1.317)	0.675 (0.367)	1.273 (0.633)
Other Christian	1.020 (0.451)	0.688 (0.209)	2.036* (0.827)	2.783* (1.610)	1.563 (0.795)	0.988 (0.342)	0.645 (0.286)
Jewish	0.274 (0.340)	0.690 (0.552)	0.587 (0.663)	4.918 (5.197)	2.113 (1.724)	0.207 (0.242)	3.253 (3.515)
Islam	1.457 (0.803)	1.578 (0.540)	2.677** (1.082)	4.683*** (2.752)	0.706 (0.538)	0.585 (0.253)	0.933 (0.530)
Eastern religions	5.286*** (3.113)	0.805 (0.412)	0.971 (0.829)		4.306** (2.799)	0.422 (0.311)	1.377 (1.047)
Other non- Christian	3.102 (3.274)	0.702 (0.534)	0.591 (0.522)	3.143 (2.496)	0.370 (0.467)	3.901** (2.703)	0.419 (0.296)
No denominatio n	0.175*** (0.0840)	1.321* (0.197)	1.466 (0.348)	2.114** (0.620)	1.421 (0.418)	0.592** (0.133)	1.543* (0.359)
Other		0.574 (0.438)	1.663 (1.611)			1.190 (1.360)	6.870** (5.594)
None	1.001 (0.272)	1.090 (0.169)	0.902 (0.242)	1.280 (0.487)	1.904** (0.599)	0.751 (0.154)	0.821 (0.210)
Level of religiosity (centered)	1.055 (0.0383)	0.975 (0.0172)	1.048* (0.0266)	1.025 (0.0420)	1.044 (0.0395)	1.046* (0.0251)	0.989 (0.0281)
Employment (<i>ref. cat. >30h. pw</i>)							
<30h. pw	0.721 (0.215)	0.773* (0.111)	1.063 (0.247)	0.674 (0.218)	2.215*** (0.575)	0.783 (0.170)	0.761 (0.194)
Self-empl.	0.379* (0.209)	0.479** (0.114) *	1.797 (0.648)	0.591 (0.291)	0.856 (0.602)	1.256 (0.407)	1.518 (0.571)
Military serv.	0.194 (0.209)	0.0341* (0.114) *		21.53*** (0.291)	1.157 (0.602)	12.18** (0.407)	14.60*** (0.571)

Variables	(9) Middle class people	(10) Upper class people	(11) Religious minorities	(12) Religious majorities	(13) Non- disabled people	(14) Disabled people	(15) Ethnic minorities
Retired	(0.293) 0.915 (0.303)	(0.0518) 0.774 (0.153)		(18.34) 1.221 (0.455)	(1.598) 2.866*** (1.052)	(14.24) 0.918 (0.269)	(11.17) 0.965 (0.309)
Housemaker	1.252 (0.451)	0.686* (0.145)	1.148 (0.325)	0.786 (0.383)	4.982*** (1.657)	0.993 (0.277)	1.346 (0.396)
Student	0.390 (0.326)	0.821 (0.227)	0.732 (0.398)	0.830 (0.372)	1.792 (0.788)	0.640 (0.251)	1.695 (0.803)
Unemployed	0.424* (0.188)	1.184 (0.307)	0.887 (0.316)	0.701 (0.410)	1.111 (0.598)	1.064 (0.305)	0.659 (0.242)
Disable	0.584 (0.388)	1.346 (0.421)	0.746 (0.374)	1.391 (0.848)	7.812*** (2.881)	1.545 (0.526)	0.618 (0.349)
Other	0.306* (0.190)	1.607* (0.425)	0.935 (0.363)	0.792 (0.501)	2.487** (0.898)	0.825 (0.297)	0.818 (0.337)
Income satisfaction (<i>ref. cat. Comfortably</i>)							
Coping	1.014 (0.222)	1.382** (0.151) *	1.138 (0.207)	0.790 (0.174)	1.277 (0.283)	0.886 (0.140)	1.031 (0.193)
Difficult	1.396 (0.386)	1.001 (0.159)	1.404 (0.362)	0.798 (0.261)	1.828** (0.556)	1.120 (0.241)	1.163 (0.296)
Very difficult	1.450 (0.593)	0.609** (0.150) *	1.396 (0.611)	0.868 (0.433)	2.864*** (1.146)	1.449 (0.442)	0.931 (0.371)
Personal income (centered)	0.946 (0.0480)	0.898** (0.0215) *	1.040 (0.0387)	0.991 (0.0501)	1.083* (0.0501)	1.023 (0.0341)	1.048 (0.0375)
Household income (centered)	0.984 (0.0485)	1.084** (0.0240) *	0.977 (0.0331)	1.010 (0.0534)	1.040 (0.0452)	0.946* (0.0315)	0.987 (0.0353)
Country (<i>ref. cat. UK</i>)							
Denmark	0.706 (0.275)	1.018 (0.170)	1.373 (0.334)	0.291** (0.171)	1.319 (0.382)	0.763 (0.173)	0.117*** (0.0394)
Hungary	0.658 (0.209)	1.228 (0.245) *	0.628 (0.201)	2.485** (1.078)	0.960 (0.420)	0.481** (0.121) *	1.214 (0.320)
Spain	0.696 (0.213)	0.616** (0.107) *	1.406 (0.386)	1.957 (0.866)	0.944 (0.327)	0.565** (0.125)	0.870 (0.218)
Germany	0.378*** (0.103)	0.988 (0.136)	0.891 (0.194)	1.371 (0.451)	1.015 (0.256)	0.456** (0.0906) *	0.353*** (0.0840)
Switzerland	0.708 (0.206)	0.777 (0.130)	0.483*** (0.130)	0.689 (0.308)	1.022 (0.317)	0.523** (0.124) *	0.209*** (0.0587)
Male GCI	0.993	1.104	0.819	0.642	1.245	0.829	1.173

Variables	(9) Middle class people	(10) Upper class people	(11) Religious minorities	(12) Religious majorities	(13) Non- disabled people	(14) Disabled people	(15) Ethnic minorities
Female GCI	(0.195) 1.066	(0.275) 1.095** *	(0.192) 1.009	(0.405) 1.040	(0.277) 1.032	(0.200) 0.890** *	(0.276) 0.871***
Own deservingness	(0.0438) 1.157**	(0.0258) 0.843** *	(0.0372) 1.252***	(0.0452) 0.990	(0.0495) 0.801***	(0.0314) 1.022	(0.0347) 1.064
Constant	(0.0841) 0.0561** *	(0.0306) 0.354** *	(0.0686) 0.0497** *	(0.0710) 0.0258** *	(0.0606) 0.0369** *	(0.0492) 0.716	(0.0614) 0.283**
Observations	(0.0342) 3,885	(0.118) 3,894	(0.0238) 3,885	(0.0193) 3,856	(0.0198) 3,885	(0.303) 3,894	(0.143) 3,894

Standard errors in parentheses

*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

Table A 16. Logit. DV: Losers of Feminism

Variables	(1) Gendered Positional Deprivatio n	(2) Losers of Feminism	(3) Gendered Positional Deprivatio n - Men	(4) Gendered Positional Deprivatio n - Women	(5) Losers of Feminism - Men	(6) Losers of Feminism - Women
Vote recall (UNTWIST scheme) (<i>ref. cat. RWPP</i>)						
MR	0.763** (0.0842)	0.293*** (0.120)	0.643*** (0.0995)	0.974 (0.148)	0.281** (0.160)	0.309* (0.206)
ML	0.787** (0.0798)	0.0926** (0.0534) *	0.563*** (0.0828)	1.140 (0.156)	0.0207*** (0.0230)	0.267 (0.226)
RL	1.131 (0.179)	0.747 (0.422)	0.712 (0.176)	1.950*** (0.410)	0.450 (0.309)	0.985 (0.709)
Other	1.074 (0.165)	0.678 (0.316)	0.738 (0.174)	1.578** (0.323)	0.330 (0.299)	1.815 (1.236)
Gender (<i>ref. cat. Men</i>)						
Women	1.317*** (0.0942)	0.838 (0.403)				
Age group (<i>ref. cat. 18-24</i>)						
25-39	0.795 (0.127)	0.435* (0.220)	0.674* (0.157)	0.911 (0.198)	1.396 (1.186)	0.157** (0.118)
40-54	0.756* (0.126)	0.178*** (0.104)	0.564** (0.140)	0.939 (0.211)	0.482 (0.439)	0.110*** (0.0916)
55-64	0.822 (0.147)	0.625 (0.377)	0.700 (0.187)	0.861 (0.205)	1.000 (0.969)	0.395 (0.304)
65+	0.636** (0.138)	0.669 (0.577)	0.677 (0.217)	0.537** (0.160)	0.184 (0.198)	1.990 (1.630)
Education (<i>ref. cat. ISCED 0-2</i>)						
ISCED 3-4	1.290** (0.162)	1.011 (0.509)	1.005 (0.184)	1.604*** (0.275)	1.113 (0.776)	1.945 (1.488)
ISCED 5-8	1.425*** (0.177)	0.762 (0.391)	1.180 (0.210)	1.711*** (0.293)	0.954 (0.741)	1.061 (0.816)
Social scale self- placement (centered)	1.002 (0.0251)	1.037 (0.106)	0.967 (0.0378)	1.030 (0.0340)	0.837 (0.137)	1.152 (0.201)
Civil status (<i>ref. cat. Married</i>)						
Civil union	0.950 (0.220)	0.848 (0.806)	1.407 (0.447)	0.644 (0.192)	3.264 (3.389)	0.315 (0.380)
Cohabitation	1.117 (0.132)	1.828 (0.827)	0.955 (0.185)	1.218 (0.186)	2.139 (1.216)	0.838 (0.529)
Divorced	1.011 (0.125)	0.166** (0.134)	0.768 (0.160)	1.189 (0.190)	0.269 (0.346)	0.104* (0.142)
Single	0.940 (0.105)	0.802 (0.426)	0.851 (0.150)	0.977 (0.147)	0.933 (0.604)	0.286* (0.210)
Separated	0.666*		0.402**	0.856		

Variables	(1) Gendered Positional Deprivatio n	(2) Losers of Feminism	(3) Gendered Positional Deprivatio n - Men	(4) Gendered Positional Deprivatio n - Women	(5) Losers of Feminism - Men	(6) Losers of Feminism - Women
Widowed	(0.152) 0.870		(0.168) 0.876	(0.249) 0.937		
Other	(0.167) 3.399**		(0.329) 1.355	(0.210) 5.074**		
Number of children (centered)	(2.014) 1.018	0.798	(1.553) 0.956	(3.912) 1.051	1.021	0.514**
Religion (<i>ref. cat. Roman-Catholic</i>)	(0.0269)	(0.114)	(0.0450)	(0.0378)	(0.154)	(0.149)
Protestant	1.093 (0.119)	0.972 (0.565)	1.026 (0.175)	1.118 (0.160)	0.913 (0.709)	0.766 (0.758)
Eastern Orthodox	1.100 (0.383)	0.905 (1.069)	0.526 (0.274)	2.517** (1.144)	0.340 (0.642)	
Other Christian	0.911 (0.218)	4.521** (3.389)	0.495* (0.209)	1.307 (0.414)		13.98*** (10.63)
Jewish	0.747 (0.375)		0.727 (0.503)	0.652 (0.466)		
Other non- Christian	0.568 (0.296)		0.668 (0.431)	0.706 (0.586)		
Islam	1.125 (0.310)	3.183 (2.804)	0.921 (0.375)	1.413 (0.529)		9.450*** (6.720)
Eastern religions	0.660 (0.275)	13.56** (16.76)	0.373* (0.213)	1.123 (0.658)		23.10*** (20.98)
No denominatio n	1.077 (0.128)	0.352* (0.200)	0.922 (0.168)	1.275 (0.201)	0.416 (0.297)	0.298 (0.244)
None	0.974 (0.116)	0.638 (0.390)	0.906 (0.165)	1.003 (0.160)	0.670 (0.591)	0.697 (0.530)
Level of religiosity (centered)	1.020 (0.0139)	0.994 (0.0552)	1.007 (0.0213)	1.027 (0.0186)	1.031 (0.0873)	1.023 (0.0567)
Employment (<i>ref. cat. >30h. pw</i>)						
<30h. pw	0.861 (0.107)	2.337 (1.338)	0.575** (0.161)	0.941 (0.137)	7.034** (5.621)	1.680 (0.820)
Self-empl.	0.880 (0.162)	1.764 (1.126)	0.692 (0.174)	1.178 (0.330)	1.496 (1.151)	2.360 (1.652)
Retired	0.888 (0.137)	0.883 (0.725)	0.720 (0.172)	1.169 (0.250)	2.521 (2.036)	0.637 (0.742)

Variables	(1) Gendered Positional Deprivation	(2) Losers of Feminism	(3) Gendered Positional Deprivation - Men	(4) Gendered Positional Deprivation - Women	(5) Losers of Feminism - Men	(6) Losers of Feminism - Women
Military serv.	1.090 (0.844)		2.008 (1.989)	0.607 (0.695)		
Unemployed	0.866 (0.185)		0.869 (0.316)	0.924 (0.233)		
Disable	0.498** (0.153)		0.620 (0.276)	0.423** (0.173)		
Housemaker	0.831 (0.170)	0.419 (0.411)	1.023 (0.566)	0.907 (0.207)		0.712 (0.915)
Student	0.881 (0.182)	2.027 (1.196)	1.266 (0.370)	0.612* (0.178)	6.764** (6.103)	0.661 (0.461)
Other	1.290 (0.261)	2.555 (2.613)	1.151 (0.423)	1.313 (0.327)	7.987 (10.51)	1.821 (2.322)
Income satisfaction (<i>ref. cat. Comfortably</i>)						
Coping	1.084 (0.0913)	1.861* (0.700)	1.226 (0.154)	0.998 (0.115)	1.101 (0.505)	2.183 (1.552)
Difficult	1.222 (0.156)	2.633** (1.242)	1.488** (0.298)	1.089 (0.180)	1.391 (0.853)	4.350 (4.219)
Very difficult	1.495** (0.304)	3.117 (2.297)	1.477 (0.518)	1.677** (0.422)	0.341 (0.674)	9.170** (8.909)
Personal income (centered)	0.987 (0.0186)	1.223** (0.108)	1.028 (0.0314)	0.962 (0.0242)	1.230* (0.154)	1.218* (0.126)
Household income (centered)	1.001 (0.0176)	0.971 (0.0659)	0.995 (0.0283)	1.003 (0.0224)	1.022 (0.102)	1.032 (0.0946)
Country (<i>ref. cat. UK</i>)						
Denmark	0.533*** (0.0729)	0.246** (0.150)	0.576*** (0.114)	0.464*** (0.0898)	0.251 (0.214)	0.169*** (0.108)
Hungary	1.006 (0.150)	0.693 (0.462)	0.883 (0.200)	1.218 (0.249)	0.502 (0.559)	0.986 (0.843)
Spain	0.477*** (0.0685)	2.253 (1.583)	0.479*** (0.102)	0.460*** (0.0903)	5.441* (5.349)	0.912 (0.894)
Germany	1.233** (0.130)	1.234 (0.691)	1.036 (0.161)	1.427** (0.206)	2.111 (1.297)	0.550 (0.553)
Switzerland	0.852 (0.111)	0.810 (0.480)	0.784 (0.156)	0.885 (0.154)	1.342 (1.134)	0.262 (0.216)
Male GCI		1.725*** (0.114)			1.786*** (0.118)	0.121 (0.350)
Female GCI		1.545*** (0.106)			2.246* (1.027)	1.697*** (0.156)
Constant	0.369***	0.0139**	0.738	0.237***	0.00647**	0.00596**

Variables	(1) Gendered Positional Deprivation	(2) Losers of Feminism	(3) Gendered Positional Deprivation - Men	(4) Gendered Positional Deprivation - Women	(5) Losers of Feminism - Men	(6) Losers of Feminism - Women
	(0.0939)	* (0.0139)	(0.278)	(0.0765)	* (0.0102)	* (0.00945)
Observations	7,044	6,190	3,145	3,899	2,701	3,301

Standard errors in parentheses
*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

Table A 17. Logit. DV: Losers of Globalisation

Variables	(7) Relative Deprivatio n	(8) Losers of Globalisatio n	(9) Relative Deprivatio n - Men	(10) Relative Deprivatio n - Women	(11) Losers of Globalisatio n - Men	(12) Losers of Globalisatio n - Women
Vote recall (UNTWIST scheme) (<i>ref. cat. RWPP</i>)						
MR	0.633*** (0.0594)	0.496*** (0.126)	0.664*** (0.0875)	0.593*** (0.0817)	0.429** (0.149)	0.608 (0.188)
ML	0.555*** (0.0497)	0.196*** (0.0537)	0.592*** (0.0756)	0.522*** (0.0670)	0.154*** (0.0587)	0.272*** (0.101)
RL	0.854 (0.127)	0.189*** (0.107)	0.723 (0.155)	0.972 (0.193)	0.194** (0.128)	0.218 (0.216)
Other	0.733** (0.108)	0.445** (0.150)	0.687* (0.146)	0.737 (0.153)	0.418* (0.210)	0.585 (0.267)
Gender (<i>ref. cat. Men</i>)						
Women	0.846** (0.0647)	0.747 (0.157)				
Age group (<i>ref. cat. 18-24</i>)						
25-39	1.055 (0.169)	0.529 (0.237)	0.909 (0.226)	1.226 (0.255)	0.508 (0.376)	0.620 (0.284)
40-54	1.303 (0.216)	0.807 (0.364)	1.131 (0.292)	1.521* (0.327)	0.678 (0.530)	1.039 (0.396)
55-64	1.417** (0.251)	0.766 (0.348)	1.310 (0.359)	1.551* (0.362)	0.566 (0.447)	0.969 (0.464)
65+	1.216 (0.247)	0.899 (0.490)	0.881 (0.274)	1.641* (0.453)	0.532 (0.479)	1.264 (0.930)
Education (<i>ref. cat. ISCED 0-2</i>)						
ISCED 3-4	1.139 (0.124)	1.143 (0.324)	1.459** (0.236)	0.907 (0.132)	0.955 (0.392)	1.711 (0.669)
ISCED 5-8	0.966 (0.103)	0.984 (0.289)	1.132 (0.178)	0.830 (0.118)	0.733 (0.310)	1.579 (0.672)
Social scale self- placement (centered)	0.911*** (0.0223)	0.930 (0.0530)	0.871*** (0.0320)	0.954 (0.0315)	0.918 (0.0802)	0.893 (0.0702)
Civil status (<i>ref. cat. Married</i>)						
Civil union	0.714 (0.152)	0.891 (0.655)	0.787 (0.258)	0.653 (0.175)	1.175 (1.355)	0.253** (0.160)
Cohabitatio n	1.077 (0.116)	1.025 (0.297)	1.065 (0.167)	1.109 (0.162)	0.897 (0.419)	1.130 (0.448)
Divorced	0.922 (0.110)	0.695 (0.235)	0.978 (0.192)	0.911 (0.140)	0.993 (0.428)	0.424* (0.194)
Single	0.823* (0.0858)	0.817 (0.277)	0.843 (0.128)	0.823 (0.119)	0.847 (0.529)	0.667 (0.220)
Separated	0.745	0.527	0.932	0.685	0.910	0.304

Variables	(7) Relative Deprivation	(8) Losers of Globalisation	(9) Relative Deprivation - Men	(10) Relative Deprivation - Women	(11) Losers of Globalisation - Men	(12) Losers of Globalisation - Women
Widowed	(0.159) 1.020	(0.297) 0.469	(0.310) 1.093	(0.196) 0.973	(0.666)	(0.259) 0.885
Number of children (centered)	(0.153) 0.982	(0.232) 1.074	(0.304) 1.034	(0.181) 0.948*	1.209**	(0.473) 0.852
Religion (<i>ref. cat. Roman-Catholic</i>)	(0.0250)	(0.0615)	(0.0422)	(0.0285)	(0.105)	(0.107)
Protestant	0.918	1.019	0.791	1.019	0.987	1.164
Eastern Orthodox	(0.0902) 0.688	(0.292) 1.593	(0.115) 0.510	(0.137) 1.073	(0.450) 1.712	(0.434) 2.270
Other Christian	(0.221) 0.756	(1.009) 1.561	(0.229) 0.660	(0.468) 0.867	(1.467) 3.333*	(1.970) 0.419
Jewish	(0.167) 1.384	(0.898)	(0.205) 0.812	(0.264) 2.778	(2.326)	(0.320)
Other non-Christian	(0.679) 1.186	3.030	(0.554) 1.511	(1.787) 0.842		7.735***
Other	(0.513) 0.971	(2.833)	(0.861) 0.612	(0.578) 1.282		(5.294)
None	(0.565) 1.032	0.970	(0.542) 0.977	(0.942) 1.041	0.902	1.084
Level of religiosity (centered)	(0.115) 0.991	(0.275) 0.898***	(0.160) 0.984	(0.158) 0.994	(0.384) 0.886**	(0.441) 0.932
Employment (<i>ref. cat. >30h. pw</i>)	(0.0127)	(0.0314)	(0.0194)	(0.0169)	(0.0442)	(0.0462)
<30h. pw	0.910	0.993	0.947	0.889	0.792	0.825
Self-empl.	(0.111) 0.806	(0.313) 1.133	(0.234) 0.759	(0.129) 0.862	(0.502) 1.328	(0.301) 1.052
Retired	(0.131) 0.952	(0.549) 0.936	(0.165) 1.193	(0.210) 0.777	(0.810) 1.601	(0.802) 0.420
Military serv.	(0.126) 0.861	(0.325)	(0.229) 1.151	(0.150) 0.633	(0.638)	(0.271)
Unemployed	(0.692) 1.075	0.697	(1.260) 1.143	(0.718) 1.043	0.523	0.478
Disable	(0.212) 0.951	(0.357) 0.949	(0.358) 0.912	(0.259) 0.996	(0.472) 2.121	(0.237) 0.0976**
Income satisfaction (<i>ref. cat. Comfortably</i>)	(0.252)	(0.495)	(0.423)	(0.333)	(1.582)	(0.0992)

Variables	(7) Relative Deprivation	(8) Losers of Globalisation	(9) Relative Deprivation - Men	(10) Relative Deprivation - Women	(11) Losers of Globalisation - Men	(12) Losers of Globalisation - Women
Coping	1.256*** (0.0923)	1.789** (0.475)	1.468*** (0.155)	1.080 (0.112)	1.759 (0.634)	1.793 (0.672)
Difficult	1.793*** (0.210)	1.823* (0.619)	2.140*** (0.387)	1.570*** (0.245)	2.073 (0.980)	1.383 (0.660)
Very difficult	2.419*** (0.527)	2.900** (1.342)	2.260** (0.823)	2.592*** (0.688)	1.089 (0.952)	4.786*** (2.648)
Personal income (centered)	0.999 (0.0168)	0.979 (0.0481)	1.017 (0.0270)	0.981 (0.0221)	1.038 (0.0812)	0.867** (0.0550)
Household income (centered)	0.999 (0.0166)	1.001 (0.0433)	1.008 (0.0262)	0.990 (0.0216)	1.002 (0.0714)	0.990 (0.0516)
Country (<i>ref. cat. UK</i>)						
Denmark	0.336*** (0.0393)	0.275*** (0.129)	0.304*** (0.0510)	0.360*** (0.0595)	0.138** (0.109)	0.674 (0.410)
Hungary	0.693*** (0.0961)	1.058 (0.347)	0.558*** (0.113)	0.818 (0.160)	1.347 (0.613)	0.581 (0.277)
Spain	0.686*** (0.0819)	1.666 (0.544)	0.623*** (0.108)	0.732* (0.121)	1.611 (0.765)	1.664 (0.803)
Germany	1.102 (0.106)	2.099*** (0.582)	0.950 (0.132)	1.250* (0.167)	2.152** (0.810)	1.941 (0.842)
Switzerland	0.741** (0.0901)	1.608 (0.559)	0.739* (0.131)	0.742* (0.125)	0.777 (0.502)	3.051** (1.415)
Male GCI	1.057* (0.0299)	0.956 (0.0790)	1.065** (0.0315)	0.905 (0.138)	0.928 (0.0809)	0.772 (0.495)
Female GCI	0.973 (0.0222)	0.878 (0.0873)	0.973 (0.210)	0.972 (0.0226)		0.882 (0.0915)
Constant	2.282*** (0.528)	0.0523*** (0.0339)	2.179** (0.739)	2.049** (0.648)	0.0840** (0.0862)	0.0175*** (0.0133)
Observations	7,044	6,820	3,145	3,899	2,883	3,775

Standard errors in parentheses
*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

Table A 18. Logit. DV: Aggrieved social groups

Variables	(1) Men	(2) Men among men	(3) Men among women	(4) Women	(5) Women among men	(6) Women among women
Vote recall (UNTWIST scheme) (<i>ref. cat. RWPP</i>)						
MR	0.520*** (0.0908)	0.498*** (0.0972)	0.627 (0.269)	1.144 (0.154)	1.004 (0.242)	1.267 (0.208)
ML	0.223*** (0.0477)	0.218*** (0.0500)	0.255** (0.148)	1.556*** (0.191)	1.896*** (0.416)	1.460** (0.218)
RL	0.0749*** (0.0385)	0.0631*** (0.0416)	0.138*** (0.102)	1.634*** (0.311)	2.503*** (0.756)	1.177 (0.287)
Other	0.492** (0.169)	0.459** (0.176)	0.596 (0.461)	1.790*** (0.322)	2.062** (0.633)	1.679** (0.374)
Gender (<i>ref. cat. Men</i>)						
Women	0.139*** (0.0318)			1.768*** (0.172)		
Age group (<i>ref. cat. 18-24</i>)						
25-39	1.083 (0.380)	1.112 (0.420)	1.382 (1.416)	0.615*** (0.108)	0.528** (0.155)	0.637** (0.145)
40-54	1.010 (0.373)	1.135 (0.447)	0.904 (1.007)	0.728* (0.134)	0.457** (0.143)	0.892 (0.211)
55-64	0.979 (0.378)	1.041 (0.433)	1.096 (1.217)	0.548*** (0.111)	0.462** (0.153)	0.575** (0.150)
65+	0.580 (0.280)	0.761 (0.375)	0.283 (0.424)	0.667* (0.163)	0.389** (0.153)	0.976 (0.307)
Education (<i>ref. cat. ISCED 0-2</i>)						
ISCED 3-4	0.808 (0.182)	0.845 (0.211)	0.766 (0.413)	0.871 (0.116)	0.989 (0.220)	0.792 (0.132)
ISCED 5-8	0.949 (0.212)	1.064 (0.264)	0.599 (0.339)	1.075 (0.138)	1.438* (0.302)	0.919 (0.149)
Social scale self- placement (centered)	0.935 (0.0523)	0.939 (0.0587)	0.933 (0.121)	0.992 (0.0302)	1.069 (0.0526)	0.936* (0.0361)
Civil status (<i>ref. cat. Married</i>)						
Civil union	1.536 (0.629)	1.799 (0.817)	0.895 (1.037)	0.926 (0.257)	0.728 (0.361)	1.073 (0.340)
Cohabitation	1.144 (0.281)	1.206 (0.325)	0.943 (0.585)	0.849 (0.120)	0.980 (0.221)	0.833 (0.150)
Divorced	1.442 (0.386)	1.373 (0.431)	2.126 (1.221)	1.162 (0.168)	1.135 (0.299)	1.204 (0.213)
Separated	1.051 (0.521)	1.287 (0.731)	0.272 (0.316)	0.771 (0.196)	0.723 (0.340)	0.817 (0.242)
Widowed	1.006 (0.404)	0.759 (0.439)	1.817 (0.993)	1.257 (0.245)	1.534 (0.564)	1.139 (0.260)
Single	0.813 (0.216)	0.878 (0.256)	0.469 (0.379)	0.921 (0.118)	0.707* (0.147)	1.078 (0.177)

Variables	(1) Men	(2) Men among men	(3) Men among women	(4) Women	(5) Women among men	(6) Women among women
Number of children (centered)	0.964 (0.0715)	0.934 (0.0710)	1.055 (0.146)	0.969 (0.0305)	0.966 (0.0602)	0.969 (0.0377)
Religion (<i>ref. cat. Roman-Catholic</i>)						
Protestant	0.653* (0.148)	0.647* (0.159)	0.588 (0.340)	1.177 (0.146)	1.415 (0.323)	1.058 (0.158)
Eastern Orthodox	0.318* (0.212)	0.299 (0.236)	1.096 (1.087)	1.298 (0.622)	2.910* (1.739)	0.580 (0.272)
Other Christian	1.126 (0.481)	0.963 (0.441)	1.852 (1.627)	1.281 (0.362)	1.040 (0.602)	1.276 (0.420)
Jewish	1.001 (0.775)	1.050 (0.829)		0.764 (0.469)	1.494 (1.391)	0.531 (0.396)
Islam	1.382 (0.813)	1.352 (0.917)	1.735 (1.822)	1.105 (0.375)	1.623 (1.086)	0.919 (0.348)
Eastern religions	0.695 (0.508)	0.573 (0.472)	1.938 (2.308)	0.830 (0.378)	1.603 (1.040)	0.489 (0.276)
Other non-Christian	0.203 (0.219)	0.226 (0.251)		0.376* (0.199)	0.255 (0.281)	0.405 (0.302)
No denomination	0.619** (0.145)	0.573** (0.151)	0.739 (0.428)	1.272* (0.171)	1.244 (0.281)	1.266 (0.220)
None	0.880 (0.226)	0.957 (0.256)	0.414 (0.333)	1.098 (0.149)	1.296 (0.312)	0.970 (0.164)
Other				0.685 (0.501)		1.331 (1.102)
Level of religiosity (centered)	1.040 (0.0298)	1.065** (0.0332)	0.929 (0.0638)	0.955*** (0.0151)	0.914*** (0.0266)	0.973 (0.0188)
Employment (<i>ref. cat. >30h. pw</i>)						
<30h. pw	1.251 (0.377)	1.313 (0.528)	1.983 (0.998)	0.947 (0.142)	0.989 (0.341)	0.894 (0.153)
Self-empl.	0.577 (0.213)	0.569 (0.227)	0.355 (0.382)	1.310 (0.295)	1.789* (0.552)	0.974 (0.304)
Military serv.	0.176 (0.212)		3.179 (4.827)	3.077 (2.214)	3.427 (4.295)	4.414* (3.384)
Retired	1.517 (0.469)	1.292 (0.399)	4.029* (3.385)	1.292 (0.228)	1.480 (0.399)	1.047 (0.238)
Housemaker	1.179 (0.519)	0.943 (0.572)	1.704 (1.266)	1.450* (0.308)	2.126 (1.546)	1.401 (0.314)
Student	0.833 (0.409)	0.787 (0.416)	1.754 (2.517)	0.892 (0.217)	0.635 (0.262)	1.030 (0.314)
Unemployed	0.811 (0.415)	0.465 (0.304)	3.402* (2.208)	1.419 (0.312)	1.426 (0.517)	1.431 (0.389)
Disable	0.761 (0.437)	0.747 (0.493)	0.727 (0.888)	1.234 (0.393)	2.136 (1.151)	0.942 (0.368)
Other	0.803 (0.459)	0.524 (0.332)	2.674 (2.817)	1.704** (0.392)	0.614 (0.284)	2.159*** (0.593)

Variables	(1) Men	(2) Men among men	(3) Men among women	(4) Women	(5) Women among men	(6) Women among women
Income satisfaction (<i>ref. cat. Comfortably</i>)						
Coping	1.424** (0.245)	1.492** (0.291)	1.131 (0.385)	1.032 (0.0990)	0.944 (0.151)	1.083 (0.134)
Difficult	2.129*** (0.578)	2.502*** (0.752)	1.112 (0.587)	1.138 (0.165)	1.180 (0.303)	1.121 (0.201)
Very difficult	1.726 (0.766)	2.043 (1.047)	0.674 (0.595)	0.900 (0.210)	0.611 (0.326)	0.959 (0.258)
Personal income (centered)	1.085* (0.0465)	1.066 (0.0533)	1.149* (0.0966)	1.020 (0.0223)	1.045 (0.0395)	1.006 (0.0271)
Household income (centered)	1.022 (0.0434)	1.039 (0.0520)	1.009 (0.0814)	0.964* (0.0202)	0.917** (0.0326)	0.985 (0.0254)
Country (<i>ref. cat. UK</i>)						
Denmark	1.181 (0.299)	1.237 (0.338)	1.070 (0.751)	0.252*** (0.0498)	0.313*** (0.109)	0.240*** (0.0561)
Hungary	0.372*** (0.129)	0.235*** (0.0936)	1.596 (1.299)	0.961 (0.173)	0.872 (0.277)	1.002 (0.227)
Spain	1.755** (0.455)	1.664* (0.461)	2.238 (1.713)	1.231 (0.187)	1.829** (0.458)	0.934 (0.182)
Germany	0.812 (0.190)	0.796 (0.201)	0.776 (0.504)	1.547*** (0.186)	1.529** (0.296)	1.566*** (0.238)
Switzerland	1.187 (0.284)	1.183 (0.309)	0.903 (0.679)	1.480*** (0.216)	1.476 (0.356)	1.489** (0.274)
Male GCI	1.221*** (0.0531)	1.227*** (0.0544)		0.963 (0.0409)	0.966 (0.0424)	
Female GCI	1.139 (0.0964)		1.089 (0.107)	1.178*** (0.0291)		1.187*** (0.0301)
Constant	0.160*** (0.0822)	0.142*** (0.0805)	0.0218*** (0.0271)	0.115*** (0.0327)	0.0995*** (0.0467)	0.217*** (0.0760)
Observations	7,029	3,134	3,854	7,044	3,139	3,899

Standard errors in parentheses
*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

Table A 19. Logit. DV: Issues perceived as a challenge. Overall dataset (1/2)

Variables	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)
	Integrating successfully into the labour market	Accessin g affordab le housing social services and other goods	Balancing paid employme nt and family duties	Caring for children elderly relatives and other dependen ts	Accessi ng good quality healthca re	Getting a good education	Exerc ising my civil rights and freed oms
Vote recall (UNTWIST scheme) (<i>ref. cat. RWPP</i>)							
MR	1.100	1.056	1.221**	1.338***	0.822**	0.929	0.715* **
	(0.123)	(0.105)	(0.121)	(0.132)	(0.0804)	(0.111)	(0.0782)
ML	1.057	1.555***	1.211**	1.369***	0.932	0.915	0.591* **
	(0.110)	(0.145)	(0.115)	(0.129)	(0.0870)	(0.103)	(0.0645)
RL	1.513* **	1.662***	1.217	1.300*	0.867	0.874	0.617* **
	(0.240)	(0.238)	(0.173)	(0.191)	(0.127)	(0.156)	(0.0988)
Other	0.811 (0.127)	1.115 (0.163)	0.999 (0.150)	1.344** (0.197)	1.021 (0.151)	1.065 (0.172)	0.912 (0.145)
Gender (<i>ref. cat. Men</i>)							
Women	0.954 (0.0834)	1.045 (0.0814)	1.279*** (0.0992)	1.143* (0.0867)	1.137* (0.0874)	1.019 (0.0943)	0.620* ** (0.0551)
Age group (<i>ref. cat. 18-24</i>)							
25-39	0.568* ** (0.0891)	1.067 (0.168)	1.389** (0.212)	1.480** (0.256)	1.817*** (0.297)	0.997 (0.181)	0.990 (0.183)
40-54	0.743* (0.121)	0.929 (0.151)	1.106 (0.177)	1.422** (0.256)	3.030*** (0.511)	0.903 (0.170)	1.490* * (0.283)
55-64	0.790 (0.139)	0.904 (0.158)	0.689** (0.120)	1.755*** (0.330)	4.029*** (0.717)	0.642** (0.131)	2.330* ** (0.457)
65+	0.595* * (0.129)	0.826 (0.169)	0.451*** (0.0927)	1.592** (0.341)	5.057*** (1.040)	0.887 (0.202)	3.195* ** (0.719)
Education (<i>ref. cat. ISCED 0-2</i>)							
ISCED 3-4	1.271* (0.157)	1.042 (0.112)	1.298** (0.151)	1.109 (0.119)	0.820* (0.0913)	1.169 (0.145)	1.126 (0.133)

Variables	(1) Integrating successfully into the labour market	(2) Accessin g affordab le housing social services and other goods	(3) Balancing paid employe nt and family duties	(4) Caring for children elderly relatives and other dependen ts	(5) Accessi ng good quality healthca re	(6) Getting a good education	(7) Exerc ising my civil rights and freed oms
ISCED 5-8	1.353* *	1.161	1.399***	1.130	0.901	1.008	1.270* *
	(0.167)	(0.124)	(0.159)	(0.120)	(0.0986)	(0.125)	(0.148)
Social scale self- placement (centered)	0.932* **	0.867***	1.014	0.967	0.889***	1.013	1.006
	(0.0255)	(0.0214)	(0.0246)	(0.0233)	(0.0221)	(0.0306)	(0.0274)
Civil status (<i>ref. cat. Married</i>)							
Civil union	1.221	1.004	0.826	0.824	0.624**	1.409	0.915
	(0.273)	(0.204)	(0.168)	(0.195)	(0.121)	(0.321)	(0.225)
Cohabitati on	1.207	1.291**	1.022	0.939	0.826*	0.945	1.035
	(0.146)	(0.137)	(0.114)	(0.104)	(0.0919)	(0.127)	(0.132)
Divorced	1.166	1.458***	0.770**	0.781**	0.980	0.860	1.010
	(0.161)	(0.167)	(0.0945)	(0.0922)	(0.117)	(0.129)	(0.135)
Separated	0.863	0.733	1.338	0.589**	0.524***	0.623	0.636
	(0.231)	(0.173)	(0.344)	(0.154)	(0.130)	(0.183)	(0.176)
Widowed	1.100	1.585***	0.861	0.725**	0.869	1.157	0.969
	(0.228)	(0.257)	(0.158)	(0.115)	(0.145)	(0.212)	(0.178)
Single	1.240* (0.138)	1.447*** (0.150)	0.610*** (0.0679)	0.683*** (0.0713)	0.871 (0.0920)	0.991 (0.128)	1.210 (0.146)
Number of children (centered)	0.942* (0.0309)	0.913*** (0.0257)	1.111** (0.0556)	1.099*** (0.0290)	0.869*** (0.0241)	1.045 (0.0345)	0.884* (0.0304)
Religion (<i>ref. cat. Roman-Catholic</i>)							
Protestant	0.978 (0.119)	1.040 (0.107)	1.011 (0.105)	1.042 (0.103)	0.800** (0.0830)	0.895 (0.111)	1.061 (0.122)
Eastern Orthodox	1.849 (0.719)	0.798 (0.317)	0.641 (0.214)	0.588 (0.226)	0.917 (0.357)	1.184 (0.471)	1.637 (0.918)
Other Christian	0.873 (0.214)	0.757 (0.176)	1.144 (0.249)	1.112 (0.237)	0.770 (0.160)	0.886 (0.223)	1.427 (0.335)
Jewish	0.296 (0.252)	0.706 (0.387)	0.508 (0.241)	0.919 (0.431)	1.031 (0.456)	1.188 (0.662)	1.189 (0.537)

Variables	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)
	Integrating successfully into the labour market	Accessin g affordab le housing social services and other goods	Balancing paid employe nt and family duties	Caring for children elderly relatives and other dependen ts	Accessi ng good quality healthca re	Getting a good education	Exerc ising my civil rights and freed oms
Islam	1.207 (0.381)	1.526* (0.389)	0.604* (0.176)	0.636 (0.200)	0.875 (0.262)	1.331 (0.407)	1.507 (0.479)
Eastern religions	2.101* (0.747)	0.950 (0.341)	0.599 (0.220)	1.001 (0.310)	0.541* (0.180)	1.035 (0.407)	1.484 (0.568)
Other non- Christian	3.012* (1.508)	4.218*** (1.630)	0.884 (0.367)	0.511 (0.213)	0.559 (0.260)	2.684* (1.381)	1.690 (0.825)
No denominati on	1.086 (0.129)	1.312** (0.143)	1.021 (0.113)	0.945 (0.105)	0.972 (0.107)	1.015 (0.132)	1.304* (0.156)
Other	0.647 (0.396)	1.584 (0.901)	0.876 (0.455)	1.376 (0.772)	0.249** (0.147)	1.002 (0.712)	0.802 (0.491)
None	0.859 (0.113)	1.152 (0.128)	0.778** (0.0872)	0.903 (0.100)	0.953 (0.109)	1.087 (0.147)	1.115 (0.143)
Level of religiosity (centered)	0.980 (0.0147)	0.992 (0.0132)	0.982 (0.0132)	1.010 (0.0125)	0.981 (0.0129)	1.006 (0.0157)	1.023 (0.0148)
Employment (<i>ref. cat. >30h. pw</i>) <30h. pw	1.111 (0.144)	0.749** (0.0890)	0.684*** (0.0809)	1.064 (0.127)	0.764** (0.0919)	1.195 (0.177)	1.116 (0.163)
Self-empl.	0.780 (0.142)	0.611*** (0.105)	0.647*** (0.104)	0.841 (0.134)	1.081 (0.172)	1.229 (0.246)	1.351* (0.238)
Military serv.	0.305 (0.362)	0.127* (0.146)	0.383 (0.266)	1.818 (1.933)	0.771 (0.655)	1.082 (0.841)	1.077 (0.979)
Retired	0.594* (0.0968)	0.825 (0.113)	0.539*** (0.0726)	0.925 (0.124)	1.186 (0.158)	1.371** (0.214)	1.067 (0.153)
Housemak er	0.858 (0.174)	0.482*** (0.0955)	0.666** (0.119)	1.306 (0.242)	0.926 (0.172)	0.839 (0.203)	1.170 (0.254)
Student	1.473* (0.297)	0.834 (0.171)	0.988 (0.199)	0.766 (0.164)	0.992 (0.208)	1.944*** (0.456)	0.940 (0.240)
Unemploy	1.924* (0.174)	0.652** (0.171)	0.685* (0.199)	0.754 (0.164)	0.965 (0.208)	1.510* (0.456)	0.767 (0.240)

Variables	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)
	Integrating successfully into the labour market	Accessin g affordab le housing social services and other goods	Balancing paid employe nt and family duties	Caring for children elderly relatives and other dependen ts	Accessi ng good quality healthca re	Getting a good education	Exerc ising my civil rights and freed oms
ed	**						
Disable	(0.372) 0.835	(0.129) 0.811	(0.139) 0.317***	(0.152) 0.888	(0.192) 1.210	(0.335) 1.052	(0.166) 1.739* *
Other	(0.231) 0.949	(0.206) 0.992	(0.0960) 0.779	(0.216) 1.096	(0.313) 0.937	(0.308) 0.929	(0.490) 0.727
Income satisfaction (<i>ref. cat. Comfortably</i>)	(0.203) 1.152	(0.187) 1.365***	(0.148) 1.226***	(0.202) 0.938	(0.177) 1.052	(0.235) 1.199*	(0.173) 0.966
Coping	(0.103) 1.480* **	(0.104) 1.634***	(0.0946) 1.573***	(0.0708) 1.024	(0.0799) 0.917	(0.111) 1.328**	(0.0831) 1.178
Difficult	(0.188) 1.355	(0.189) 1.385*	(0.192) 1.423*	(0.119) 1.012	(0.107) 1.048	(0.184) 1.104	(0.156) 1.389
Very difficult	(0.285) 0.915* **	(0.268) 0.940***	(0.277) 0.963**	(0.196) 0.996	(0.213) 0.974	(0.259) 1.015	(0.305) 0.997
Personal income (centered)	(0.0183) 1.062* **	(0.0162) 1.002	(0.0167) 1.040**	(0.0171) 1.032*	(0.0166) 1.016	(0.0218) 1.018	(0.0195) 0.998
Household income (centered)	(0.0195) 0.918	(0.0167) 0.668***	(0.0174) 0.872	(0.0179) 1.091	(0.0174) 0.567***	(0.0200) 0.871	(0.0190) 0.899
Country (<i>ref. cat. UK</i>)	(0.137) 2.096* **	(0.0812) 1.010	(0.103) 0.673***	(0.124) 0.695***	(0.0661) 1.007	(0.125) 1.667***	(0.122) 0.863
Denmark	(0.323) 2.183* **	(0.141) 1.448***	(0.0990) 0.960	(0.0961) 0.436***	(0.142) 0.764**	(0.264) 0.977	(0.139) 2.174* **
Hungary	(0.305) 0.866	(0.180) 1.412***	(0.119) 0.911	(0.0546) 0.810**	(0.0944) 0.344***	(0.142) 0.545***	(0.284) 1.092
Spain	(0.107) 1.243	(0.138) 1.130	(0.0893) 0.713***	(0.0775) 0.544***	(0.0340) 0.297***	(0.0689) 0.804	(0.125) 0.891
Germany							
Switzerlan							

Variables	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)
	Integrating successfully into the labour market	Accessin g affordab le housing social services and other goods	Balancing paid employme nt and family duties	Caring for children elderly relatives and other dependen ts	Accessi ng good quality healthca re	Getting a good education	Exerc ising my civil rights and freed oms
d							
Male GCI	(0.180) 0.926* *)	(0.141) 0.959	(0.0887) 0.941**	(0.0676) 0.965	(0.0376) 0.926**	(0.119) 0.996	(0.127) 1.044
Female GCI	(0.0309) 0.983	(0.0296) 0.972	(0.0287) 1.025	(0.0298) 0.975	(0.0294) 0.939***	(0.0363) 0.892***	(0.0341) 1.015
Losers of Feminism	(0.0251) 0.978	(0.0222) 1.222	(0.0233) 0.807	(0.0227) 1.604	(0.0219) 1.574	(0.0289) 1.409	(0.0299) 0.905
Losers of Globalisati on	(0.363) 1.600* *)	(0.402) 1.819***	(0.327) 1.290	(0.495) 1.011	(0.514) 1.349	(0.480) 0.939	(0.304) 1.787* **
Constant	(0.313) 0.234* **)	(0.328) 0.383***	(0.266) 0.669*	(0.192) 0.407***	(0.265) 0.905	(0.229) 0.237***	(0.348) 0.166* **)
Observatio ns	7,038	7,038	7,038	7,038	7,038	7,038	7,038

Standard errors in parentheses
*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

Table A 20. Logit. DV: Issues perceived as a challenge. Overall dataset. (2/2)

Variables	(8) Being able to express my sexual orientation	(9) Being physically safe	(10) Being a good mother/father	(11) Raising and educating children	(12) Forming a family	(13) Gaining the respect of others
Vote recall (UNTWIST scheme) (<i>ref. cat. RWPP</i>)						
MR	0.721 (0.167)	0.794** (0.0788)	1.001 (0.110)	1.058 (0.119)	1.165 (0.165)	0.836 (0.104)
ML	1.571** (0.302)	0.665*** (0.0634)	0.882 (0.0945)	0.987 (0.106)	1.005 (0.140)	0.927 (0.111)
RL	2.008*** (0.528)	0.595*** (0.0957)	0.802 (0.136)	0.714* (0.127)	0.711* (0.146)	0.865 (0.164)
Other	1.424 (0.428)	0.698** (0.107)	0.701* (0.141)	0.753* (0.128)	0.955 (0.194)	1.038 (0.210)
Gender (<i>ref. cat. Men</i>)						
Women	0.670** (0.116)	1.175** (0.0934)	0.803** (0.0728)	0.897 (0.0813)	0.768** (0.0847)	1.032 (0.106)
Age group (<i>ref. cat. 18-24</i>)						
25-39	0.786 (0.191)	1.159 (0.194)	1.443* (0.287)	1.237 (0.223)	1.098 (0.184)	0.720 (0.146)
40-54	0.685 (0.182)	1.435** (0.248)	1.037 (0.218)	0.781 (0.146)	0.374*** (0.0694)	0.725 (0.154)
55-64	0.662 (0.202)	2.009*** (0.365)	0.551*** (0.126)	0.339*** (0.0695)	0.178*** (0.0400)	0.544*** (0.124)
65+	0.347** (0.145)	2.579*** (0.549)	0.552** (0.146)	0.326*** (0.0795)	0.225*** (0.0649)	1.031 (0.268)
Education (<i>ref. cat. ISCED 0-2</i>)						
ISCED 3-4	1.417 (0.348)	0.860 (0.0907)	0.816* (0.100)	0.906 (0.117)	0.703** (0.112)	0.777* (0.106)
ISCED 5-8	1.115 (0.268)	0.898 (0.0930)	0.662*** (0.0787)	1.098 (0.137)	0.693** (0.108)	0.793* (0.107)
Social scale self- placement (centered)	0.973 (0.0458)	1.014 (0.0252)	1.012 (0.0289)	1.000 (0.0292)	0.969 (0.0338)	0.999 (0.0322)
Civil status (<i>ref. cat. Married</i>)						
Civil union	1.317 (0.467)	1.014 (0.249)	0.633* (0.157)	0.899 (0.216)	1.378 (0.331)	0.733 (0.248)
Cohabitation	1.210 (0.249)	1.112 (0.126)	0.676*** (0.0904)	0.566*** (0.0713)	1.410** (0.199)	1.033 (0.144)
Divorced	0.663 (0.221)	1.021 (0.125)	0.718** (0.101)	1.221 (0.172)	0.684 (0.167)	0.732** (0.111)
Separated	0.832 (0.391)	0.876 (0.202)	0.635* (0.160)	0.785 (0.200)	0.604 (0.230)	0.294*** (0.0990)

Variables	(8) Being able to express my sexual orientation	(9) Being physically safe	(10) Being a good mother/father	(11) Raising and educating children	(12) Forming a family	(13) Gaining the respect of others
Widowed	0.762 (0.423)	0.919 (0.145)	0.563** (0.132)	0.727 (0.167)	0.908 (0.312)	0.686* (0.143)
Single	1.472** (0.270)	1.060 (0.115)	0.412*** (0.0618)	0.446*** (0.0566)	1.620*** (0.217)	0.888 (0.121)
Number of children (centered)	0.771*** (0.0599)	0.875*** (0.0280)	1.300*** (0.0924)	1.278*** (0.0415)	0.945 (0.0431)	0.909** (0.0347)
Religion (<i>ref. cat. Roman-Catholic</i>)						
Protestant	0.715 (0.168)	0.795** (0.0829)	1.259* (0.149)	1.064 (0.120)	0.878 (0.133)	1.022 (0.129)
Eastern Orthodox	1.899 (0.971)	0.726 (0.257)	0.309*** (0.140)	0.601 (0.218)	1.639 (0.682)	1.044 (0.516)
Other Christian	0.341*** (0.140)	1.010 (0.233)	1.414 (0.386)	0.620** (0.150)	0.861 (0.260)	0.769 (0.210)
Jewish	0.594 (0.698)	1.316 (0.752)	1.679 (0.981)	2.134 (1.140)	1.323 (1.038)	0.968 (0.700)
Islam	0.384 (0.253)	0.878 (0.254)	0.627 (0.224)	0.926 (0.305)	0.594 (0.236)	0.844 (0.300)
Eastern religions	2.424* (1.195)	0.527* (0.198)	0.759 (0.359)	0.897 (0.359)	1.327 (0.528)	0.996 (0.463)
Other non- Christian	4.586*** (2.690)	0.943 (0.481)	1.527 (0.827)	0.834 (0.472)	1.035 (0.697)	1.417 (0.689)
No denomination	1.199 (0.284)	0.859 (0.0983)	1.066 (0.146)	0.935 (0.119)	0.795 (0.124)	1.028 (0.152)
Other	1.318 (1.302)	0.514 (0.346)	1.044 (0.761)	0.535 (0.386)	0.998 (0.771)	
None	1.159 (0.263)	0.860 (0.0978)	1.240 (0.163)	0.993 (0.127)	0.799 (0.133)	0.987 (0.139)
Level of religiosity (centered)	1.036 (0.0293)	0.984 (0.0130)	1.026 (0.0159)	1.011 (0.0158)	1.022 (0.0194)	1.049*** (0.0175)
Employment (<i>ref. cat. >30h. pw</i>)						
<30h. pw	1.123 (0.266)	0.846 (0.110)	1.108 (0.154)	1.188 (0.160)	0.885 (0.166)	1.346** (0.202)
Self-empl.	0.636 (0.225)	1.105 (0.186)	1.167 (0.219)	1.276 (0.232)	0.925 (0.223)	1.096 (0.257)

Variables	(8) Being able to express my sexual orientation	(9) Being physically safe	(10) Being a good mother/father	(11) Raising and educating children	(12) Forming a family	(13) Gaining the respect of others
Military serv.	1.926 (1.595)	0.398 (0.284)	0.149* (0.169)	0.216 (0.212)	0.277* (0.205)	1.938 (1.622)
Retired	1.038 (0.347)	1.227 (0.171)	1.142 (0.182)	1.067 (0.179)	1.017 (0.240)	0.989 (0.167)
Housemaker	1.134 (0.472)	0.893 (0.174)	1.185 (0.254)	1.224 (0.252)	1.229 (0.331)	1.142 (0.275)
Student	0.869 (0.286)	1.344 (0.272)	1.181 (0.300)	1.579* (0.385)	1.516* (0.340)	0.954 (0.250)
Unemployed	0.765 (0.261)	0.623** (0.136)	0.992 (0.230)	1.284 (0.274)	0.558** (0.156)	1.134 (0.289)
Disable	0.736 (0.338)	1.085 (0.265)	1.024 (0.333)	1.280 (0.351)	0.890 (0.305)	1.141 (0.356)
Other	0.641 (0.324)	1.419* (0.273)	0.737 (0.173)	1.186 (0.258)	0.595 (0.193)	0.904 (0.223)
Income satisfaction (<i>ref. cat. Comfortably</i>)						
Coping	0.831 (0.142)	1.062 (0.0839)	1.080 (0.0969)	1.124 (0.0987)	0.922 (0.0995)	1.122 (0.110)
Difficult	1.071 (0.271)	1.169 (0.143)	0.904 (0.129)	1.193 (0.161)	1.179 (0.186)	1.114 (0.171)
Very difficult	1.565 (0.534)	1.490** (0.291)	1.032 (0.247)	1.476* (0.341)	0.708 (0.217)	1.284 (0.319)
Personal income (centered)	1.020 (0.0386)	0.999 (0.0173)	1.022 (0.0199)	0.991 (0.0193)	1.060** (0.0282)	1.042* (0.0229)
Household income (centered)	1.019 (0.0335)	1.003 (0.0174)	0.994 (0.0198)	1.070*** (0.0206)	0.990 (0.0234)	0.955** (0.0213)
Country (<i>ref. cat. UK</i>)						
Denmark	0.999 (0.275)	0.374*** (0.0453)	1.434*** (0.184)	0.714** (0.0993)	2.042*** (0.361)	1.324** (0.187)
Hungary	0.773 (0.231)	0.320*** (0.0465)	0.531*** (0.0908)	1.023 (0.158)	1.884*** (0.392)	0.702* (0.130)
Spain	1.147 (0.285)	0.420*** (0.0522)	0.635*** (0.0951)	0.876 (0.122)	2.115*** (0.378)	0.774 (0.125)
Germany	0.950 (0.199)	0.446*** (0.0444)	0.808* (0.0919)	0.830* (0.0916)	1.231 (0.182)	1.290** (0.164)
Switzerland	1.274 (0.323)	0.389*** (0.0473)	0.888 (0.124)	0.700** (0.0987)	1.068 (0.200)	1.272 (0.188)
Male GCI	1.046 (0.0507)	0.977 (0.0316)	1.007 (0.0331)	0.905*** (0.0307)	0.986 (0.0378)	1.042 (0.0393)
Female GCI	1.120**	1.024	1.055**	1.006	0.996	1.082***

Variables	(8) Being able to express my sexual orientation	(9) Being physically safe	(10) Being a good mother/father	(11) Raising and educating children	(12) Forming a family	(13) Gaining the respect of others
Losers of Feminism	(0.0517) 0.256	(0.0241) 1.778*	(0.0285) 1.953	(0.0255) 1.347	(0.0360) 1.956*	(0.0316) 0.841
Losers of Globalisation	(0.267) 1.468	(0.611) 1.777***	(0.809) 1.186	(0.534) 0.992	(0.716) 1.318	(0.359) 0.630
Constant	(0.586) 0.0511*** (0.0241)	(0.345) 0.753 (0.177)	(0.256) 0.576** (0.156)	(0.227) 0.576** (0.149)	(0.366) 0.335*** (0.0984)	(0.188) 0.256*** (0.0751)
Observations	7,038	7,038	7,038	7,038	7,038	7,023

Standard errors in parentheses
*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

Table A 21. Logit. DV: Issues perceived as a challenge – Men (1/2)

Variables	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)
	Integrating successfully into the labour market	Accessing affordable housing social services and other goods	Balancing paid employment and family duties	Caring for children elderly relatives and other dependents	Accessing good quality healthcare	Getting a good education	Exercising my civil rights and freedoms
<i>Vote recall (UNTWIST scheme) (ref. cat. RWPP)</i>							
MR	1.057 (0.171)	1.112 (0.156)	1.224 (0.175)	1.427*** (0.196)	0.798 (0.111)	0.895 (0.149)	0.843 (0.123)
ML	1.152 (0.180)	1.640** (0.222) *	1.225 (0.172)	1.413*** (0.189)	0.910 (0.123)	0.880 (0.137)	0.607*** (0.0896)
RL	1.327 (0.319)	1.875** (0.404) *	1.136 (0.241)	1.081 (0.241)	0.877 (0.188)	1.096 (0.259)	0.740 (0.165)
Other	0.825 (0.198)	1.279 (0.265)	0.811 (0.182)	1.148 (0.245)	1.155 (0.253)	1.044 (0.239)	0.973 (0.205)
<i>Age group (ref. cat. 18-24)</i>							
25-39	0.573** (0.133)	1.108 (0.260)	1.330 (0.311)	1.193 (0.317)	2.340** (0.604) *	1.767** (0.513)	1.038 (0.287)
40-54	0.688 (0.169)	0.893 (0.216)	0.909 (0.221)	1.017 (0.284)	3.447** (0.923) *	1.406 (0.437)	1.751* (0.502)
55-64	0.734 (0.196)	0.971 (0.249)	0.546** (0.140)	1.264 (0.368)	4.818** (1.339) *	1.218 (0.394)	2.727*** (0.801)
65+	0.747 (0.245)	0.902 (0.275)	0.514** (0.157)	0.949 (0.311)	5.257** (1.635) *	1.747 (0.618)	3.573*** (1.175)
<i>Education (ref. cat. ISCED 0-2)</i>							
ISCED 3-4	1.066 (0.185)	0.919 (0.148)	1.342* (0.231)	1.124 (0.178)	0.910 (0.149)	1.200 (0.216)	1.210 (0.199)
ISCED 5-8	1.127 (0.193)	1.164 (0.184)	1.291 (0.218)	1.095 (0.172)	0.988 (0.158)	0.936 (0.170)	1.380** (0.224)
Social scale self- placement (centered)	0.958 (0.0402)	0.859** (0.0319) *	0.997 (0.0363)	0.967 (0.0354)	0.885** (0.0320) *	1.013 (0.0439)	1.002 (0.0367)
<i>Civil status (ref. cat. Married)</i>							
Civil union	1.229	0.882	1.028	0.649	0.433**	1.725*	1.060

Variables	(1) Integrating successfully into the labour market	(2) Accessing affordable housing social services and other goods	(3) Balancing paid employment and family duties	(4) Caring for children elderly relatives and other dependents	(5) Accessing good quality healthcare	(6) Getting a good education	(7) Exercising my civil rights and freedoms
					*		
Cohabitation	(0.431) 1.226	(0.275) 1.231	(0.315) 0.882	(0.258) 1.048	(0.128) 0.767	(0.555) 0.958	(0.404) 1.040
Divorced	(0.220) 0.869	(0.194) 1.396*	(0.145) 0.666**	(0.173) 0.898	(0.125) 0.809	(0.187) 0.912	(0.187) 1.004
Separated	(0.205) 0.881	(0.251) 0.899	(0.134) 1.325	(0.161) 1.372	(0.152) 0.627	(0.207) 0.459	(0.192) 0.745
Widowed	(0.351) 1.193	(0.293) 1.297	(0.544) 0.676	(0.501) 0.930	(0.232) 0.687	(0.219) 1.043	(0.271) 0.886
Single	(0.444) 1.502**	(0.409) 1.337*	(0.251) 0.478***	(0.259) 0.712**	(0.209) 0.894	(0.327) 0.925	(0.276) 1.177
Number of children (centered)	(0.244) 0.912*	(0.202) 0.914**	(0.0744) 1.141***	(0.112) 1.158***	(0.138) 0.869**	(0.173) 1.012	(0.191) 0.877***
					*		
Religion (<i>ref. cat. Roman-Catholic</i>)	(0.0454)	(0.0394)	(0.0465)	(0.0479)	(0.0360)	(0.0469)	(0.0388)
Protestant	0.916 (0.166)	1.055 (0.162)	1.003 (0.158)	0.983 (0.142)	0.811 (0.126)	0.836 (0.156)	0.969 (0.156)
Eastern Orthodox	2.491* (1.348)	1.076 (0.524)	0.745 (0.332)	0.567 (0.307)	1.247 (0.650)	1.013 (0.582)	1.073 (0.812)
Other Christian	0.904 (0.345)	0.923 (0.299)	1.011 (0.316)	1.130 (0.376)	0.599 (0.188)	0.537 (0.228)	1.363 (0.464)
Jewish	0.130 (0.163)	0.849 (0.569)	0.409 (0.256)	0.446 (0.265)	0.814 (0.456)	1.292 (1.024)	2.238 (1.138)
Islam	0.960 (0.479)	1.564 (0.574)	0.463* (0.208)	0.817 (0.424)	1.017 (0.458)	1.111 (0.494)	1.287 (0.574)
Eastern religions	1.693 (0.900)	0.641 (0.303)	0.653 (0.343)	0.600 (0.270)	0.591 (0.254)	1.401 (0.661)	1.591 (0.813)
Other non- Christian	1.798 (1.365)	5.621** (2.642)	0.678 (0.368)	0.280** (0.158)	0.620 (0.395)	2.325 (1.558)	3.405** (2.039)
No denomination	1.156 (1.365)	1.416** (2.642)	1.092 (0.368)	1.083 (0.158)	0.989 (0.395)	1.204 (1.558)	1.289 (2.039)

Variables	(1) Integrating successfully into the labour market	(2) Accessing affordable housing social services and other goods	(3) Balancing paid employment and family duties	(4) Caring for children elderly relatives and other dependents	(5) Accessing good quality healthcare	(6) Getting a good education	(7) Exercising my civil rights and freedoms
Other	(0.202) 0.334 (0.395)	(0.226) 0.131* (0.161)	(0.177) 0.266 (0.281)	(0.175) 0.470 (0.537)	(0.157) 0.305 (0.267)	(0.221) 0.711 (0.801)	(0.211) 2.020 (1.750)
None	0.798 (0.156)	1.232 (0.197)	0.804 (0.132)	1.077 (0.172)	1.045 (0.174)	1.066 (0.207)	1.119 (0.197)
Level of religiosity (centered)	0.999 (0.0222)	0.988 (0.0198)	0.978 (0.0190)	1.021 (0.0185)	1.004 (0.0192)	1.013 (0.0223)	1.035* (0.0206)
Employment (<i>ref. cat. >30h. pw</i>) <30h. pw	1.078 (0.267)	0.493** (0.116) *	0.536*** (0.128)	1.047 (0.249)	0.916 (0.211)	1.235 (0.342)	1.451 (0.362)
Self-empl.	0.806 (0.192)	0.474** (0.107) *	0.731 (0.151)	1.001 (0.217)	1.279 (0.265)	1.022 (0.274)	1.364 (0.299)
Military serv.	0.909 (1.194)		0.635 (0.515)			1.355 (1.615)	1.791 (1.819)
Retired	0.583** (0.137)	0.584** (0.116)	0.385*** (0.0775)	1.280 (0.240)	1.358* (0.250)	1.187 (0.252)	1.136 (0.222)
Housemake r	2.162 (1.204)	0.579 (0.325)	0.839 (0.391)	0.994 (0.547)	1.002 (0.572)		
Student	1.261 (0.366)	0.814 (0.261)	1.044 (0.306)	0.606 (0.198)	1.001 (0.323)	3.056** (1.061) *	0.917 (0.325)
Unemploye d	1.522 (0.474)	0.525** (0.164)	0.948 (0.290)	1.119 (0.337)	0.993 (0.337)	1.940* (0.664)	0.963 (0.296)
Disable	0.907 (0.396)	0.902 (0.383)	0.268*** (0.132)	0.385** (0.165)	1.471 (0.657)	1.550 (0.668)	0.867 (0.360)
Other	0.624 (0.225)	0.887 (0.287)	0.861 (0.284)	1.525 (0.446)	1.139 (0.325)	1.066 (0.397)	1.128 (0.362)
Income satisfaction (<i>ref. cat. Comfortably</i>) Coping	1.380** (0.177)	1.208* (0.132)	1.180 (0.133)	1.020 (0.112)	0.926 (0.102)	1.017 (0.131)	0.950 (0.109)
Difficult	1.649**	1.577**	1.634***	1.303	0.895	1.134	1.053

Variables	(1) Integrating successfully into the labour market	(2) Accessing affordable housing social services and other goods	(3) Balancing paid employment and family duties	(4) Caring for children elderly relatives and other dependents	(5) Accessing good quality healthcare	(6) Getting a good education	(7) Exercising my civil rights and freedoms
	(0.328)	(0.270)	(0.307)	(0.230)	(0.161)	(0.235)	(0.196)
Very difficult	1.343	1.255	1.723*	1.189	1.022	0.770	1.568
Personal income (centered)	0.912***	0.931** *	0.969	1.004	0.957	1.010	0.999
Household income (centered)	(0.0279) 1.093***	(0.0250) 1.001	(0.0262) 1.032	(0.0278) 1.047*	(0.0261) 1.032	(0.0323) 1.029	(0.0295) 0.984
Country (<i>ref. cat. UK</i>)	(0.0308)	(0.0255)	(0.0274)	(0.0287)	(0.0285)	(0.0300)	(0.0280)
Denmark	0.800	0.650**	0.880	1.047	0.589** *	0.841	0.924
Hungary	(0.168) 1.271	(0.115) 1.021	(0.151) 0.719	(0.173) 0.665**	(0.0966) 1.007	(0.166) 1.447*	(0.167) 0.933
Spain	(0.285) 1.555**	(0.201) 1.463**	(0.157) 0.952	(0.133) 0.388***	(0.213) 0.749	(0.321) 0.783	(0.199) 1.874***
Germany	(0.311) 0.777	(0.262) 1.243	(0.171) 0.832	(0.0725) 0.867	(0.132) 0.327** *	(0.164) 0.472** *	(0.341) 1.086
Switzerland	(0.136) 0.880	(0.172) 1.102	(0.119) 0.812	(0.118) 0.464***	(0.0463) 0.300** *	(0.0840) 0.697*	(0.166) 0.826
Male GCI	(0.186) 0.921**	(0.199) 0.950	(0.150) 0.939**	(0.0853) 0.972	(0.0551) 0.927**	(0.152) 1.007	(0.164) 1.040
Female GCI	(0.0312) 0.855	(0.0298) 0.795	(0.0293) 0.583**	(0.0311) 0.850	(0.0300) 0.757	(0.0373) 0.828	(0.0352) 1.816**
Losers of Feminism	(0.169) 1.624	(0.134) 0.804	(0.132) 0.788	(0.163) 1.334	(0.193) 1.111	(0.220) 1.422	(0.461) 1.402
Losers of Globalisation	(0.697) 1.918**	(0.352) 2.415** *	(0.356) 1.206	(0.572) 1.108	(0.476) 1.342	(0.594) 0.553*	(0.570) 2.172***
Constant	(0.517) 0.300***	(0.607) 0.466**	(0.390) 0.866	(0.274) 0.442**	(0.375) 0.759	(0.199) 0.182**	(0.572) 0.132***

Variables	(1) Integrating successfully into the labour market	(2) Accessing affordable housing social services and other goods	(3) Balancing paid employment and family duties	(4) Caring for children elderly relatives and other dependents	(5) Accessing good quality healthcare	(6) Getting a good education	(7) Exercising my civil rights and freedoms
	(0.109)	(0.158)	(0.295)	(0.161)	(0.269)	(0.0738)	(0.0487)
Observations	3,144	3,139	3,144	3,139	3,139	3,124	3,124

Standard errors in parentheses
 *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

Table A 22. Logit. DV: Issues perceived as a challenge – Men (2/2)

Variables	(8) Being able to express my sexual orientation	(9) Being physically safe	(10) Being a good mother/father	(11) Raising and educating children	(12) Forming a family	(13) Gaining the respect of others
Vote recall (UNTWIST scheme) (<i>ref. cat. RWPP</i>)						
MR	0.651 (0.211)	0.890 (0.123)	0.984 (0.146)	1.048 (0.167)	0.871 (0.168)	0.796 (0.145)
ML	1.659* (0.451)	0.673*** (0.0926)	0.850 (0.127)	0.984 (0.152)	0.951 (0.179)	0.869 (0.155)
RL	1.905* (0.663)	0.766 (0.181)	1.052 (0.253)	0.710 (0.182)	0.809 (0.222)	0.878 (0.252)
Other	1.923 (0.776)	0.752 (0.172)	0.702 (0.212)	0.645* (0.172)	0.790 (0.241)	1.174 (0.344)
Age group (<i>ref. cat. 18-24</i>)						
25-39	0.913 (0.310)	1.350 (0.365)	1.392 (0.419)	1.186 (0.350)	0.985 (0.258)	0.942 (0.274)
40-54	1.050 (0.400)	1.858** (0.529)	1.153 (0.361)	0.762 (0.236)	0.398*** (0.114)	1.620 (0.489)
55-64	1.197 (0.520)	2.396*** (0.715)	0.642 (0.208)	0.385*** (0.124)	0.225*** (0.0731)	0.950 (0.314)
65+	0.595 (0.329)	2.834*** (0.965)	0.630 (0.227)	0.369*** (0.135)	0.291*** (0.125)	2.080* (0.781)
Education (<i>ref. cat. ISCED 0-2</i>)						
ISCED 3-4	1.457 (0.508)	1.094 (0.170)	0.759 (0.131)	0.936 (0.172)	0.822 (0.185)	0.777 (0.158)
ISCED 5-8	1.427 (0.488)	1.031 (0.157)	0.596*** (0.103)	1.096 (0.197)	0.765 (0.169)	0.884 (0.174)
Social scale self- placement (centered)	0.933 (0.0579)	1.028 (0.0386)	1.048 (0.0457)	0.975 (0.0421)	0.963 (0.0484)	0.957 (0.0453)
Civil status (<i>ref. cat. Married</i>)						
Civil union	2.281* (1.115)	0.526 (0.260)	0.809 (0.289)	0.801 (0.298)	1.881* (0.680)	0.906 (0.424)
Cohabitation	1.542 (0.433)	1.120 (0.191)	0.759 (0.141)	0.584*** (0.113)	1.674** (0.349)	1.027 (0.217)
Divorced	1.107 (0.493)	0.947 (0.189)	0.856 (0.181)	2.056*** (0.412)	1.240 (0.391)	0.717 (0.176)
Separated	1.626 (0.849)	0.764 (0.264)	0.668 (0.239)	0.810 (0.312)	0.553 (0.329)	0.310** (0.159)
Widowed	0.955 (0.799)	0.730 (0.209)	0.508 (0.239)	0.691 (0.303)	0.455 (0.331)	0.542 (0.211)
Single	1.773** (0.455)	1.143 (0.182)	0.354*** (0.0753)	0.334*** (0.0648)	2.024*** (0.401)	1.012 (0.203)
Number of	0.663***	0.963	1.351***	1.207***	0.922	0.881**

Variables	(8) Being able to express my sexual orientation	(9) Being physically safe	(10) Being a good mother/father	(11) Raising and educating children	(12) Forming a family	(13) Gaining the respect of others
children (centered)						
	(0.0684)	(0.0416)	(0.0615)	(0.0528)	(0.0754)	(0.0500)
Religion (<i>ref. cat. Roman-Catholic</i>)						
Protestant	0.815 (0.264)	0.755* (0.117)	1.231 (0.212)	1.141 (0.189)	0.880 (0.194)	1.080 (0.209)
Eastern Orthodox	2.769 (2.851)	0.537 (0.275)	0.217** (0.143)	0.555 (0.301)	1.365 (0.927)	0.674 (0.599)
Other Christian	0.145* (0.153)	1.260 (0.449)	1.012 (0.417)	0.705 (0.251)	1.052 (0.489)	0.918 (0.386)
Jewish	1.482 (1.901)	2.330 (1.556)	1.064 (0.690)	2.929 (2.115)	1.297 (1.255)	0.267 (0.298)
Islam	0.432 (0.343)	0.671 (0.285)	0.417* (0.216)	0.417* (0.194)	0.667 (0.422)	0.566 (0.299)
Eastern religions	3.117* (2.038)	1.125 (0.459)	0.162** (0.126)	0.731 (0.401)	1.641 (0.805)	0.594 (0.408)
Other non- Christian	4.258** (3.088)	1.534 (1.005)	1.314 (0.695)	1.295 (0.871)	2.135 (1.674)	1.209 (0.915)
No denomination	1.027 (0.325)	0.738* (0.122)	1.166 (0.227)	1.065 (0.200)	0.747 (0.170)	1.272 (0.267)
Other	2.840 (2.798)					
None	1.293 (0.379)	0.764* (0.123)	1.341 (0.254)	0.924 (0.175)	0.691 (0.166)	1.049 (0.219)
Level of religiosity (centered)	1.027 (0.0419)	0.988 (0.0188)	1.047** (0.0222)	1.008 (0.0227)	0.985 (0.0267)	1.071*** (0.0256)
Employment (<i>ref. cat. >30h. pw</i>)						
<30h. pw	1.199 (0.415)	0.815 (0.208)	0.967 (0.269)	1.321 (0.348)	0.733 (0.246)	1.426 (0.408)
Self-empl.	0.754 (0.331)	1.154 (0.249)	1.017 (0.244)	1.138 (0.274)	0.637 (0.237)	1.084 (0.332)
Military serv.			0.223 (0.374)	0.565 (0.674)		
Retired	1.029 (0.421)	1.244 (0.242)	1.071 (0.222)	1.047 (0.231)	0.984 (0.328)	1.068 (0.261)
Housemaker	0.324 (0.449)	0.178** (0.151)	0.662 (0.439)	1.286 (0.708)	0.424 (0.305)	0.917 (0.677)
Student	0.467* (0.0419)	1.097 (0.0188)	2.140** (0.0222)	2.363** (0.0227)	2.599*** (0.0267)	1.698 (0.0256)

Variables	(8) Being able to express my sexual orientation	(9) Being physically safe	(10) Being a good mother/father	(11) Raising and educating children	(12) Forming a family	(13) Gaining the respect of others
Unemployed	(0.215) 0.382*	(0.335) 0.714	(0.756) 0.788	(0.862) 1.498	(0.878) 0.565	(0.613) 0.913
Disable	(0.196) 0.314	(0.237) 1.362	(0.301) 1.541	(0.512) 1.449	(0.241) 1.448	(0.354) 1.019
Other	(0.255) 0.610 (0.399)	(0.527) 2.640*** (0.783)	(0.681) 0.332** (0.144)	(0.648) 0.819 (0.301)	(0.745) 0.465* (0.215)	(0.566) 0.896 (0.378)
Income satisfaction (<i>ref. cat. Comfortably</i>)						
Coping	0.711 (0.153)	1.008 (0.114)	1.143 (0.142)	1.113 (0.141)	0.884 (0.136)	1.116 (0.152)
Difficult	1.270 (0.394)	1.111 (0.207)	0.823 (0.184)	1.391 (0.282)	1.358 (0.314)	1.160 (0.268)
Very difficult	0.818 (0.413)	1.089 (0.365)	1.378 (0.507)	1.301 (0.471)	0.844 (0.385)	1.449 (0.534)
Personal income (centered)	0.983 (0.0523)	0.977 (0.0277)	1.037 (0.0328)	1.001 (0.0328)	1.098** (0.0437)	1.044 (0.0371)
Household income (centered)	1.006 (0.0464)	0.994 (0.0273)	1.006 (0.0312)	1.075** (0.0338)	0.999 (0.0336)	0.962 (0.0326)
Country (<i>ref. cat. UK</i>)						
Denmark	1.565 (0.569)	0.353*** (0.0622)	1.397* (0.251)	0.741 (0.143)	2.277*** (0.545)	1.566** (0.319)
Hungary	0.597 (0.266)	0.333*** (0.0719)	0.610* (0.154)	0.923 (0.209)	2.467*** (0.736)	0.719 (0.199)
Spain	1.963** (0.639)	0.494*** (0.0883)	0.746 (0.159)	0.836 (0.168)	2.258*** (0.558)	1.013 (0.240)
Germany	1.186 (0.320)	0.517*** (0.0742)	0.884 (0.143)	0.745* (0.118)	1.246 (0.255)	1.657*** (0.308)
Switzerland	1.167 (0.419)	0.442*** (0.0782)	1.172 (0.224)	0.649** (0.132)	1.047 (0.281)	1.322 (0.295)
Male GCI	1.067 (0.0542)	0.983 (0.0320)	1.013 (0.0343)	0.923** (0.0321)	1.003 (0.0388)	1.075* (0.0417)
Female GCI	2.106*** (0.445)	1.117 (0.242)	0.784 (0.224)	0.944 (0.199)	1.275 (0.266)	1.314 (0.275)
Losers of Feminism	0.320 (0.409)	2.103* (0.829)	1.537 (0.689)	1.545 (0.744)	1.489 (0.762)	0.704 (0.360)
Losers of Globalisation	0.336 (0.251)	2.214*** (0.587)	1.093 (0.287)	0.739 (0.243)	1.272 (0.467)	0.668 (0.287)
Constant	0.0221*** (0.0142)	0.535* (0.198)	0.498* (0.201)	0.564 (0.229)	0.255*** (0.109)	0.105*** (0.0435)

Variables	(8) Being able to express my sexual orientation	(9) Being physically safe	(10) Being a good mother/father	(11) Raising and educating children	(12) Forming a family	(13) Gaining the respect of others
Observations	3,139	3,133	3,138	3,138	3,133	3,133

Standard errors in parentheses
 *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

Table A 23. Logit. DV: Issues perceived as a challenge – Women (1/2)

Variables	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)
	Integrating successfully into the labour market	Accessing affordable housing social services and other goods	Balancing paid employment and family duties	Caring for children elderly relatives and other dependents	Accessing good quality healthcare	Getting a good education	Exercising my civil rights and freedoms
Vote recall (UNTWIST scheme) (<i>ref. cat. RWPP</i>)							
MR	1.209 (0.189)	0.997 (0.142)	1.211 (0.169)	1.246 (0.181)	0.853 (0.118)	1.000 (0.173)	0.561*** (0.0941)
ML	1.045 (0.152)	1.517** (0.199) *	1.196 (0.159)	1.314** (0.180)	0.952 (0.123)	0.981 (0.161)	0.531*** (0.0856)
RL	1.899*** (0.403)	1.477** (0.288)	1.321 (0.261)	1.382 (0.276)	0.848 (0.170)	0.730 (0.209)	0.485*** (0.114)
Other	0.847 (0.180)	1.023 (0.210)	1.199 (0.244)	1.502** (0.299)	0.916 (0.186)	1.124 (0.266)	0.763 (0.184)
Age group (<i>ref. cat. 18-24</i>)							
25-39	0.555*** (0.116)	0.988 (0.207)	1.432* (0.287)	1.891*** (0.409)	1.496* (0.312)	0.544** (0.120) *	0.885 (0.222)
40-54	0.816 (0.178)	0.874 (0.192)	1.232 (0.261)	1.984*** (0.443)	2.875** (0.625) *	0.558** (0.130)	1.251 (0.317)
55-64	0.897 (0.211)	0.790 (0.187)	0.763 (0.178)	2.430*** (0.573)	3.592** (0.841) *	0.306** (0.0807) *	1.930** (0.518)
65+	0.545** (0.163)	0.679 (0.188)	0.346*** (0.0955)	2.532*** (0.708)	5.088** (1.439) *	0.426** (0.131) *	2.663*** (0.836)
Education (<i>ref. cat. ISCED 0-2</i>)							
ISCED 3-4	1.508** (0.258)	1.163 (0.170)	1.273 (0.200)	1.093 (0.160)	0.716** (0.109)	1.201 (0.210)	1.079 (0.181)
ISCED 5-8	1.665*** (0.284)	1.176 (0.172)	1.483** (0.228)	1.176 (0.170)	0.797 (0.121)	1.160 (0.200)	1.155 (0.190)
Social scale self- placement (centered)	0.905*** (0.0332)	0.869** (0.0294) *	1.034 (0.0333)	0.963 (0.0312)	0.887** (0.0306) *	1.009 (0.0433)	1.009 (0.0417)
Civil status (<i>ref. cat. Married</i>)							
Civil union	1.146 (0.323)	1.137 (0.294)	0.686 (0.179)	1.021 (0.287)	0.879 (0.222)	1.310 (0.426)	0.795 (0.237)

Variables	(1) Integrating successfully into the labour market	(2) Accessing affordable housing social services and other goods	(3) Balancing paid employment and family duties	(4) Caring for children elderly relatives and other dependents	(5) Accessing good quality healthcare	(6) Getting a good education	(7) Exercising my civil rights and freedoms
Cohabitation	1.207 (0.192)	1.398** (0.200)	1.139 (0.169)	0.863 (0.126)	0.892 (0.135)	0.862 (0.160)	1.045 (0.187)
Divorced	1.384* (0.249)	1.560** (0.237)	0.877 (0.140)	0.687** (0.109)	1.096 (0.171)	0.803 (0.167)	0.963 (0.182)
Separated	0.861 (0.333)	0.599 (0.188)	1.311 (0.424)	0.241*** (0.0799)	0.442** (0.150)	0.813 (0.298)	0.489* (0.209)
Widowed	1.033 (0.265)	1.688** (0.334)	1.012 (0.219)	0.640** (0.126)	0.970 (0.194)	1.141 (0.273)	1.069 (0.236)
Single	1.051 (0.164)	1.604** (0.233)	0.741** (0.111)	0.665*** (0.0945)	0.840 (0.121)	0.994 (0.178)	1.246 (0.220)
Number of children (centered)	0.967 (0.0405)	0.906** (0.0351)	1.087 (0.0787)	1.057* (0.0330)	0.868** (0.0333)	1.082** (0.0410)	0.872** (0.0474)
Religion (<i>ref. cat. Roman-Catholic</i>)							
Protestant	1.008 (0.168)	1.026 (0.143)	1.020 (0.141)	1.137 (0.154)	0.784* (0.110)	0.947 (0.159)	1.222 (0.206)
Eastern Orthodox	1.306 (0.607)	0.575 (0.338)	0.551 (0.279)	0.588 (0.332)	0.514 (0.277)	1.733 (0.864)	2.331 (1.446)
Other Christian	0.772 (0.247)	0.611 (0.204)	1.225 (0.365)	1.121 (0.323)	0.844 (0.233)	1.218 (0.377)	1.778* (0.570)
Jewish	0.924 (0.946)	0.452 (0.413)	0.675 (0.466)	2.047 (1.512)	1.463 (0.984)	0.788 (0.695)	0.139* (0.153)
Islam	1.859 (0.717)	1.331 (0.463)	0.718 (0.275)	0.452** (0.169)	0.666 (0.271)	1.479 (0.596)	1.989 (0.918)
Eastern religions	2.798** (1.358)	1.452 (0.723)	0.571 (0.291)	1.610 (0.704)	0.427 (0.225)	0.669 (0.500)	1.777 (1.002)
Other non- Christian	6.092** (4.884)	3.389* (2.268)	1.350 (0.791)	0.955 (0.523)	0.395 (0.261)	2.737 (1.965)	0.182** (0.146)
No denomination	1.053 (4.884)	1.214 (2.268)	0.911 (0.791)	0.861 (0.523)	0.964 (0.261)	0.786 (1.965)	1.349* (0.146)

Variables	(1) Integrating successfully into the labour market	(2) Accessing affordable housing social services and other goods	(3) Balancing paid employment and family duties	(4) Caring for children elderly relatives and other dependents	(5) Accessing good quality healthcare	(6) Getting a good education	(7) Exercising my civil rights and freedoms
on	(0.168)	(0.183)	(0.137)	(0.135)	(0.148)	(0.144)	(0.235)
Other	0.784	10.15**	1.268	2.442	0.211*	1.115	0.307
None	(0.605)	(11.20)	(0.882)	(1.688)	(0.176)	(0.954)	(0.341)
Level of religiosity (centered)	0.876	1.081	0.733**	0.768*	0.860	1.070	1.220
	(0.158)	(0.169)	(0.113)	(0.119)	(0.137)	(0.211)	(0.228)
	0.964*	0.993	0.979	1.000	0.961**	0.999	1.014
Employment (<i>ref. cat. >30h. pw</i>)	(0.0196)	(0.0179)	(0.0177)	(0.0173)	(0.0175)	(0.0217)	(0.0213)
<30h. pw	1.095	0.943	0.754**	1.040	0.714**	1.191	0.942
Self-empl.	(0.173)	(0.136)	(0.105)	(0.149)	(0.104)	(0.217)	(0.175)
omitted	0.801	0.777	0.559**	0.668	0.876	1.831**	1.347
	(0.223)	(0.211)	(0.140)	(0.164)	(0.218)	(0.532)	(0.387)
Retired	-						
	0.523***	1.245	0.784	0.672**	1.037	1.729**	1.029
	(0.121)	(0.242)	(0.149)	(0.132)	(0.206)	(0.413)	(0.223)
Military serv.		0.308	0.134**	19.06**	2.809	0.582	0.207
		(0.493)	(0.125)	(24.46)	(2.991)	(0.582)	(0.259)
Housemaker	0.742	0.557**	0.708*	1.219	0.855	0.952	1.252
		*					
	(0.168)	(0.118)	(0.139)	(0.245)	(0.173)	(0.245)	(0.291)
Student	1.668*	0.836	0.960	0.948	1.025	1.288	0.850
	(0.475)	(0.226)	(0.259)	(0.263)	(0.278)	(0.403)	(0.303)
Unemployed	2.291***	0.823	0.541**	0.516**	0.865	1.089	0.602*
	(0.585)	(0.208)	(0.142)	(0.139)	(0.197)	(0.317)	(0.180)
Disable	0.770	0.842	0.357***	1.202	1.025	0.821	2.524***
	(0.279)	(0.263)	(0.134)	(0.369)	(0.329)	(0.334)	(0.885)
Other	1.071	1.115	0.764	0.930	0.844	0.755	0.367**
	(0.287)	(0.260)	(0.172)	(0.224)	(0.221)	(0.282)	(0.149)
Income satisfaction (<i>ref. cat. Comfortably</i>)							
Coping	0.947	1.550**	1.266**	0.856	1.185	1.550**	1.004
		*				*	
	(0.120)	(0.166)	(0.134)	(0.0914)	(0.126)	(0.214)	(0.132)
Difficult	1.353*	1.757**	1.504**	0.847	0.938	1.637**	1.296

Variables	(1) Integrating successfully into the labour market	(2) Accessing affordable housing social services and other goods	(3) Balancing paid employment and family duties	(4) Caring for children elderly relatives and other dependents	(5) Accessing good quality healthcare	(6) Getting a good education	(7) Exercising my civil rights and freedoms
	(0.229)	(0.276)	(0.242)	(0.132)	(0.147)	(0.315)	(0.242)
Very difficult	1.316	1.507*	1.261	0.935	1.075	1.487	1.394
	(0.344)	(0.374)	(0.312)	(0.226)	(0.283)	(0.440)	(0.431)
Personal income (centered)	0.899***	0.945**	0.958*	0.986	0.984	1.028	1.000
	(0.0250)	(0.0223)	(0.0226)	(0.0223)	(0.0224)	(0.0310)	(0.0267)
Household income (centered)	1.044*	1.009	1.049**	1.017	1.011	1.008	1.011
	(0.0261)	(0.0226)	(0.0231)	(0.0234)	(0.0225)	(0.0273)	(0.0263)
Country (<i>ref. cat. UK</i>)							
Denmark	1.059	0.674**	0.832	1.143	0.542** *	0.847	0.842
	(0.229)	(0.114)	(0.139)	(0.184)	(0.0906)	(0.181)	(0.178)
Hungary	3.271***	1.015	0.641**	0.692*	1.004	2.047** *	0.753
	(0.722)	(0.205)	(0.129)	(0.138)	(0.196)	(0.478)	(0.197)
Spain	2.984***	1.459**	0.989	0.483***	0.746*	1.202	2.640***
	(0.591)	(0.254)	(0.170)	(0.0835)	(0.131)	(0.249)	(0.509)
Germany	0.973	1.546** *	0.972	0.755**	0.356** *	0.628**	1.106
	(0.176)	(0.216)	(0.133)	(0.103)	(0.0491)	(0.114)	(0.196)
Switzerland	1.734***	1.143	0.633***	0.624***	0.283** *	0.931	1.016
	(0.352)	(0.198)	(0.105)	(0.107)	(0.0497)	(0.183)	(0.216)
Male GCI	0.748	1.304	0.842	0.737	0.964	0.889	1.233
	(0.186)	(0.245)	(0.153)	(0.148)	(0.144)	(0.157)	(0.210)
Female GCI	0.983	0.978	1.028	0.975	0.945**	0.892** *	1.010
	(0.0264)	(0.0233)	(0.0240)	(0.0233)	(0.0229)	(0.0301)	(0.0313)
Losers of Feminism	0.306*	2.256	0.805	2.185*	3.208**	1.335	0.239*
	(0.212)	(1.222)	(0.569)	(0.984)	(1.578)	(0.716)	(0.193)
Losers of Globalisation	1.184	1.283	1.411	0.799	1.468	1.742*	1.327

Variables	(1) Integrating successfully into the labour market	(2) Accessing affordable housing social services and other goods	(3) Balancing paid employment and family duties	(4) Caring for children elderly relatives and other dependents	(5) Accessing good quality healthcare	(6) Getting a good education	(7) Exercising my civil rights and freedoms
Constant	(0.316) 0.159*** (0.0565)	(0.308) 0.337** (0.111) *	(0.342) 0.741 (0.230)	(0.238) 0.423*** (0.135)	(0.430) 1.254 (0.398)	(0.548) 0.287** (0.0988) *	(0.388) 0.135*** (0.0474)
Observations	3,885	3,894	3,894	3,894	3,894	3,894	3,894

Standard errors in parentheses
*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

Table A 24. Logit. DV: Issues perceived as a challenge – Women (2/2)

Variables	(8) Being able to express my sexual orientation	(9) Being physically safe	(10) Being a good mother/father	(11) Raising and educating children	(12) Forming a family	(13) Gaining the respect of others
Vote recall (UNTWIST scheme) (<i>ref. cat. RWPP</i>)						
MR	0.782 (0.266)	0.706** (0.103)	0.990 (0.164)	1.095 (0.172)	1.793*** (0.375)	0.866 (0.147)
ML	1.490 (0.410)	0.649*** (0.0888)	0.894 (0.142)	1.044 (0.153)	1.145 (0.238)	0.966 (0.154)
RL	2.363** (0.970)	0.425*** (0.0919)	0.606** (0.149)	0.800 (0.192)	0.722 (0.220)	0.833 (0.206)
Other	0.856 (0.451)	0.668* (0.142)	0.693 (0.184)	0.920 (0.207)	1.250 (0.355)	0.959 (0.270)
Age group (<i>ref. cat. 18-24</i>)						
25-39	0.694 (0.254)	1.028 (0.226)	1.532* (0.396)	1.198 (0.258)	1.106 (0.234)	0.616* (0.168)
40-54	0.450** (0.176)	1.214 (0.277)	0.942 (0.266)	0.731 (0.165)	0.299*** (0.0699)	0.408*** (0.117)
55-64	0.367** (0.166)	1.823** (0.443)	0.471** (0.154)	0.268*** (0.0702)	0.113*** (0.0350)	0.383*** (0.116)
65+	0.207** (0.144)	2.602*** (0.748)	0.520* (0.201)	0.263*** (0.0883)	0.139*** (0.0566)	0.620 (0.224)
Education (<i>ref. cat. ISCED 0-2</i>)						
ISCED 3-4	1.374 (0.504)	0.681*** (0.101)	0.902 (0.159)	0.891 (0.161)	0.598** (0.137)	0.812 (0.144)
ISCED 5-8	0.831 (0.306)	0.737** (0.108)	0.727* (0.123)	1.094 (0.191)	0.631** (0.139)	0.714* (0.132)
Social scale self- placement (centered)	1.008 (0.0742)	1.008 (0.0332)	0.978 (0.0370)	1.022 (0.0409)	0.977 (0.0468)	1.042 (0.0458)
Civil status (<i>ref. cat. Married</i>)						
Civil union	0.775 (0.478)	1.499 (0.420)	0.458** (0.166)	1.123 (0.335)	1.013 (0.320)	0.676 (0.315)
Cohabitation	0.952 (0.296)	1.142 (0.171)	0.576*** (0.113)	0.524*** (0.0864)	1.162 (0.219)	1.005 (0.190)
Divorced	0.353** (0.172)	1.068 (0.172)	0.677** (0.129)	0.806 (0.160)	0.323*** (0.118)	0.777 (0.152)
Separated	0.269 (0.272)	1.053 (0.339)	0.628 (0.223)	0.722 (0.251)	0.595 (0.328)	0.291*** (0.132)
Widowed	0.616 (0.493)	1.090 (0.214)	0.586** (0.160)	0.744 (0.199)	1.181 (0.456)	0.818 (0.204)
Single	1.190 (0.309)	0.961 (0.145)	0.490*** (0.105)	0.566*** (0.0965)	1.304 (0.244)	0.869 (0.159)
Number of	0.933	0.778***	1.231	1.398***	0.973	0.932

Variables	(8) Being able to express my sexual orientation	(9) Being physically safe	(10) Being a good mother/father	(11) Raising and educating children	(12) Forming a family	(13) Gaining the respect of others
children (centered)						
	(0.0813)	(0.0393)	(0.183)	(0.0678)	(0.0480)	(0.0434)
Religion (<i>ref. cat. Roman-Catholic</i>)						
Protestant	0.695 (0.237)	0.822 (0.118)	1.258 (0.205)	1.001 (0.157)	0.839 (0.173)	1.011 (0.167)
Eastern Orthodox	1.577 (0.787)	1.032 (0.474)	0.535 (0.292)	0.844 (0.404)	2.629* (1.319)	1.759 (1.123)
Other Christian	0.509 (0.238)	0.845 (0.248)	1.898* (0.646)	0.601 (0.196)	0.744 (0.317)	0.648 (0.232)
Jewish		0.560 (0.514)	2.325 (2.092)	1.144 (0.724)	0.660 (0.811)	1.776 (1.586)
Islam	0.328 (0.344)	1.000 (0.386)	0.861 (0.400)	1.810 (0.819)	0.463* (0.212)	0.908 (0.453)
Eastern religions	1.643 (1.190)	0.167*** (0.110)	1.917 (1.069)	1.094 (0.712)	0.710 (0.490)	1.729 (1.101)
Other non- Christian	2.567 (1.903)	0.407 (0.290)	2.008 (1.731)	0.278 (0.244)	0.156 (0.197)	1.419 (1.003)
No denomination	1.749* (0.583)	1.025 (0.163)	0.916 (0.175)	0.775 (0.133)	0.785 (0.165)	0.827 (0.171)
Other		1.649 (1.156)	2.279 (1.731)	0.858 (0.654)	1.579 (1.298)	
None	1.178 (0.403)	0.948 (0.153)	1.099 (0.205)	1.044 (0.181)	0.892 (0.209)	0.963 (0.186)
Level of religiosity (centered)	1.061 (0.0437)	0.980 (0.0181)	1.004 (0.0221)	1.007 (0.0212)	1.056** (0.0277)	1.036 (0.0241)
Employment (<i>ref. cat. >30h. pw</i>)						
<30h. pw	1.014 (0.343)	0.911 (0.143)	1.184 (0.193)	1.056 (0.171)	0.813 (0.180)	1.273 (0.228)
Self-empl.	0.440 (0.247)	1.005 (0.251)	1.292 (0.393)	1.484 (0.418)	1.401 (0.423)	1.075 (0.387)
Retired	0.824 (0.481)	1.166 (0.232)	1.185 (0.298)	1.025 (0.272)	1.032 (0.372)	0.876 (0.219)
Housemaker	1.266 (0.573)	1.036 (0.220)	1.433 (0.322)	1.097 (0.253)	1.191 (0.346)	1.155 (0.296)
Military serv.	2.136 (2.129)	0.944 (0.820)	0.0667** (0.0778)	0.0312** (0.0423)	0.523 (0.485)	3.932 (4.242)
Student	1.601	1.557	0.572	0.997	0.894	0.582

Variables	(8) Being able to express my sexual orientation	(9) Being physically safe	(10) Being a good mother/father	(11) Raising and educating children	(12) Forming a family	(13) Gaining the respect of others
Unemployed	(0.826) 1.326	(0.429) 0.546**	(0.217) 1.271	(0.317) 1.085	(0.278) 0.564	(0.220) 1.271
Disable	(0.605) 1.348	(0.156) 0.942	(0.367) 0.774	(0.297) 1.253	(0.199) 0.504	(0.431) 1.108
Other	(0.735) 0.571 (0.477)	(0.304) 0.902 (0.244)	(0.375) 1.090 (0.311)	(0.429) 1.313 (0.364)	(0.229) 0.580 (0.253)	(0.417) 0.833 (0.255)
Income satisfaction (<i>ref. cat. Comfortably</i>)						
Coping	1.034 (0.283)	1.114 (0.125)	1.008 (0.133)	1.174 (0.147)	1.037 (0.161)	1.171 (0.167)
Difficult	0.869 (0.367)	1.188 (0.192)	0.908 (0.179)	1.112 (0.202)	1.164 (0.251)	1.117 (0.236)
Very difficult	2.420* (1.192)	2.008*** (0.513)	0.745 (0.223)	1.635 (0.503)	0.614 (0.254)	1.245 (0.421)
Personal income (centered)	1.085 (0.0618)	1.006 (0.0231)	1.001 (0.0271)	1.002 (0.0251)	1.056 (0.0378)	1.036 (0.0298)
Household income (centered)	1.024 (0.0487)	1.010 (0.0229)	0.983 (0.0268)	1.060** (0.0259)	0.968 (0.0337)	0.955 (0.0290)
Country (<i>ref. cat. UK</i>)						
Denmark	0.451* (0.185)	0.391*** (0.0669)	1.573** (0.295)	0.646** (0.133)	2.018*** (0.532)	1.238 (0.246)
Hungary	0.731 (0.318)	0.282*** (0.0586)	0.439*** (0.105)	1.094 (0.235)	1.483 (0.442)	0.631* (0.160)
Spain	0.498* (0.195)	0.324*** (0.0574)	0.510*** (0.107)	0.930 (0.184)	2.063*** (0.551)	0.617** (0.140)
Germany	0.770 (0.241)	0.383*** (0.0536)	0.720** (0.116)	0.921 (0.144)	1.313 (0.282)	1.079 (0.185)
Switzerland	1.162 (0.407)	0.341*** (0.0581)	0.655** (0.132)	0.799 (0.152)	1.324 (0.347)	1.293 (0.257)
Male GCI	1.355 (0.285)	1.128 (0.223)	1.189 (0.262)	0.505** (0.146)	0.848 (0.249)	0.944 (0.183)
Female GCI	1.081 (0.0528)	1.023 (0.0251)	1.061** (0.0296)	0.998 (0.0266)	0.983 (0.0381)	1.062** (0.0322)
Losers of Feminism		1.378 (0.765)	2.004 (1.373)	0.937 (0.645)	3.389** (1.816)	0.859 (0.687)
Losers of Globalisation	2.961** (1.371)	1.141 (0.319)	1.328 (0.446)	1.543 (0.516)	1.537 (0.686)	0.523 (0.233)
Constant	0.0789*** (0.0572)	1.264 (0.403)	0.519* (0.192)	0.559* (0.186)	0.308*** (0.125)	0.462** (0.180)

	(8)	(9)	(10)	(11)	(12)	(13)
Variables	Being able to express my sexual orientation	Being physically safe	Being a good mother/father	Raising and educating children	Forming a family	Gaining the respect of others
Observations	3,847	3,894	3,894	3,894	3,894	3,885

Standard errors in parentheses
 *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

Table A 25. Linear regression and logit. DV: Voting and closeness to RWPP

Variables	(1) Closene ss	(2) Closene ss - Men	(3) Closen ess - Wome n	(4) PTV	(5) PTV - Men	(6) PTV - Wome n	(7) Vote recall for RWPP	(8) Vote recall for RWPP - Men	(9) Vote recall for RWPP - Wome n
Vote recall (UNTWIST scheme) (<i>ref. cat. RWPP</i>)									
MR	0.0353* **	0.0317* **	- 3.398* **						
	(0.0048 8)	(0.0064 6)	(0.202)						
ML	0.00891 ***	0.00621 ***	- 4.534* **						
	(0.0013 5)	(0.0014 6)	(0.209)						
RL	0.00654 ***	0.00252 ***	- 4.633* **						
	(0.0018 5)	(0.0011 2)	(0.376)						
Other	0.0164* **	0.0206* **	- 4.594* **						
	(0.0036 4)	(0.0067 2)	(0.297)						
Gender (<i>ref. cat. Men</i>)									
Women	0.800**			- 0.158* **			1.212* *		
	(0.0887)			(0.059 8)			(0.091 2)		
Age group (<i>ref. cat. 18-24</i>)									
25-39	1.118 (0.277)	1.136 (0.382)	0.255 (0.349)	-0.134 (0.142)	0.102 (0.222)	- 0.318* (0.179)	0.886 (0.145)	0.584* (0.159) *	0.982 (0.207)
40-54	0.987 (0.256)	1.019 (0.354)	0.190 (0.368)	- 0.283* (0.149)	0.084 2 (0.235)	- 0.576* ** (0.190)	0.948 (0.158)	0.645 (0.182)	1.024 (0.218)
55-64	0.927	0.935	0.171	- 0.633* (0.149)	-0.262 (0.235)	- 0.896* (0.190)	0.812 (0.158)	0.714 (0.182)	0.755 (0.218)

Variables	(1) Closeness	(2) Closeness - Men	(3) Closeness - Women	(4) PTV	(5) PTV - Men	(6) PTV - Women	(7) Vote recall for RWPP	(8) Vote recall for RWPP - Men	(9) Vote recall for RWPP - Women
	(0.258)	(0.351)	(0.395)	(0.155)	(0.241)	(0.201)	(0.145)	(0.210)	(0.175)
65+	0.957	0.908	0.291	-	-	-	0.635*	0.673	0.526*
	(0.299)	(0.393)	(0.437)	(0.174)	(0.271)	(0.224)	(0.137)	(0.233)	(0.153)
Education (<i>ref. cat. ISCED 0-2</i>)									
ISCED 3-4	0.897	0.991	-0.245	-	1.02e-05	-	1.028	0.788	1.258
	(0.128)	(0.202)	(0.210)	(0.095)	(0.141)	(0.129)	(0.120)	(0.144)	(0.198)
ISCED 5-8	0.785*	0.789	-0.343	-	-	-	0.576*	0.481*	0.662*
	(0.112)	(0.164)	(0.209)	(0.091)	(0.135)	(0.123)	(0.067)	(0.087)	(0.106)
Social scale self-placement (centered)	0.988	1.009	-	0.0129	0.035	0.0022	0.886*	0.884*	0.890*
	(0.0342)	(0.0519)	(0.048)	(0.022)	(0.034)	(0.029)	(0.023)	(0.037)	(0.030)
Civil status (<i>ref. cat. Married</i>)									
Civil union	0.997	0.664	0.246	0.538*	0.500	0.572*	1.343	0.709	1.804*
	(0.332)	(0.390)	(0.325)	(0.203)	(0.287)	(0.293)	(0.272)	(0.283)	(0.448)
Cohabitation	1.351*	1.202	0.368*	0.223*	0.362	0.0657	1.122	1.297	1.012
	(0.217)	(0.300)	(0.207)	(0.095)	(0.156)	(0.116)	(0.133)	(0.252)	(0.156)
Divorced	1.323	1.774**	-	0.152	0.319	-	1.108	1.338	1.011
	(0.232)	(0.462)	(0.239)	(0.111)	(0.196)	(0.127)	(0.142)	(0.277)	(0.169)
Separate	1.222	1.341	0.0600	0.546*	0.729	0.382	1.377	2.033*	1.126

Variables	(1) Closeness	(2) Closeness - Men	(3) Closeness - Women	(4) PTV	(5) PTV - Men	(6) PTV - Women	(7) Vote recall for RWPP	(8) Vote recall for RWPP - Men	(9) Vote recall for RWPP - Women
d	(0.492)	(0.697)	(0.679)	(0.195)	(0.318)	(0.240)	(0.338)	(0.816)	(0.362)
Widowed	1.003	1.681	-0.407*	0.256*	0.773	-0.0011	1.139	0.769	1.293
Single	1.168	1.139	0.103	0.131	0.174	0.0539	1.037	1.060	0.992
Number of children (centered)	1.128**	1.122**	0.115**	0.0850	0.081	0.0925	1.046*	0.983	1.082*
Religion (<i>ref. cat. Roman-Catholic</i>)	(0.0363)	(0.0629)	(0.0372)	(0.0269)	(0.0424)	(0.0356)	(0.0284)	(0.0486)	(0.0355)
Protestant	1.271*	1.297	0.203	0.134	0.239	0.0750	0.975	0.915	1.013
Eastern Orthodox	2.238*	2.254	0.469	1.253**	1.069	1.496**	1.003	2.344*	0.651
Other Christian	1.663*	1.121	0.932*	0.305	0.293	0.360	0.702*	0.985	0.639*
Jewish	1.703	0.254	2.086**	0.462	-0.290	1.415*	0.435		1.037
Islam	0.602	0.282	0.267	0.0757	-0.214	0.372	0.426**	0.461	0.432*
Eastern religions	1.269	0.947	0.773	0.0174	-0.164	0.424	0.561	0.674	0.567

Variables	(1) Closeness	(2) Closeness - Men	(3) Closeness - Women	(4) PTV	(5) PTV - Men	(6) PTV - Women	(7) Vote recall for RWPP	(8) Vote recall for RWPP - Men	(9) Vote recall for RWPP - Women
Other non-Christian	0.741 (0.273)	0.500* (0.193)	-0.260 (0.589)	0.381 (0.413)	-0.279 (0.495)	0.767 (0.610)	5.133** (1.991)	3.478* (2.130)	7.719** (4.326)
No denomination	0.792 (0.134)	0.941 (0.230)	-0.373 (0.241)	0.0369 (0.085)	0.043 (0.136)	0.0345 (0.108)	0.882 (0.111)	0.817 (0.168)	0.966 (0.157)
Other	0.655 (0.537)		0.374 (0.830)	-0.107 (0.272)	-0.345 (0.373)	0.193 (0.467)			
None	1.083 (0.175)	1.262 (0.286)	-0.123 (0.235)	0.122 (0.106)	0.064 (0.167)	0.152 (0.131)	1.270* (0.158)	1.689** (0.336)	1.032 (0.170)
Level of religiosity (centered)	1.056** (0.0200)	1.097** (0.0306)	0.0194 (0.0263)	0.0525*** (0.0129)	0.034 (0.0207)	0.0695*** (0.0160)	1.007 (0.0139)	1.009 (0.0225)	1.010 (0.0182)
Employment (<i>ref. cat. >30h. pw</i>) <30h. pw	1.182 (0.233)	2.015** (0.673)	- (0.238)	0.166 (0.108)	0.364 (0.233)	0.111 (0.121)	0.803* (0.105)	0.466* (0.140)	0.878 (0.133)
Self-empl.	0.864 (0.198)	1.008 (0.327)	-0.294 (0.344)	- (0.136)	-0.154 (0.196)	0.119 (0.188)	0.957 (0.167)	0.776 (0.200)	1.117 (0.273)
Military serv.	0.294 (0.464)	0.435 (0.921)	-1.931 (1.472)	0.587 (0.955)	0.645 (1.367)	0.406 (0.959)	0.998 (0.590)	0.526 (0.504)	1.471 (1.102)
Retired	0.879 (0.170)	0.818 (0.219)	-0.137 (0.284)	- (0.114)	-0.187 (0.167)	0.0975 (0.151)	0.675* (0.105)	0.528** (0.123)	0.805 (0.174)

Variables	(1) Closeness	(2) Closeness - Men	(3) Closeness - Women	(4) PTV	(5) PTV - Men	(6) PTV - Women	(7) Vote recall for RWPP	(8) Vote recall for RWPP - Men	(9) Vote recall for RWPP - Women
Housemaker	1.007 (0.252)	1.212 (0.865)	-0.0789 (0.274)	0.231 (0.182)	0.786 (0.636)	0.141 (0.193)	0.790 (0.146)	0.381 (0.245)	0.873 (0.172)
Student	0.836 (0.268)	0.616 (0.256)	0.138 (0.500)	-0.237 (0.180)	-0.0876 (0.295)	-0.430* (0.208)	0.440** (0.120)	0.456* (0.192)	0.413* (0.151)
Unemployed	0.901 (0.226)	0.633 (0.260)	0.0793 (0.326)	0.217 (0.168)	0.00936 (0.267)	0.290 (0.216)	1.021 (0.207)	1.220 (0.429)	0.961 (0.240)
Disable	0.749 (0.285)	0.472 (0.367)	-0.0220 (0.327)	-0.191 (0.181)	-0.121 (0.309)	-0.292 (0.202)	0.984 (0.260)	1.235 (0.527)	0.832 (0.295)
Other	1.212 (0.295)	2.025* (0.816)	-0.0701 (0.328)	-0.322* (0.177)	-0.192 (0.276)	-0.495* (0.223)	0.895 (0.193)	0.951 (0.332)	0.737 (0.207)
Income satisfaction (<i>ref. cat. Comfortably</i>)									
Coping	1.215* (0.131)	1.501** (0.225)	-0.0463 (0.159)	0.215** (0.066)	0.225** (0.102)	0.235** (0.082)	1.284** (0.114)	1.202 (0.168)	1.417** (0.167)
Difficult	1.274 (0.212)	1.659** (0.413)	0.0425 (0.226)	0.430** (0.103)	0.369** (0.163)	0.533** (0.129)	1.402** (0.176)	1.022 (0.217)	1.810** (0.294)
Very difficult	1.163 (0.328)	1.111 (0.563)	0.138 (0.344)	0.369* (0.166)	0.203 (0.255)	0.583** (0.215)	1.114 (0.227)	1.098 (0.389)	1.270 (0.325)
Personal income (centered)	1.044* (0.0262)	1.022 (0.0421)	0.0604* (0.0322)	0.0657*** (0.0163)	-0.00770 (0.0274)	0.116** (0.0199)	0.994 (0.0191)	1.023 (0.0349)	0.988 (0.0241)

Variables	(1) Closeness	(2) Closeness - Men	(3) Closeness - Women	(4) PTV	(5) PTV - Men	(6) PTV - Women	(7) Vote recall for RWPP	(8) Vote recall for RWPP - Men	(9) Vote recall for RWPP - Women
Household income (centered)	0.984	0.985	- 0.0199	- 0.0553 ***	- 0.027 3	- 0.0679 ***	0.972	0.917* **	1.001
	(0.0256)	(0.0401)	(0.034 2)	(0.015 4)	(0.027 3)	(0.017 1)	(0.018 0)	(0.030 4)	(0.023 4)
Country (<i>ref. cat. UK</i>)									
Denmark	1.289	1.049	0.457* 0.0030 9	- 0.0030 9	- 0.081 8	0.0766	1.310* *	0.914	1.688* **
	(0.206)	(0.232)	(0.237)	(0.103)	(0.160)	(0.128)	(0.165)	(0.179)	(0.290)
Hungary	0.708	0.504**	-0.109 0.306)	0.264* *	-0.123 0.178)	0.530* **	5.896* **	4.828* **	7.798* **
	(0.149)	(0.153)	(0.306)	(0.111)	(0.178)	(0.141)	(0.803)	(1.050)	(1.448)
Spain	1.356* 0.220	1.361	0.301 0.233)	- 0.413* **	- 0.493 ***	- 0.346* **	0.533* **	0.356* **	0.721* 0.136
	(0.220)	(0.316)	(0.233)	(0.101)	(0.153)	(0.133)	(0.077 0)	(0.085 8)	(0.136)
Germany	0.502** *	0.512** *	- 0.706* **	0.0735	- 0.039 0	0.202	0.735* **	0.480* **	1.026
	(0.0708)	(0.103)	(0.199)	(0.104)	(0.161)	(0.131)	(0.087 7)	(0.090 1)	(0.166)
Switzerland	0.802	0.808	-0.260 0.269)	0.329* **	- 0.077 8	0.723* **	1.832* **	1.938* **	1.965* **
	(0.140)	(0.190)	(0.269)	(0.109)	(0.158)	(0.147)	(0.236)	(0.381)	(0.345)
Male GCI	1.008	1.009	-0.177						
	(0.0392)	(0.0414)	(0.209)						
Female GCI	0.870** *	1.014	- 0.129* **						
	(0.0311)	(0.397)	(0.034 5)						
Losers of Feminis	3.134**	6.461**	-0.141	0.607* *	1.276 ***	-0.389	2.690* **	4.003* **	1.801

Variables	(1) Closeness	(2) Closeness - Men	(3) Closeness - Women	(4) PTV	(5) PTV - Men	(6) PTV - Women	(7) Vote recall for RWPP	(8) Vote recall for RWPP - Men	(9) Vote recall for RWPP - Women
m	(1.465)	(5.005)	(0.483)	(0.308)	(0.377)	(0.364)	(0.806)	(1.639)	(0.862)
Losers of Globalisation	2.132** *	2.382**	0.636	1.207* **	1.572 ***	0.738* *	2.437* **	1.842* *	3.025* **
Ideology (left-right)	(0.584)	(0.920)	(0.419)	(0.234)	(0.330)	(0.299)	(0.421)	(0.507)	(0.697)
Constant	9.072** *	8.761** *	2.097* **	0.390* **	0.412 ***	0.365* **	1.579* **	1.675* **	1.524* **
Observations	7,044	3,139	3,899	8,758	3,858	4,900	7,019	3,121	3,883
R-squared				0.236	0.243	0.250			

Standard errors in parentheses
*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

